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**A synopsis of the earthworms (Clitellata, Megadrili)
of South Asia including Myanmar**

by

S. PRASANTH NARAYANAN, R. PALIWAL, A.P. THOMAS & J.M. JULKA

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A synopsis of the earthworms (Clitellata, Megadrili) of South Asia including Myanmar

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Abstract. A first comprehensive summary of the earthworm species hitherto known from South Asia including Myanmar is presented. This work is based on an extensive review of available published data covering over a period of 181 years (1844–2026 April 7th), highlights the diversity and provides a synopsis of their distribution in South Asia including Myanmar. It includes the currently used valid scientific name, type locality, type repository information and the species distribution in all the nine countries within South Asia-Myanmar region. Apart from these, here we critically reviewed the original descriptions and reinvestigated the type materials of *Progizzardus varadiamensis* Nair, 2010, *Dichogaster vellanikkarae* Jaya, Aja & Nair, 2011, *Megascolex kavalaianus* Stephenson, 1915, and *Megascolex trivandranus* Stephenson, 1916. As a result, *D. vellanikkarae*, is a junior synonym of *Dichogaster bolau* (Michaelsen, 1891), while *M. kavalaianus* and *M. trivandranus*, are found to be junior synonyms of *Megascolex insignis* Michaelsen, 1910, respectively. Whereas, due to the immature state of the type materials, *P. varadiamensis* represent a *Glyphidrilus* species, most probably *G. annandalei* Michaelsen, 1910. In total, earthworm fauna of South Asia-Myanmar region comprises 698 species belonging to 78 genera, spread over 9 families. Of these, 85% are endemic, 9% exotic peregrine, followed by native peregrines and others. The family Megascolecidae and the genus *Drawida* exhibit high species diversity. Among the countries, India has the highest species richness with 503 species followed by Myanmar (208 spp.) and least number is recorded from the Maldives (2 spp.). India has the highest number of endemic species (384 spp. *sensu stricto*), followed by Myanmar and Sri Lanka, have 107 and 58 endemic species respectively. Meanwhile, there are another 44 species found endemic to the South Asia-Myanmar area, but have been distributed in two or more countries of the region. Taxonomic investigations on the earthworm fauna have not been carried out comprehensively in most of the South Asian countries. The present work can serve as a basis for further studies on the regional distribution and diversity of earthworm fauna that would help to evolve conservation strategies.

Keywords. Annelida, endemic, India, Indomalayan realm, Maldives, Sri Lanka, synonymy.

INTRODUCTION

South Asia is an important region in the world, spread over an area of 5.1 million km² and which is 11.51% of the Asian continent and 3.4% of the global surface area (Faqeerzada *et al.* 2018). Myanmar is a Southeast Asian country, but in certain regional studies it is often grouped with

South Asia, mainly due to historical or ecological contexts, as Myanmar geographically shares borders with India and Bangladesh. South Asia together with Myanmar (span from 06° N to 38° N latitude and 60° E to 101° E longitude) is having a total land area of approximately 5.88 million km². It is one of the cradle of ancient civilization and an important portion of the Indian subcontinent.

At present, South Asia is the region with high human population and based on the latest United Nations estimate, the region's current population is over 2 billion people, which is equivalent to 25.29% of the world population (Bhat 2024). The region 'South Asia' includes eight countries namely, Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, and we have included Myanmar also in the work due to its geographical proximity (Fig. 1). The topography, climate, and habitats of the region are exceptionally varied, making it one of the most diverse regions in the world. The region is home to mountains (Himalayas, Karakoram, Hindu Kush, portions of Hengduan), hills (Aravalli, Shivaliks, Vindhyas, Satpuras, Western Ghats, Eastern Ghats, Khasi, Garo, Naga, Dawna, Karen, Tenasserim, etc.), deserts (Thar, Dasht-e-Margo, etc.), plateaus (Deccan, Malwa, Chota Nagpur, Shan, etc.), wetlands, coastal zones, continental (Andaman and Nicobar) and oceanic (Lakshadweep, Maldives) islands, rivers (Helmand, Indus, Ganges, Brahmaputra, Mahanadi, Godawari, Irrawady (Ayeyarwady), Salween, etc.), etc. The

climate from Afghanistan, Pakistan and north-western India is arid and highly seasonal, whereas the Peninsular India is chiefly at the influence of monsoon. Sri Lanka is having more tropical climate due to its proximity to the tropics. The region has various kinds of vegetation from sparse arid grassland vegetation to scrub and thorn forests, alpine meadows, coniferous forests in the mountains especially in the Himalayas, relict pockets of evergreen forests in the Western Ghats, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, North-eastern Indian Hills. Tropical evergreen forests are found in high rainfall zones of Tanintharyi Region and the Rakhine coast of Myanmar. Other forests like, semi evergreen, deciduous, moist deciduous, mangrove forests etc. are also found in various portions of this region. This region is very rich in biodiversity with high rate of endemism, most of the endemic flora and fauna are confined to the biodiversity hotspots. Out of the 36 recognised biodiversity hotspots of the world, five includes the portions of South Asia-Myanmar Region, viz., Himalaya, Western Ghats-Sri Lanka, Indo-Burma, Sundaland, and the Mountains of Central Asia

Figure 1. Location of the South Asian countries including Myanmar (adapted from Google Earth)

(Koeing 2016). South Asia-Myanmar is part of the world's two major zoogeographical realms, Palaearctic and Indomalaya (Oriental). Most of South Asia falls in the Indomalayan Zoogeographical realm.

South Asia including Myanmar is one of the most earthworm rich regions of the world. Taxonomic studies on the earthworms of the region started in the second quarter of the 19th century (Narayanan *et al.* 2021a) by the description of *Megascolex caeruleus* by Robert Templeton in the year 1844 from Sri Lanka. Studies on the earthworm fauna in South Asia-Myanmar had been very uneven since Templeton's description of the first earthworm species. The initial active period, though brief, was towards the third quarter of the nineteenth century by Schmarda (1861) and Perrier (1872). Schmarda (1861) described 4 new species from Sri Lanka *viz.*, *Perichaeta brachycycla* (= *Megascolex brachycyclus*), *Perichaeta cingulata* (= *M. cingulatus*), *Perichaeta leucocycla* (= *M. leucocyclus*) and *Perichaeta viridis* (= *Megascolex? viridis*). Of these, generic status of *Perichaeta viridis* is still uncertain (Narayanan *et al.* 2021a). Later Perrier (1872) described *Moniligaster deshayesi* and *Perichaeta houletti* (= *Metaphire houletti*) from India, of this *Metaphire houletti* is a well-known peregrine species. Towards the end of the nineteenth century (1876–1900), Beddard (1883, 1886, 1890a), Bourne (1886, 1889, 1894a, b), Rosa (1888, 1890a, 1892, 1894), Benham (1893), Michaelsen (1897a, 1900) and Fedarb (1898a, b) contributed to the earthworm fauna of the region. Together they described 62 new species, of these 26 were from Sri Lanka (Beddard 1886, 1890a, Rosa 1892, 1894, Michaelsen 1897a, 1899), 13 were from Myanmar (Rosa 1888, 1890°, Beddard 1892) and the rest are from India (Beddard 1883, Bourne 1886, 1889, 1894a, b, Fedarb 1898). Later, Beddard (1900), Michaelsen (1907a, 1909, 1910a, 1913a), Cognetti (1911), Stephenson (1914a, b, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1921a, 1923, 1924a, b, 1925a, b), Gates (1925a, b, c, 1926 a, b, 1927, 1929, 1930, 1931, 1932, 1933, 1936, 1937a, b, 1938a, b, 1939a, b, 1940a, b, 1942, 1943, 1945a, b, 1947, 1962, 1972), Aiyer (1929), *etc.* immensely

contributed to the South Asian – Myanmarese earthworm fauna.

The first quarter of the 20th century is the 'golden era' for the Indian (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a) as well as the regions' earthworm taxonomy (Fig. 2). Julka (1991) summarized the history of taxonomical investigations on Indian earthworms since their inception to the late 20th century. India is the only South Asian country where taxonomical studies on the earthworm fauna are kept active since the independence from the European colonists. Later, in the first three quarters of the 20th century, Michaelsen (1907, 1909, 1910a, 1913), Cognetti (1911), Stephenson (1914, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1921a, 1923, 1924a, b, 1925a, b), Aiyer (1929), Gates (1937a, b, 1938a, b, 1939a, b, 1940a, b, 1945a, b, c, d, 1947, 1956, 1962, 1972) *etc.* immensely contributed to the South Asian and Myanmarese earthworm fauna. Subsequent noteworthy contributions on earthworms were by Julka (1975, 1976a, b, 1977, 1978, 1979, 1981, 1982, 1983, 1988), Jamieson (1977a, b), Julka & Paliwal (1993, 1994), Reynolds (1994), Reynolds *et al.* (1995), Julka *et al.* (1997) *etc.* The Indian list is being expanded by the discovery of several new taxa and new reports from different portions of the country particularly from the Western Ghats and Northeastern Hills and several regional new records (Julka *et al.* 2004; Narayanan *et al.* 2014a, b, 2016b, c, 2017, 2019a, b, c, 2020, 2021b, 2022, 2023b, c, d, 2024a, b, c, d, 2025a, b, c, d, Ahmed & Julka 2017, Kumari *et al.* 2017, Kumar *et al.* 2018, Sathrumithra *et al.* 2018, Anuja *et al.* 2020, 2023, Lone *et al.* 2020, 2022, Thakur *et al.* 2020, Has-yagar *et al.* 2021, 2022, Mustafa *et al.* 2023, Tiwari *et al.* 2021, 2022, 2024, 2025a, b, c, d, 2026, Ahmed *et al.* 2022, 2023a, b, 2025, 2026a, b, Chang *et al.* 2024, Hasan *et al.* 2024, Naik *et al.* 2024, Rodingpuia *et al.* 2024, Ardra *et al.* 2026, Fahis *et al.* 2026). Recently Bantaowong *et al.* (2020) and Chanabun *et al.* (2020) contributed to the Myanmarese earthworm fauna with two new species descriptions and new reports. But in other South Asian countries taxonomical studies on the earthworm fauna is rather neglected or standstill state (*e.g.* Sri Lanka Narayanan *et al.* 2021a).

Figure 2. Valid earthworm species/subspecies described from the South Asia-Myanmar region at different time intervals

Studies on the megadrile worms in South Asia have a long history of about 181 years. Despite the high earthworm diversity, a complete list of earthworms of South Asian countries including Myanmar has not been published. Moreover, many changes in nomenclature and taxonomy of earthworms have occurred in the period. The aim of this study is, therefore, to summarise the faunal information on the earthworms of the region with updated nomenclature that provides a base for further investigations in the countries of the region and it is hoped that this will be useful for the regional governments as well. Apart from their importance in identification, checklists form a source of useful information on the species distribution and endemism, so that conservation strategies can be developed (Narayanan *et al.* 2016a). As a result, 698 valid species and subspecies are recorded and much is still to be learned about the earthworm diversity of the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Current synopsis is based upon an exhaustive review of literature published over 181 years from the description of the first species from the region by Templeton (1844). The cut-off date for taxonomic decisions and distribution information is April 7th, 2026. Information on the number of species and distributional records are mostly

derived from regional faunal works, checklists and original publications. Precisely, the data is gathered for each country in the region is as follows – Afghanistan (Omodeo 1959, 1962, Gates 1972, Aminjan *et al.* 2021), Bangladesh (Reynolds 1994, Reynolds *et al.* 1995, Das & Reynolds 2003, Bahar *et al.* 2015, Narayanan *et al.* 2024e), species mentioned in the work of Makin *et al.* (2014) has been omitted here, since their identification are based on non taxonomical literature, Bhutan (Julka & Halder 1975, Soota & Halder 1981, Suberi & Koirala 2021), India (mainly from Narayanan *et al.* 2023a, who summarised the works carried out in India from 1872–2022 and the rest [2023–2026 7th April] gathered from Ahmed *et al.* 2023a, b, 2025, 2026a, b, Mustafa *et al.* 2023, Narayanan *et al.* 2024a, b, c, e, 2025a, b, c, d, Chang *et al.* 2024, Naik *et al.* 2024, Rodingpuia *et al.* 2024, Tiwari *et al.* 2024, 2025a, b, c, d, 2026, Kumar *et al.* 2025, Ardra *et al.* 2026, Fahis *et al.* 2026) and the species mentioned in the work of Khan *et al.* (2024) from the Pakistan Occupied Kashmir region of India has been omitted here, since most of the species recorded cannot be identified based on the literature cited in the work, Maldives (Beddard 1903), Nepal (Michaelsen 1907, Gates 1934, 1937a, 1938, 1955, Sims 1963, Neemann *et al.* 2007, Julka *et al.* 2009, Narayanan *et al.* 2024e; Singh & Khanal 2025), Pakistan (Parshad 1916, Stephenson 1916, 1917, 1920, 1922a, 1926, Gates 1937a, 1962a, 1972, Ghafoor *et al.* 1988, 2008, Ghafoor & Qureshi 1999, Rafique & Rana 2001, Sarwar *et al.* 2006, Hussian *et al.* 2022, Narayanan *et al.* 2024e, Raza *et al.* 2024), Sri Lanka (Beddard 1886a, Rosa 1892, 1894, Michaelsen 1897a, 1907, 1909, 1910, Stephenson 1913, 1915, 1916, Gates 1941a, Szederjesi *et al.* 2019, Narayanan *et al.* 2021a, 2024e, *etc.*) and Myanmar (Rosa 1888, 1890a, Michaelsen 1907, Gates 1925a, b, c, 1926 a, b, 1927, 1929, 1930, 1931, 1932, 1933, 1936, 1942, 1943, 1954, 1955, 1958a, 1961a, 1962a, 1972, Blakemore 2006a, 2007b, Aung 2014, Csuzdi *et al.* 2015, Bantaowong *et al.* 2020, Chanabun *et al.* 2020, Narayanan *et al.* 2024e).

In 1972 Gates published a detailed work entitled 'Burmese earthworms', but this also included

many regional species which had not yet been reported from Myanmar proper. In other words, 'Burmese earthworms' include species that are confined to the contiguous regions of India (Northeastern Indian states, Union Territory of Andaman and Nicobar Islands), China (Yunnan), and Thailand (Blakemore 2006a). Therefore, in this work we have included species known within the political borders of Myanmar proper. Apart from these, several exotic species (especially various lumbricid taxa) included in the Gates (1972) list are without any accurate locations from the country (Blakemore 2006a). Hence, here they are included with a question mark.

Distribution of various genera and widespread or exotic species are from Stephenson (1923), Gates (1972), Easton (1984), Julka (1988), Csuzdi & Zisci (2003), Csuzdi & Pavlíček (2005a, b, 2009), Csuzdi (2005), Shen & Yeo (2005), Talavera (2007), González *et al.* (2007), Chang *et al.* (2009), Plisko (2010), Christoffersen (2011), Szederjesi (2011, 2013a, b, 2015, 2017, 2019, 2023, 2025), Blakemore (2012a), James & Divina (2012), Mısırlıoğlu (2012), Nxele (2012), Pop *et al.* (2012), Szederjesi *et al.* (2012, 2013a, b, 2014, 2018a, b, 2019), Farhadi *et al.* (2013), Kutuzović & Kutuzović (2013), Stonjanović & Milutinović (2013), Stonjanović *et al.* (2013), Csuzdi & Sciberras (2014), Lehmitz *et al.* (2014), Shen *et al.* (2015), Nguyen *et al.* (2016), Reynolds & Reeves (2018), Reynolds (2022), Abdullaev *et al.* (2023), Kamal *et al.* (2023), Mustafa *et al.* (2023), Narayanan *et al.* (2023a, 2024e), Pavlíček *et al.* (2023), Gabriac *et al.* (2024), Kokhia *et al.* (2024), Seesamut *et al.* (2024), Alvarez-Abreu & Carrera-Martinez (2025), Chergui *et al.* (2025), Popović *et al.* (2025) and Han *et al.* (2026).

There are a number of species' names published from South Asia, which are not published according to the criteria of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (Art. 8.5.1., 8.5.3, & 78.2.4) (ICZN 2012). Intrasubspecific names coined after 1961 are not available names, and names of such taxa are outside the scope of the ICZN (Art. 45.5) (ICZN 2012) and are therefore not available for scientific purposes. Hence, such

Nomina nuda and infrasubspecific names (see Neesemann *et al.* 2007, Aja & Jaya 2016, Mandal *et al.* 2017a, b, Selvamuthukumar *et al.* 2025) are excluded from this work.

Classification

Higher and lower level classification in oligochaetous-clitellates are in much debates and in constant change (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a). Order-level classification proposed by Schmelz *et al.* (2021) is followed in this work. Classification of megascolecoid earthworms at the family level is not yet stabilized (Fender & McKey-Fender 1990, Blakemore 2005, 2013a, Pavlíček *et al.* 2012). The recent proposal by Blakemore (2013a) to place megascolecoid earthworm taxa among several subfamilies appears to be a step in the right direction (Narayanan *et al.* 2016a) but to date there has been limited acceptance of these subfamilies (Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2023). The genus *Dichogaster* is the most speciose genus of the family Benhamiidae (Brown *et al.* 2023), until recently this genus was considered as a member of the family Octochaetidae (Julka 1988a), but later placed in family Acanthodrilidae as a subfamily Benhamiinae by Csuzdi (1996). Currently Benhamiinae is treated as Family Benhamiidae (James & Gamiette 2016, Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2023). But in the recent, Glasby *et al.* (2025) key to the 'Annelida family-level taxa' family Benhamiidae is placed under the Acanthodrilidae family. Even though, here we have retained it as a valid family. Brown *et al.* (2023) and Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* (2023) have been followed for the family and genera level classification.

Format

Generally, families, genera within families and species within genera are arranged alphabetically following Narayanan *et al.* (2016a). Whereas, nominotypical subspecies are presented first whenever discussing the subspecies. Information on each species includes the following records: 1) Scientific name; 2) Original publication, synonyms and further pertinent redescrptions; 3) Type locality; 4) Type material, data about the type material was gathered from the original publications or from Reynolds and Cook (1976), Julka

Table 1. List of depository of type material hosting institutions, list is arranged alphabetically after the acronym of institutions

Acronym	Depository institution	Place	Country
BMNH (= NHMUK)	British Museum (Natural History), now Natural History Museum	London	United Kingdom
CTU	Can Tho University	Can Tho City	Vietnam
CUMZ	Chulalongkorn University, Museum of Zoology	Bangkok	Thailand
DHSGV-ZDM	Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya Zoology Department Museum	Sagar	India
HARC-ZSI (= HAZFS ZSI)	Zoological Survey of India, High Altitude Regional Centre	Solan	India
HNHM	Hungarian Natural History Museum	Budapest	Hungary
JWRC	John W. Reynolds Oligochaete Collection (all specimens have now been transferred to the Canadian Museum of Nature in Alymer, Quebec, Canada)	Ontario	Canada
LKCNHM (= ZRC)	Lee Kong Chian Natural History Museum, National University of Singapore (ex Raffles Museum of Biodiversity Research Collection)	Clementi	Singapore
MGDG	Museo Civico di Storia Naturale ‘Giacomo’	Genova	Italy
MHNG	Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle	Geneva	Switzerland
MNHN	Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle	Paris	France
MNHU (= ZMB)	Zoologisches Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt Universität (now Museum für Naturkunde Berlin)	Berlin	Germany
MZUSP	Museu de Zoologia da Universidade de São Paulo	São Paulo	Brazil
MZUT	Museo ed Instituto di Zoologia Sistemática dell'Università di Torino	Torino	Italy
NHRS (= NHMS)	Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Stockholm National Museum of Natural Sciences, National Museums of Canada (Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle)	Stockholm	Sweden
NMNS (= NMCIC)	La Collection Ouest-Européenne Centrale d'Oligochètes	Ottawa	Canada
OEEO (= CO-ECO)	Pachhunga University College Zoological Museum	Sully	France
PUCZM	Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie	Aizwal	India
RNHL (= RMNH)	The Zoological Collections, Oxford University Museum	Leiden	Netherlands
UMOU	Tall Timbers research Station (Transferred to USNM)	Oxford	England
TTRS	United States National Museum	Tallahassee	United States of America
USNM	University Museum of Zoology, Cambridge University	Washington D.C.	United States of America
UZMC	Naturhistorisches Museum Wien	Cambridge	United Kingdom
WNHM (= NHMV)	Unisyrtyet Wroclawski Muzeum Przyrodnicze, Sienkiewicza (Wroclaw University Museum of Natural History)	Vienna	Austria
WUMW	Zoologisches Museum Universität Hamburg (now Biozentrum Grindel und Zoologisches Museum, University of Hamburg)	Wroclaw	Poland
ZMUH (= ZMH)	Zoological Survey of India, Central Zone Regional Centre	Hamburg	Germany
ZSI-CZRC (= ZSI CZRC)	Zoological Survey of India, Western Ghats Regional Centre	Jabalpur	India
ZSIK (= ZSI/WGRC)	Zoological Survey of India, General Non-Chordata Section	Kozhikode (Calicut)	India
ZSI-GNC	Zoological Survey of India	Kolkata	India
ZSIC (= ZSI)		Kolkata	India

(1988), Narayanan *et al.* (2021a, 2023a), and Reynolds & Wetzl (2024), otherwise the reference is cited after. Depository data about the types of a few species are unavailable and many types are considered as lost. The type depository institutions information is summarised in table 1; 5) Distribution, country names are arranged in alphabetical order; 6) Distribution elsewhere, if applicable; 7) Status; 8) Remarks on the taxonomic status of species, if necessary. Based on the endemicity and ability of dispersal, Indian earthworms are categorized into four groups: i) endemic: species recorded only from South Asia and Myanmar; ii) sub-endemic: those with extended distribution to one of the neighbouring country; iii) exotic peregrine: species which have been introduced to the region from other distant countries or zoogeographical regions; iv) native peregrine: species evolved in the Indian subcontinent and Myanmar and have gained distribution in various parts of the South Asian region and other countries, it is corresponding to 'local peregrine' concept of Frago *et al.* (1995).

TAXONOMY

Kingdom ANIMALIA Haeckel, 1878

Phylum ANNELIDA Lamarck, 1802

Class CLITELLATA Michaelsen, 1919

Subclass OLIGOCHAETA Grube, 1850

Superorder MEGADRILI Benham, 1890

Order MONILIGASTRIDA Brinkhurst & Jamieson, 1971

Family MONILIGASTRIDAE Claus, 1880

Genus *Desmogaster* Rosa, 1890

Desmogaster Rosa, 1890a: 369.

Type species. *Desmogaster doriae* Rosa, 1890.

Distribution. From Myanmar in mainland Asia, Borneo and Sumatra in Malay Archipelago,

and also from China and Matsu Island (Taiwan), probably by introduction (Narayanan *et al.* 2024e).

***Desmogaster albalabia* Gates, 1930**

Desmogaster albalabia Gates, 1930: 265.

Type locality. Thandaung, Kyain State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** None (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Desmogaster doriae* Rosa, 1890**

Desmogaster doriae Rosa, 1890a: 369.

Type locality. Metelindaung, Kayah (Karen) State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** MGDG 44012, MNHU 2268; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Desmogaster ferina* Gates, 1943**

Desmogaster ferina Gates, 1943a: 91.

Type locality. Tingpai (Myitkyina), Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** None; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Probably introduced to India (Julka 1993).

***Desmogaster planata* Gates, 1931**

Desmogaster planata Gates, 1931: 331.

Type locality. Ye, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** None (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Drawida* Michaelsen, 1900

Moniligaster Perrier: Beddard 1895a: 196 (part).
Drawida Michaelsen, 1900a: 114.

Type species. *Moniligaster barwelli* Beddard, 1886.

Distribution. Its natural range is South Asia (mainly peninsular and northeastern India, Bangladesh and introduced to Sri Lanka and (?) Nepal), to Southeastern Asia (through Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, Vietnam, Malay Peninsula, Malay Archipelago (Borneo, Mindoro Island in the Philippines) and East Asia (through China, Taiwan, Korea, Far East Russia [protruding far north along the Amur River flood plain] and Japan) (Narayanan *et al.* 2024e, 2025e). It is presumed that the *Drawida* range in Southeast Asia begins west of the Wallace Line in the Malay Archipelago, despite the fact that no endemic *Drawida* species has been described from the Sumatra, Java and Bali Islands of the Sunda Shelf (Narayanan *et al.* 2024e).

***Drawida aculeata* Gates, 1945**

Drawida aculeata Gates, 1945a: 57.

Type locality. Madras (Chennai), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida agricola* Stephenson, 1925**

Drawida agricola Stephenson, 1925b: 53.

Type locality. Taliparamba, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Drawida ampullacea* Gates, 1945**

Drawida ampullacea Gates, 1945a: 58.

Type locality. Bababudan Hills – jungle between Kemmangundi and Kalhattagiri, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3272; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida annandalei* Stephenson, 1913**

Drawida annandalei Stephenson, 1913: 261.

Type locality. Caveri River - Tanjore (Tanjore or Thanjavur), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 4895; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Recently Aminjan *et al.* (2021) reported this species from Afghanistan, but did not furnish any details of the species. Since Afghanistan is far away from the type locality, this record needs further verification (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a).

***Drawida aruna* Julka, 1981**

Drawida aruna Julka, 1981: 4.

Type locality. Seiom, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HAZFS ZSI An-122 (Julka 1981a), HAZFS ZSI An123 to An128 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida assamensis* Gates, 1945**

Drawida assamensis Gates, 1945a: 59.

Type locality. Dumpep, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida barwelli* (Beddard, 1886)**

Moniligaster barwelli Beddard, 1886a: 94.

Moniligaster bahamensis Beddard, 1893: 690.

Drawida barwelli (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 116 (part).

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Manila, Philippines; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:522-3, 582; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Africa: São Tomé and Príncipe; Americas: Bahamas, Chile, Cuba, Jamaica, Martinique Island (France), Mexico, Nicaragua, Puerto Rico; Asia: Myanmar, Philippines,

Singapore, Southern Sulawesi, Sumatra, Thailand; Europe: England; Oceania: Australia, Fiji, Jap Island (Carolines), Tonga, Samoa, Flores? Aru Island? Lombok, New Caledonia, Papua New Guinea; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Drawida beddardii* (Rosa, 1890)**

Moniligaster beddardii Rosa, 1890a: 379.
Moniligaster beddardi Rosa: Bourne 1894a: 373.
Moniligaster barwelli Beddard: Beddard 1895a: 200 (part).
Drawida barwelli (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 116 (part).
Drawida beddardi (Rosa): Gates 1962a: 312.
Drawida beddardii (Rosa): Shen et al. 2015: 435.
For synonyms see Gates (1962a, 1972) and Narayanan et al. (2024e).

Type locality. Chiala, Myanmar; **Type depository.** NHM London; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** South Korea, Thailand? Vietnam; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Drawida bifida* Gates, 1945**

Drawida bifida Gates, 1945a: 60.

Type locality. Kemmangundi, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida brunnea* Stephenson, 1915**

Drawida brunnea Stephenson, 1915: 51.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6920; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida bullata* Gates, 1933**

Drawida constricta Gates, 1930: 282 (part, excluding adiverticulate worms).
Drawida bullata Gates, 1933: 424.
Drawida fucosa Gates, 1933: 439.

Type locality. Henzada (Himthada), Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida caenosa* Gates, 1945**

Drawida caenosa Gates, 1945a: 61.

Type locality. Yercaud, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3429; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida caerulea caerulea* Gates, 1926**

Drawida caerulea Gates, 1926a: 143.
Drawida caerulea: Gates 1930: 279 (part) (excluding some Chindwin specimens).
Drawida caerulea var. *typica*: Gates, 1933: 429.
Drawida caerulea caerulea Gates: Gates 1962a: 318.

Type locality. Nyaunglebin, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1928:4:2, USNM 19310, ZSIC 3042; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida caerulea rasilis* Gates, 1933**

Drawida caerulea Gates: Gates 1930: 279 (part).
Drawida caerulea var. *rasilis* Gates, 1933: 433 (including only a few Chindwin Valley worms)
Drawida caerulea rasilis Gates: Gates 1962a: 319.

Type locality. Chindwin Valley north of Monywa, Sagaing Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida calebi* Gates, 1945**

Drawida calebi Gates, 1945b: 211.

Type locality. Jubbulpore (Jabalpur), Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida chalakudiana* Stephenson, 1915**

Drawida chalakudiana Stephenson, 1915: 54.

Type locality. Chalakudi (Chalakudy), India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6594; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida chlorina* (Bourne, 1894)**

Moniligaster chlorina Bourne, 1894b: 364.

Drawida chlorina (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900: 119.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1895:9:3:8, UMOU 1517; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic to India.

***Drawida circumpapillata* Aiyer, 1929**

Drawida circumpapillatus Aiyer, 1929: 50.

Drawida circumpapillata Aiyer: Blakemore 2007a: 4.

Type locality. Nedumangad, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1511; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida constricta* Gates, 1929**

Drawida constricta Gates, 1929: 8.

Type locality. Mandalay, Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Paratypes in BMNH and USNM 19251; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida coonoorensis* Gates, 1945**

Drawida coonoorensis Gates, 1945a: 63.

Type locality. Coonoor, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida decourcyi* Stephenson, 1914**

Drawida decourcyi Stephenson, 1914b: 373.

Type locality. Upper Rotung, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV516017, ZSIC W5381/7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida delicata* Gates, 1962**

Drawida sp.: Gates 1930: 298.

Drawida delicata Gates, 1962a: 319.

Type locality. Mergui (Myeik), Tanintharyi Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Vietnam; **Status.** Native peregrine?

***Drawida dolosa* Gates, 1945**

Drawida dolosa Gates, 1945a: 64.

Type locality. Srivaikuntam, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida duttai* Julka, 1981**

Drawida duttai Julka, 1981: 7.

Type locality. Yame, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HAZFS ZSI An119 (Holotype), HAZFS ZSI An120, An121 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida elegans* Rao, 1921**

Drawida elegans Rao, 1921: 519.

Type locality. Bhagamandala, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1922:2:10:3, ZSIC 415, ZMUH V 9170 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida exilis* Gates, 1945**

Drawida exilis Gates, 1945a: 65.

Type locality. Nellore, Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3651; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida fakir* Cognetti, 1911**

Drawida fakir Cognetti, 1911: 495.

Type locality. Arumanallur (Arumanalloor), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1911:4:16:1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Only known from the type locality.

***Drawida fausta* Gates, 1945**

Drawida fausta Gates, 1945a: 65.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam/Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida ferina* Gates, 1945**

Drawida ferina Gates, 1945a: 66.

Type locality. Jog Falls jungle near Rajah Hill, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Jog Falls jungle near Rajah Hill (Gates 1945a); **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida flexa* Gates, 1929**

Drawida flexa Gates, 1929: 10.

Type locality. Kawkareik, Karen State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** USNM 19252 (Gates 1929); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida friderici* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Moniligaster friderici Michaelsen, 1897a: 169.

Drawida friderici (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 115.

Type locality. Trincomali (Trincomalee), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4641 (Holotype) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. As per Narayanan *et al.* (2025e) this species is probably introduced to Sri Lanka from the mainland India. But it is yet to be recorded from India (Narayanan *et al.* 2025e).

***Drawida ghatensis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Drawida ghatensis Michaelsen, 1910: 52.

Type locality. Tenmalai (Thenmala), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3596 (3 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.*), ZSIC 4166/7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. In the original description Michaelsen (1910) referred to Kulattupuzha (now Kula-thupuzha), Maddathoray (now Madathara), Tenmalai (now Thenmala) of the present day Kollam and Kottayam of Kottayam district of Kerala State (Narayanan *et al.* 2016a). Specimens from Kollam District were collected by Dr. N. Annandale, while the Kottayam specimens were collected by Mr. G. Matthai (Michaelsen 1910). But, among the 3 Syntypes preserved in the Hamburg Museum (ZMUH V 3596), there is an additional location, Shasthacottah (now Sathamkotta of Kollam District), collected by Matthai along with Kottayam specimen (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2026). However, this information was not provided in the original publication.

***Drawida gouri* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Drawida gouri Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari *et al.*, 2025a: 4.

Type locality. Botany Department, Dr. Harsingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya (A Central University), Madhya Pradesh State, India (Tiwari *et al.* 2025a); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/3 (Holotype), MP18-1246-2A5, MP18-1247-2A6 (Paratypes) (Tiwari *et al.* 2025a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Known only from the type locality. It was previously misidentified as *D. minuta* (Tiwari *et al.* 2025a).

***Drawida gracilis* Gates, 1925**

Moniligaster gracilis Gates, 1925a: 660.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3087; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Indian record is from the Kolli Hills (Kumar *et al.* 2025) of Tamil Nadu State, which needs further corroboration.

***Drawida grandis* (Bourne, 1886)**

Moniligaster grandis Bourne, 1886: 671.
Drawida grandis (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 117.

Type locality. Nilgiris, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1895:9:3:1, UMOU 1577-8, 1659; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida heingangensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Drawida heingangensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari *et al.*, 2025a: 6.

Type locality. Paddy field close to Imphal river in Heingang district, Manipur State, India (Tiwari *et al.* 2025a); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/19 (Holotype), MNP17-1177-47A27

(Paratype) (Tiwari *et al.* 2025a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida impertusa* Stephenson, 1920**

Drawida barwelli var. *impertusus* Stephenson, 1920: 200.
Drawida barwelli var. *impertusa*: Stephenson 1923: 134.
Drawida impertusa Stephenson: Gates 1965: 87.

Type locality. Victoria Gardens Bombay (Jijamata Udyan Mumbai), Mumbai, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 301; BMNH 1925:5:12:77; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Philippines; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Drawida jalpaigurensis* Stephenson, 1916**

Drawida jalpaigurensis Stephenson, 1916: 307.
Drawida jalpaigurensis: Stephenson 1923: 141.
Drawida nepalensis (part): Blakemore 2012a: 173.
Drawida jalpaigurensis: Tiwari *et al.* 2026: 3.

Type locality. Edge of Tista (Teesta) River at Jalpaiguri, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 7198 (Holotype), in a poor state of preservation (Stephenson 1916); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Until now it was treated as a synonym of *D. nepalensis* Michaelsen, 1907 (Blakemore 2012a, Narayanan *et al.* 2024e). Recently Tiwari *et al.* (2026) restored its species status based on the specimen from the Manipur State of India.

***Drawida jatinderi* Narayanan, 2024**

Drawida jatinderi Narayanan in Narayanan *et al.*, 2024b: 564.

Type locality. Neriampalam, Kerala State, India (Narayanan *et al.* 2024b); **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26787 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26788 (Paratypes) (Narayanan *et al.* 2024b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida japonica* (Michaelsen, 1892)**

Moniligaster japonicus Michaelsen, 1892: 232.

Drawida japonica (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 115.

Type locality. Japan; **Type depository.** ZM UH 403, 1 syntype in MNHU (ZMB Verm. 2122) (Hartwich & Kiliias 1989); **Distribution.** India, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Japan, Korea, Southeast Asia, Taiwan; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Drawida kanarensis* Stephenson, 1917**

Drawida kanarensis Stephenson, 1917: 364.

Type locality. Talewadi (Talawade), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 132; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida karatala* Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka, 2025**

Drawida karatala Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2025a: 97.

Type locality. Ranipuram, Kerala State, India (Narayanan et al. 2025a); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.29371 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.29372, ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.29373 (Paratypes) (Narayanan et al. 2025a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida kempi* Stephenson, 1914**

Drawida kempi Stephenson, 1914b: 376.

Drawida pellucida (Bourne): Stephenson 1914b: 368.

Drawida rotungana Stephenson, 1914b: 372.

Drawida pellucida f. *typica* (Bourne): Stephenson 1923: 150 (part).

Type locality. Egar stream - between Renging and Rotung, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5382; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida lacertosa lacertosa* Gates, 1930**

Drawida lacertosa Gates, 1930: 284.

Drawida lacertosa var. *typical* Gates: Gates, 1933: 445.

Drawida lacertosa lacertosa Gates: Gates 1972: 251.

Type locality. Ngapoli (Ngapali), Rakhine State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida lacertosa sepulta* Gates, 1931**

Drawida sepulta Gates, 1931: 352.

Drawida lacertosa var. *sepulta* Gates: Gates, 1933: 447.

Drawida lacertosa sepulta Gates: Gates 1962a: 361.

Type locality. Kya In (Kyain), Kyain state, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3119; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida laichingensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Drawida laichingensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025a: 9.

Type locality. Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025a); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/11 (Holotype) (Tiwari et al. 2025a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida leibiensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Drawida leibiensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025a: 8.

Type locality. Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025a); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/10 (Holotype) (Tiwari et al. 2025a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida lennora* Gates, 1945**

Drawida lennora Gates, 1945a: 67.

Type locality. Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3652; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida limella* Gates, 1934**

Drawida limella Gates, 1934: 241.

Drawida periodiosa Gates, 1934: 247.

Drawida limella Gates: Julka 1976b: 323.

Type locality. Kinchana near Amingaon, Assam State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3536; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida longatria longatria* Gates, 1925**

Drawida longatria Gates, 1925c: 50.

Drawida longatria var. *typica* Gates: Gates, 1930: 286 (part?).

Moniligaster straeleni Michaelsen, 1930: 1.

Drawida longatria longatria Gates: Gates 1962a: 328.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1926:6:5:24, ZSIC 1232, 1175; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Sumatra Island (Indonesia); **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. A single record from Sumatra (Gates 1972), probably introduced (Gates 1965, 1972).

***Drawida longatria deminuta* Gates, 1930**

Drawida longatria var. *deminuta* Gates, 1930: 287.

Drawida longatria deminuta Gates: Gates 1972: 253.

Type locality. Pynmana, Naypyidaw Union Territory, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3082; **Distribution.** Myanmar. **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida longatria ordinata* Gates, 1930**

Drawida longatria var. *ordinata* Gates, 1930: 288.

Drawida longatria ordinata Gates: Gates 1972: 253.

Type locality. Toungoo (Taungoo), Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3127; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida longatria planata* Gates, 1931**

Drawida longatria var. *planata* Gates, 1931: 344.

Drawida longatria planata Gates: Gates 1972: 253.

Type locality. Shwegyin, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3095; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida longatria tortuosa* Gates, 1931**

Drawida longatria var. *tortuosa* Gates, 1931: 345.

Drawida longatria tortuosa Gates: Gates 1972: 253.

Type locality. Chaungson (Chaungzon), Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3086; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida longatria verrucosa* Gates, 1931**

Drawida longatria var. *verrucosa* Gates, 1931: 347.

Drawida longatria verrucosa Gates: Gates 1972: 253.

Type locality. Tharrawaddy (Thayarwaddy), Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida loricata* Gates, 1945**

Drawida loricata Gates, 1945a: 67.

Type locality. Srivaikuntam, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3276; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida matthaii* Michaelsen, 1910**

Drawida matthaii Michaelsen, 1910: 47.

Type locality. Calicut (Kozhikode), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3484, ZMUH V 3597 (2 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida minuta* (Bourne, 1886)**

Moniligaster minutus Bourne, 1886: 672.
Moniligaster minuta (Bourne): Bourne 1894b: 372.
Drawida minuta (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 120.

Type locality. Salem, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** UMOU 1513; BMNH 1875: 9: 3: 7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida modesta* Rao, 1921**

Drawida modesta Rao, 1921: 525.

Type locality. Moornad (Murnad), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1922:2: 10:4; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida molesta* Gates, 1933**

Drawida molesta Gates, 1933: 463.

Type locality. Victoria point (Kawthoung), Tanintharyi Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida montana* Gates, 1945**

Drawida montana Gates, 1945a: 68.

Type locality. Dumpep, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida mysorensis* Gates, 1945**

Drawida mysorensis Gates, 1945a: 69.

Type locality. Mysore (Mysuru), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida naduvatamensis* (Bourne, 1894)**

Moniligaster naduvatamensis Bourne, 1894b: 361.
Drawida naduvatamensis (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 117.

Type locality. Naduvatam (Naduvattam), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Only known from the type locality.

***Drawida nagana* Gates, 1945**

Drawida nagana Gates, 1945a: 69.

Type locality. Khezabana, Nagaland State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida nana* Gates, 1933**

Drawida longatria var. *nana* Gates, 1933: 461.
Drawida nana Gates: Gates 1962a: 330.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida nandiensis* Stephenson, 1924**

Drawida nandiensis Stephenson, 1924b: 326.
Drawida nandiensis Stephenson: Narayanan et al. 2024d: 49.

Type locality. Nandi Hills, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1111, BMNH 1925:5:12:29-30; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida nepalensis* Michaelsen, 1907**

Drawida nepalensis Michaelsen, 1907: 146.
Drawida burchardi Michaelsen, 1902: 7.
Drawida troglodytes Stephenson, 1924a: 129.
Drawida cacharensis Stephenson, 1926: 251.
Moniligaster ivaniosi Manazhy et al., 2011: 11.
For further synonyms see Gates (1972) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Gowchar (Gauchar) near Kathmandu, Bagmati province, Nepal; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7140; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Indonesia; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Drawida nilamburensis* (Bourne, 1894)**

Moniligaster nilamburensis Bourne, 1894b: 362.
Drawida nilamburensis (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 117.

Type locality. Nilambur, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida paliwali* Narayanan, 2024**

Drawida paliwali Narayanan in Narayanan et al., 2024b: 568.

Type locality. Karimala Gopuram Hill in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Kerala State, India (Narayanan et al. 2024b); **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26789 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26790 (Paratypes) (Narayanan et al. 2024b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida papillifer* Stephenson, 1917**

Drawida papillifer Stephenson, 1917: 370.
Drawida hodgarti Stephenson, 1917: 366.
Drawida rosea Stephenson, 1922a: 430.
Drawida pomella Gates, 1934: 250.
For further synonyms see Gates (1972) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Rangamati, Chittagong division, Bangladesh; **Type depository.** BMNH

1925:5:12:121, ZSIC 70; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida paradoxa* Rao, 1921**

Drawida paradoxa Rao, 1921: 528.

Type locality. Madapur (Madapura), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 418, BMNH 1922:2:10:5-6, ZMUH V 9169 (1 Syn-type) (Cs. Csuzdi in litt. 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida parambikulamana* Stephenson, 1915**

Drawida parambikulamana Stephenson, 1915: 53.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6579; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida parva* (Bourne, 1894)**

Moniligaster parva Bourne, 1894b: 371.
Drawida parva (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 118.

Type locality. Ootacamund (now Udhagamandalam or Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida peguana* Gates, 1925**

Drawida peguana Gates, 1925b: 316.
Drawida papillifer peguana Gates 1962a: 342.

Type locality. Rangoon, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3110, BMNH 1926:6:5:26-8, USNM 19662; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida pellucida pellucida* (Bourne, 1894)**

Moniligaster pellucida Bourne, 1894b: 363.
Drawida pellucida (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900: 118.
Drawida pellucidus f. *typica* (Bourne): Michaelsen 1910: 50.
Drawida pellucida pellucida (Bourne): Blakemore 2007a: 7.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), India; **Type depository.** ZMUH 4642, 4667, BMNH 1895:9:3:10, UMOU 1515, 1612; **Distribution.** India **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida pellucida bournei* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Moniligaster bournei Michaelsen, 1897a: 167.

Moniligaster pauli Michaelsen, 1897a: 171.

Drawida bournei (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 116.

Drawida pellucidus vr. *bournei* (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1910a: 50.

Drawida pellucida bournei (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 7.

Type locality. Probably Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4671 (6 Syn-types) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.*), MNHU 7382 (= ZMB Verm. 7382) Cotype (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. As per Narayanan *et al.* (2025e) this species is probably introduced to Sri Lanka from the mainland India. But it is yet to be recorded from India (Narayanan *et al.* 2025e).

***Drawida pellucida pallida* Michaelsen, 1910**

Drawida pellucidus var. *pallida* Michaelsen, 1910a: 51.

Drawida pellucida var. *pallida* Michaelsen: Stephenson 1923: 151

Drawida pellucida pallida Michaelsen: Blakemore 2007a: 7.

Type locality. Shencottah (Shenkottai), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1925:5:12:28, ZSIC 4140; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida pellucida raoi* Stephenson, 1926**

Drawida pellucida var. *raoi* Stephenson, 1926: 255.

Drawida pellucida raoi Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 7.

Type locality. Terkumalai, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida pellucida stewarti* Stephenson, 1914**

Drawida pellucida var. *stewarti* Stephenson, 1914b: 369.

Drawida pellucida stewarti Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 7.

Type locality. Rotung, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5444, 5394-401, BMNH 1925:5:12:55; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida polydiverticulata* Narayanan & Julka, 2017**

Drawida polydiverticulata Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan *et al.*, 2017: 3.

Type locality. Meenthottychola in Eravikulam National Park, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/IR/INV-8835 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/IR/INV-8836 (Paratype) Narayanan *et al.* 2017); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida proboscidea* Narayanan, 2024**

Drawida proboscidea Narayanan in Narayanan *et al.*, 2024b: 571.

Type locality. Peringuzha, Kerala State, India (Narayanan *et al.* 2024b); **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26791 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26792 (Paratypes) (Narayanan *et al.* 2024b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida ramnadana* Michaelsen, 1907**

Drawida ramnadana Michaelsen, 1907: 145.

Type locality. Ramnad (Ramanathapuram), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7161, ZSIC 2939; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida rangamatiana* Stephenson, 1917**

Drawida rangamatiana Stephenson, 1917: 369.

Type locality. Rangamati, Bangladesh; **Type depository.** ZSIC 82; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida rangoonensis* Gates, 1925**

Drawida rangoonensis Gates, 1925b: 320.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1229, 3054; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida rara* Gates, 1925**

Drawida rara Gates, 1925b: 321.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1233, 3054, BMNH 1926:6:5:25, USNM; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida reynoldsi* Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka, 2026**

Drawida reynoldsi Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka in Fahis et al., 2026: 197.

Type locality. Between Sispara and Anginda in Silent Valley National Park, Kerala State, India (Fahis et al. 2026); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/L.R.INV.30067 (Holotype) (Fahis et al. 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida robusta robusta* (Bourne, 1886)**

Moniligaster robustus Bourne, 1886: 672.

Moniligaster indicus Benham, 1893: 363.

Drawida robusta robusta (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 120.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** UMOU 1520; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida robusta cochinensis* Stephenson, 1925**

Drawida robusta var. *cochinensis* Stephenson, 1925b: 52.

Drawida robusta cochinensis (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 8.

Type locality. Chalakudi (Chalakyudi), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida robusta ophidioides* (Bourne, 1894)**

Moniligaster ophidioides Bourne, 1894b: 365.

Drawida robusta ophidioides (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 120.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** UMOU 1521, BMNH 1895: 9:3:6; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida sapphirinaoides* (Bourne, 1886)**

Moniligaster sapphirinaoides Bourne, 1886: 672.

Drawida sapphirinaoides (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 119.

Type locality. Pykara (Pykara Falls), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** UMOU 1516, BMNH 1895:9:3:2; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida scandens* Rao, 1921**

Drawida scandens Rao, 1921: 515.

Drawida raii Stephenson, 1921a: 755.

Drawida scandens Rao: Stephenson 1923: 156.

Type locality. Bhagamandala, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1922:2: 10:1-2 (Holotype), ZSIC 417, ZMUH V 9168; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida schunkarai* Michaelsen, 1913**

Drawida schunkarai Michaelsen, 1913a: 74.

Type locality. Cape Comorain (Kanyakumari), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH 8095; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida somavarpatana* Rao, 1921**

Drawida somavarpatana Rao, 1921: 497.

Type locality. Somvarpatana (Somwarpet, Somvarpet), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1922:2:10:7-10 (Holotype), ZMUH V 9167, ZSIC 416; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida spissata* Gates, 1930**

Drawida spissata Gates, 1930: 291.

Type locality. On road over Arakan Yomas through Taungup Pass, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1233, 3054, BMNH 1926:6:5:25, USNM; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida sulcata* Michaelsen, 1907**

Drawida sulcata Michaelsen, 1907: 144.
non *Drawida sulcata* Zhong, 1986 = *Drawida zhongi* Blakemore, 2006.

Type locality. Coonoor, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7184 (Holotype) (Cs. Csuzdi in litt. 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida tenellula* Gates, 1962**

Drawida sp. Gates 1933: 476.
Drawida tenellula Gates, 1962a: 351.

Type locality. Tharrawady (Thayarwaddy), Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** *Typus perditus*; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida thomasi* Narayanan & Julka, 2017**

Drawida thomasi Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2017: 5.

Type locality. Kozhippara waterfalls, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WG RC/

IR/INV-8837 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/IR/INV-8838 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida thurstoni* Gates, 1945**

Drawida thurstoni Gates, 1945a: 70.

Type locality. Nilgiri Hills, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida tihunensis* Julka, 1976**

Drawida tihunensis Julka, 1976a: 230.

Type locality. Tihun, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An110/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An111/1 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Drawida travancorensis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Drawida travancorensis Michaelsen, 1900a: 46.

Type locality. Kottayam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3494; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida tumida tumida* Gates, 1929**

Drawida tumida Gates, 1929: 12.
Drawida tumida variety *typica* Gates: Gates 1930: 294.

Type locality. Moulmien (Mawlamyine), Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** USNM 19253; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida tumida deleta* Gates, 1930**

Drawida tumida variety *deleta* Gates, 1930: 295.

Type locality. Tavoy (Dawei) district, Tanintharyi Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** USNM 19253; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida unica* (Bourne, 1886)**

Moniligaster unicus Bourne, 1886: 671.
Moniligaster papillatus Bourne, 1886: 672.
Drawida unica (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 118.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** UMOU 1518, BMNH 1895:9:39; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida vazhania* Ardra & Narayanan, 2026**

Drawida vazhania Ardra & Narayanan in Ardra et al., 2026: 270.

Type locality. Vazhani dam site in Peechi-Vazhani Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala State, India (Ardra et al. 2026); **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.30544 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.30545 (5 Paratypes) (Ardra et al. 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida victoriana* Gates, 1962**

Drawida victoriana Gates, 1962a: 352.

Type locality. Mount Victoria (Pakokku Chin Hills) east side of near path from Kanpetlet, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida vulgaris* Gates, 1930**

Drawida vulgaris Gates, 1930: 296.

Type locality. Kalewa, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1930: 12:27:70, ZSIC 3052; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Drawida willsi* Michaelsen, 1907**

Drawida willsi Michaelsen, 1907: 145.

Type locality. Bilashpur (Bilaspur), Chhattisgarh State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7160 (20 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi, in litt. 2026), ZSIC; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Hastirogaster* Gates, 1930

Hastirogaster Gates, 1930: 275.

Type species. *Hastirogaster livida* Gates, 1930.

Distribution. Myanmar, Sumatra Island (Indonesia) (Gates 1972, Narayanan et al. 2024e).

***Hastirogaster browni* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eupolygaster Browni Michaelsen, 1907: 133.

Eupolygaster browni Michaelsen: Michaelsen 1909: 139.

Hastirogaster browni (Michaelsen): Gates 1930: 275.

Type locality. Lashio, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type material.** ZSIC 2935; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Hastirogaster livida* Gates, 1930**

Hastirogaster livida Gates, 1930: 276.

Type locality. Pantha (Panghta), Sagaing Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Moniligaster* Perrier, 1872

Moniligaster Perrier, 1872: 130.

Type species. *Moniligaster deshayesi* Perrier, 1872.

Distribution. India (endemic to the Western Ghats with one record from Eastern Ghats).

***Moniligaster aiyeri* Gates, 1940**

Moniligaster aiyeri Gates, 1940d: 493.

Moniligaster aiyeri Gates: Narayanan et al. 2022: 41.

Moniligaster aiyeri Gates: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Muthukkuzhi, Tamil Nadu State India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster bahli* Narayanan & Julka, 2021**

Moniligaster bahli Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2021b: 382.

Moniligaster bahli Narayanan & Julka: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Vengolimala in Parambikulam Tiger Reserve, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.8843 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.8844 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster blakemorei* Narayanan & Julka, 2021**

Moniligaster blakemorei Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2021b: 385.

Moniligaster blakemorei Narayanan & Julka: Narayanan et al. 2022: 42.

Moniligaster blakemorei Narayanan & Julka: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Between Aranamoozhi and Ilampapmba, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.8841 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.8842 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster cernosvitovi* Gates, 1962**

Moniligaster perrieri Michaelsen: Stephenson 1924b: 322 (part).

Moniligaster beddardi Gates, 1940d: 496.

Moniligaster cernosvitovi Gates, 1962a: 355. nom nov. pro *M. beddardi* Gates 1940 not *M. beddardii* Rosa, 1890.

Moniligaster cernosvitovi Gates: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster deshayesi* Perrier, 1872**

Moniligaster deshayesi Perrier, 1872: 130.

Moniligaster deshayesi Perrier: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Unknown, probably from the southern portion of Western Ghats in Kerala State; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster gatesi* Ahmed & Narayanan, 2025**

Moniligaster gatesi Ahmed & Narayanan in Narayanan et al., 2025b: 144.

Type locality. Ooty (= Udthagamandalam or Udhagai), Tamil Nadu State, India (Narayanan et al. 2025a); **Type depository.** ZSI-GNC-An 7976/2 (Holotype), ZSI-GNC-An7977/2 (Paratypes) (Narayanan et al. 2025a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Moniligaster girishi* Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka, 2026**

Moniligaster girishi Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka, 2026 in Fahis et al., 2026: 191.

Type locality. Chembotti in Silent Valley National Park, Kerala State, India (Fahis et al. 2026); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.30068 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.19325, ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.30069 (1 Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster gravelyi* Stephenson, 1915**

Moniligaster deshayesi var. *gravelyi* Stephenson, 1915: 59.

Moniligaster gravelyi Stephenson: Gates 1940d: 504 (part, Kavalai specimen = *M. bahli* Narayanan & Julka, 2021).

Moniligaster gravelyi Stephenson: Narayanan et al. 2023e: 366.

Moniligaster gravelyi Stephenson: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Trichur (Thrissur) (10.5276°N, 76.2144°E), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed (Narayanan et al. 2023e); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster horsti* Gates, 1940**

Moniligaster horsti Gates, 1940d: 506.
Moniligaster horsti Gates: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Bungitappal (Bangitappal), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3434; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster julkai* Narayanan & Paliwal, 2022**

Moniligaster julkai Narayanan & Paliwal in Narayanan et al., 2022: 32.
Moniligaster julkai Narayanan & Paliwal: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Puthuvely, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.19324 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.19325, ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.19326 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster keralensis* Narayanan & Julka, 2021**

Moniligaster keralensis Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2021b: 386.
Moniligaster keralensis Narayanan & Julka: Narayanan et al. 2022: 44.
Moniligaster keralensis Narayanan & Julka: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Kurichikanam in Konni Reserve Forest, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.8839 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/IR.INV.8840 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster michaelseni* Gates, 1940**

Moniligaster michaelseni Gates, 1940d: 508.
Moniligaster michaelseni Gates: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215. 7

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3433; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster minor* Michaelsen, 1913**

Moniligaster deshayesi var. *minor* Michaelsen, 1913a: 78.
Moniligaster deshayesi Perrier: Gates 1940d: 499 (part).
Moniligaster deshayesi minor Michaelsen: Blakemore 2007a: 9.
Moniligaster minor Michaelsen: Narayanan et al. 2022: 36.
Moniligaster minor Michaelsen: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Chimunji (= Chemmunji), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 8096 (Holotype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster perrieri* Michaelsen, 1907**

Moniligaster perrieri Michaelsen, 1907: 146.
Moniligaster perrieri Michaelsen: Gates 1940d: 511.
Moniligaster perrieri Michaelsen: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2902–03, BMNH 1925:5:12:95, ZMUH V 7143; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster stephensoni* Gates, 1940**

Moniligaster perrieri Michaelsen: Stephenson 1924b: 322 (part).
Moniligaster stephensoni Gates, 1940d: 514.
Moniligaster stephensoni Gates: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Vanderavu (Bander), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2902–03, BMNH 1925:5:12:95, ZMUH 7143; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Moniligaster troyi* Jamieson, 1977**

Moniligaster troyi Jamieson, 1977a: 111.

Moniligaster troyi Jamieson: Narayanan et al. 2024f: 215.

Type locality. Vanderavu, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1978.1.10 (Holotype), BMNH 1978.1.11 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Order CRASSICLITELLATA Jamieson, 1988

Family ACANTHODRILIDAE Claus, 1880

Genus *Bahlia* Gates, 1945

Bahlia Gates, 1945b: 236.

Type species. *Bahlia albida* Gates, 1945.

Distribution. India (southernmost portion of the Gangetic plain in Uttar Pradesh) (Julka 1988a).

***Bahlia albida* Gates, 1945**

Bahlia albida Gates, 1945b: 237.

Type locality. Allahabad (Prayagraj), Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3461/1, W3469/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Calebiella* Gates, 1945

Calebiella Gates, 1945b: 242.

Type species. *Calebiella parva* Gates, 1945.

Distribution. India (Gangetic Plains of Uttar Pradesh) (Julka 1988a).

***Calebiella parva* Gates, 1945**

Calebiella parva Gates, 1945b: 242.

Type locality. Pratagarh (Pratapgarh), Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC, w 3635/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Chaetocotoides* Julka, 1988

Octochaetus Beddard: Stephenson 1920: 234 (part.).
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides): Stephenson 1923: 384 (part.).

Octochaetoides Michaelsen: Gates 1962b: 209 (part.).
Chaetocotoides Julka, 1988a: 89.

Type species. *Octochaetus montanus* Stephenson, 1920.

Distribution. India (Northern Western Ghats) (Julka 1988a).

***Chaetocotoides montanus* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Octochaetus montanus Stephenson, 1920: 234.
Chaetocotoides montanus (Stephenson): Julka 1988a: 90.

Type locality. Panchgani, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W25916/1, BMNH 1933:5:25:904-5; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. It is known only from the type locality so far.

Genus *Eudichogaster* Michaelsen, 1902

Benhamia Michaelsen: Beddard, 1896: 209 (part).
Trigaster Benham: Michaelsen 1900: 330 (part).
Eudichogaster Michaelsen, 1902: 13 (part).
Eudichogaster Michaelsen: Gates 1940a: 160.

Type species. *Benhamia indica* Beddard, 1896.

Distribution. Western India from Poona (Pune) to Central India just in Rajasthan and east to Jubbulpore (Jabalpur) and Nagpur (Julka 1988a).

***Eudichogaster ashworthi* Michaelsen, 1902**

Eudichogaster ashworthi Michaelsen, 1902: 14.

Type locality. Nagpur, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 5886 (2 Syn-

types) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026), MNHU 5202 (= ZMB Verm. 5202) Paratype (Hartwich & Kilius 1989); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eudichogaster indica* (Beddard, 1896)**

Benhamia indica Beddard, 1896: 209.

Trigaster indica (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 333.

Eudichogaster indica (Beddard): Michaelsen 1902: 13.

Eudichogaster indicus (Beddard): Stephenson 1923: 414.

Type locality. Thana (Thane), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** Presumably lost; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eudichogaster kinneari* Stephenson, 1920**

Eudichogaster kinneari Stephenson, 1920: 255.

Eudichogaster ashworthi var. *kinneari* Stephenson: Stephenson 1923: 407.

Type locality. Nasik (Nashik), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:5: 25:341-3; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eudichogaster mullani* Stephenson, 1922**

Eudichogaster mullani Stephenson, 1922a: 438.

Type locality. Bombay (Mumbai), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W705/1, BMNH 1933:2:25:1383-4; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eudichogaster poonensis* (Fedarb, 1898)**

Benhamia poonensis Fedarb, 1898a: 434.

Trigaster poonensis (Fedarb): Michaelsen 1900a: 333.

Eudichogaster poonensis (Fedarb): Michaelsen 1902: 13.

Type locality. Poona (Pune), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eudichogaster prashadi* Stephenson, 1920**

Eudichogaster prashadi Stephenson, 1920: 250.

Eudichogaster prashadi (Stephenson): Julka 1988a: 125.

Type locality. Palia, Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W282/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:100-2; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Eutyphoeus* Michaelsen, 1900

Typhaeus Beddard, 1883: 219.

Typhaeus Beddard 1888: 111, 117.

Typhaeus Rosa 1890: 388.

Eutyphoeus Michaelsen, 1900a: 322.

Typhoeus Beddard: Blakemore 2013a: 115 (as per ICZN priority).

Type species. *Typhoeus orientalis* Beddard, 1883.

Distribution. India (from Myanmar border into the Gangetic plains and west through the Himalaya and Odisha), Bangladesh, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan (Julka 1988a).

***Eutyphoeus aborianus* Stephenson, 1914**

Eutyphoeus aborianus Stephenson, 1914b: 406.

Typhoeus aborianus (Stephenson): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Kobo, Assam State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV6068/7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus annandalei* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus annandalei Michaelsen, 1907: 174.

Typhoeus annandalei (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Bhim Tal, Uttarakhand State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3040; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality so far.

***Eutyphoeus annulatus* Gates, 1931**

Eutyphoeus annulatus Gates, 1931: 418.
Eutyphoeus annulatus var. *typicus* Gates, 1933: 562.
Eutyphoeus annulatus Gates: Gates 1958a: 157.
Typhoeus annulatus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Sagaing, Sagaing Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3048, but as per Gates (1972) no types; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus assamensis* Stephenson, 1926**

Eutyphoeus assamensis Stephenson, 1926: 262.
Typhoeus assamensis (Stephenson): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Katlicherra, Assam State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1951/1; BMNH 1933: 2:23:510-1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus baronngini* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus baronngini Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 146.

Type locality. Shirui Kashong (Peak) in Shiroi National Park, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/13 (Holotype), MNP17-1106-45A3, MNP17-1115-45A12 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus bifovis* Gates, 1929**

Eutyphoeus bifovis Gates, 1929: 25.
Typhoeus bifovis (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Mandalay, Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes in USNM 19257, BMNH 1928:2:4, ZSIC 3109, 1497; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus bullatus* Gates, 1933**

Eutyphoeus bullatus (part) Gates, 1933: 566.

Eutyphoeus bullatus Gates: Gates 1958a: 112.
Typhoeus bullatus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Tiddim (Tedim), Chin Hills, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3111, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus callosus* Gates, 1938**

Eutyphoeus callosus Gates, 1938a: 67.
Typhoeus callosus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Dumpep, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3325; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus cochlearis* Gates, 1931**

Eutyphoeus cochlearis Gates, 1931: 422.
Typhoeus cochlearis (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Pakokku, Magway Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3064, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus comillahnus* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus comillahnus Michaelsen, 1907: 187 (part).
Typhoeus comillahnus (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Comillah (Comilla, Cumilla), Bangladesh; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2837/7, ZMUH V 7156 (Cs. Csuzdi in litt. 2026); **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus compositus* Gates, 1933**

Eutyphoeus annulatus var. *compositus* Gates, 1933: 563.
Eutyphoeus compositus Gates: Gates 1958a: 155.
Typhoeus compositus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Tonbo, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3098, but as per Gates (1972) no types; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus constrictus* Gates, 1929**

Eutyphoeus constrictus Gates, 1929: 28.
Eutyphoeus hastatus Gates, 1929: 32.
Eutyphoeus hamatus Gates, 1930: 332.
Eutyphoeus montanus Gates, 1933: 587.
Typhoeus constrictus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Meiktila, Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes in BMNH 1928:2:4:6, USNM 19261, ZSIC 1480; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus dhubriensis* Ahmed, Julka, Banerjee & Marimuthu, 2023**

Eutyphoeus dhubriensis Ahmed, Julka, Banerjee & Marimuthu in Ahmed et al., 2023a: 168.

Type locality. Dhubri, Assam State, India (Ahmed et al. 2023a); **Type depository.** ZSIC-GNC An7271/1 (Holotype), ZSIC ZSIC-GNC An7272/1 (Paratypes) (Ahmed et al. 2023a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus excavatus* Gates, 1929**

Eutyphoeus excavatus Gates, 1929: 30.
Typhoeus excavatus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Meiktila, Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes in BMNH 1928:2:4:5, USNM, ZSIC 1484; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus ferinus* Gates, 1958**

Eutyphoeus ferinus Gates, 1958a: 146.
Typhoeus ferinus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Myitkyina, Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus festivus* Gates, 1938**

Eutyphoeus festivus Gates, 1938a: 71.

Typhoeus festivus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Dumpep, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3324/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus foveatus* (Rosa, 1890)**

Typhaeus foveatus Rosa, 1890a: 389.
Eutyphoeus foveatus (Rosa): Michaelsen 1900: 323.
Typhoeus foveatus (Rosa): Beddard 1901a: 206.
Eutyphaeus foveatus (Rosa): Michaelsen 1903a: 108.
Eutyphoeus foveatus (Rosa): Gates 1972: 292.
Typhoeus foveatus Rosa: Blakemore 2013a: 115.
Eutyphoeus foveatus (Rosa): Csuzdi et al. 2015: 179.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** MGDG 44024 in poor condition, Topotypes in USNM (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus gammiei* (Beddard, 1888)**

Typhaeus gammii Beddard, 1888a: 111.
Eutyphoeus gammiei (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900: 323.
Eutyphoeus chittagongianus Michaelsen, 1907: 181.
Eutyphoeus gammiei (Beddard): Stephenson 1923: 434 (part).
Eutyphoeus koboensis Stephenson, 1914b: 404.
Eutyphoeus magnus Stephenson, 1914b: 408.
Eutyphoeus gammiei (Beddard): Gates 1972: 293.
Typhoeus gammiei Beddard: Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Darjiling (Darjeeling), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:2:263; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Elsewhere.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus gigas* Stephenson, 1917**

Eutyphoeus gigas Stephenson, 1917: 408.
Eutyphoeus longiseta Gates, 1930: 332.
Eutyphoeus longiseta postremus Gates, 1930: 336.
Eutyphoeus gigas Stephenson: Blakemore 2006a: 16.
Typhoeus gigas (Stephenson): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Rangamati, Chattogram Division, Bangladesh; **Type depository.** ZSIC

W73/1; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus incommodus* (Beddard, 1901)**

Typhoeus incommodus Beddard, 1901a: 200.
Eutyphaeus incommodus (Beddard): Michaelsen 1903a: 109.
Eutyphoeus mohammedi Stephenson, 1914a: 350.
Eutyphoeus annandalei var. *fulgidus* Stephenson, 1916: 342.
Typhoeus incommodus Beddard: Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Calcutta (now Kolkata), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** Probably do not exist; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Pakistan; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus kashongensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus kashongensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 139.

Type locality. Shirui Kashong (Peak) in Shiroi National Park, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/14 (Holotype), MNP17-1112-45A9, MNP17-1114-45A11, MNP17-1119-45A16 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus kempii* Stephenson, 1914**

Eutyphoeus kempii Stephenson, 1914b: 401.
Typhoeus kempii (Stephenson): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Kobo, Assam State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV5150/7; BMNH 1933:5:25:262; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus kherai* Julka, 1978**

Eutyphoeus kherai Julka, 1978: 191.

Type locality. Bisoi, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An 305/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An

306/1 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus kwathensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus kwathensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 157.

Type locality. Kwatha range in Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/5 (Holotype), MNP17-1045-42A4, MNP17-1046-42A5 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus lamdengensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus lamdengensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 134.

Type locality. Lamdeng Makhaleikai forest range, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/18 (Holotype), MNP 17-1158-47A7, MNP 17-1166-47A16 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus levis* (Rosa, 1890)**

Typhaeus laevis Rosa, 1890a: 388.
Typhaeus levis (Rosa): Beddard 1895a: 475.
Eutyphoeus levis (Rosa) part: Michaelsen 1900: 323.
Excluding Ceylon (Sri Lanka) specimen.
Eutyphaeus falcifer Gates, 1933: 574.
Eutyphoeus levis (Rosa): Gates 1972: 296.

Type locality. Cobapo, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype at MGDG, but even in 1890 was in too poor condition for study of internal anatomical features (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus lippus* Gates, 1934**

Eutyphoeus lippus Gates, 1934: 273.
Typhoeus lippus: Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Gurjung, Gandaki province, Nepal; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3045; **Distribution.** Nepal; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus lokchaensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus lokchaensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 144.

Type locality. Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/9 (Holotype), MNP17-1075-44A, MNP17-1076-44A2, MNP17-1076-44A3 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus macer* Gates, 1933**

Eutyphoeus macer Gates, 1933: 582.
Typhoeus macer (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Thaton, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus manipurensis manipurensis* Stephenson, 1921**

Eutyphoeus manipurensis Stephenson, 1921a: 763.
Eutyphoeus manipurensis manipurensis Stephenson: Gates 1958a: 110.
Typhoeus manipurensis manipurensis Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Thonga (Thanga) Island in Loktak Lake, Manipur State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W555/1; BMNH 1933:5:25:1344; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus manipurensis chinensis* Gates, 1933**

Eutyphoeus manipurensis Gates, 1933: 583.
Eutyphoeus manipurensis chinensis Gates, 1958a: 110.
Typhoeus manipurensis chinensis (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Falam, Chin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types lost (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus marmoreus* Gates, 1933**

Eutyphoeus marmoreus Gates, 1933: 585.
Eutyphoeus bullatus Gates, 1933: 569 (part).
Eutyphoeus marmoreus Gates: Gates 1958a: 110.
Typhoeus marmoreus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Tiddim (Tedim), Chin Hills, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3 105; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus mizoramensis* Julka, Ramanujam & Lalthanzara, 2005**

Eutyphoeus mizoramensis Julka, Ramanujam & Lalthanzara in Julka et al., 2005: 70.
Typhoeus mizoramensis (Julka et al.): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Aizwal, Mizoram State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An817 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An818 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus morehensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus morehensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 131.

Type locality. Kwatha Range in Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/6 (Holotype), MNP 17-1061-43A1 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus nainianus* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus nainianus Michaelsen, 1907: 177.
Typhoeus nainianus (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Naini Tal, Uttarakhand State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2842/7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus nepalensis* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus nepalensis Michaelsen, 1907: 176.
Typhoeus nepalensis (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Chitlong (Chitlang), Nepal
Type depository. ZSIC ZEV2880/7, ZMUH V 7131 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India, Nepal, Pakistan; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus nicholsoni* (Beddard, 1901)**

Typhoeus nicholsoni Beddard, 1901a: 206.
Eutyphoeus khani Michaelsen, 1907: 182.
Eutyphoeus provincialis Michaelsen, 1909: 219.
Eutyphoeus nicholsoni (Beddard): Stephenson 1923: 446.
Typhoeus nicholsoni (Beddard): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Calcutta (now Kolkata), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7162 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus orientalis* (Beddard, 1883)**

Typhoeus orientalis Beddard, 1883: 219.
Typhoeus masoni Bourne, 1889: 112.
Eutyphoeus orientalis (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900: 322.
Eutyphoeus paivai Michaelsen, 1907: 178.
Eutyphoeus bastianus Michaelsen, 1907: 183.
Eutyphoeus andersoni Michaelsen, 1907: 185.
Eutyphoeus bishambari Stephenson, 1914a: 355.
Typhoeus orientalis (Beddard): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Neighbourhood of Calcutta (now Kolkata), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Pakistan; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus* Gates, 1925**

Eutyphoeus peguanus Gates, 1925b: 323.
Eutyphoeus peguanus var. *typicus* Gates, 1930: 337.
Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus Gates: Gates 1958a: 142; 1972: 299.
Typhoeus peguanus peguanus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes USNM 19658, ZSIC 1177; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Blakemore (2006a) stated that many subspecies and varieties (illegitimate) are mentioned by Gates (1972), the status of these as valid subspecies is uncertain. Although they are provided below for brevity.

***Eutyphoeus peguanus intermedius* Gates, 1958**

Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus f. *intermedius* Gates, 1958a: 141; 1972: 300.
Eutyphoeus peguanus intermedius Gates: Blakemore 2006a: 17.
Typhoeus peguanus intermedius (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Hlegu, Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ? **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus peguanus praecox* Gates, 1931**

Eutyphoeus peguanus var. *praecox* Gates, 1931: 426.
Eutyphoeus peguanus similis f. *praecox* Gates: Gates 1958a: 142.
Eutyphoeus peguanus praecox Gates: Blakemore 2006a: 17; 1972: 300.
Typhoeus peguanus praecox (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Shwegyin, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus peguanus promotus* Gates, 1930**

Eutyphoeus peguanus var. *promotus* Gates, 1930: 339.
Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus f. *promotus* Gates: Gates 1958a: 141.
Eutyphoeus peguanus promotus Gates: Blakemore 2006a: 17; 1972: 300.
Typhoeus peguanus promotus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus peguanus postremus* Gates, 1931**

Eutyphoeus peguanus var. *postremus* Gates, 1931: 427.
Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus f. *postremus* Gates:
Gates 1958a: 141.
Eutyphoeus peguanus postremus Gates: Blakemore
2006a: 17; 1972: 300.
Typhoeus peguanus postremus (Gates): Blakemore
2013a: 115.

Type locality. Syriam (Thanlyin), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic; **Remarks.** See remarks section of *E. p. peguanus*.

Eutyphoeus peguanus similis Gates, 1929

Eutyphoeus similis Gates, 1929: 37.
Eutyphoeus peguanus similis Gates: Gates 1958a: 142;
1972: 300.
Eutyphoeus peguanus similis Gates: Blakemore 2006a:
17.
Typhoeus peguanus similis (Gates): Blakemore 2013a:
115.

Type locality. Kawkareik (Gates 1972), Kayin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Eutyphoeus peguanus simplex Gates, 1930

Eutyphoeus peguanus var. *simplex* Gates, 1930: 340.
Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus f. *simplex* Gates:
Gates 1958a: 141.
Eutyphoeus peguanus simplex Gates: Blakemore
2006a: 17; 1972: 300.
Typhoeus peguanus simplex (Gates): Blakemore
2013a: 115.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Eutyphoeus peguanus tumidus Gates, 1930

Eutyphoeus peguanus var. *tumidus* Gates, 1930: 341.
Eutyphoeus peguanus peguanus f. *tumidus* Gates:
Gates 1958a: 142.

Eutyphoeus peguanus tumidus Gates: Blakemore
2006a: 17; 1972: 301.
Typhoeus peguanus tumidus (Gates): Blakemore
2013a: 115.

Type locality. Toungoo (Taungoo), Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Eutyphoeus pharpingianus Michaelsen, 1907

Eutyphoeus pharpingianus Michaelsen, 1907: 177.
Typhoeus pharpingianus Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Pharping (or Phamting), Nepal; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2863/7; **Distribution.** India, Nepal; **Status.** Endemic.

Eutyphoeus phawngpuiensis Tiwari, Lone, Thakur, James & Yadav, 2021

Eutyphoeus phawngpuiensis Tiwari et al., 2021b: 46.

Type locality. Close to Chhimtui in *Phawngpui* Blue Mountain National Park, Mizoram State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/24 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDM-272016005 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Eutyphoeus pius Gates, 1958

Eutyphoeus pius Gates, 1958a: 150.
Typhoeus pius (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Kyaiktiyo, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Eutyphoeus planatus Gates, 1929

Eutyphoeus planatus Gates, 1929: 10.
Typhoeus planatus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Thayetmyo (Thayet), Magway Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes in USNM 19258, ZSIC 1482; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus plenus* Gates, 1958**

Eutyphoeus plenus Gates, 1958a: 142.

Typhoeus plenus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Pyinmana, Naypyidaw Union Territory, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus pusillulus* Gates, 1931**

Eutyphoeus pusillulus Gates, 1931: 428.

Typhoeus pusillulus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Ye, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus quadripapillatus* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus quadripapillatus Michaelsen, 1907: 175.

Typhoeus quadripapillatus (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Saraghat (Saraighat), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2845-2846/7; MNHU 7260 (= ZMB Verm. 7260, anterior end, posterior end and middle fragment of 1 Syntype) (Hartwich & Kilius 1989); ZMUH 7135, 7153; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus quiquepertitus* Gates, 1930**

Eutyphoeus quiquepertitus Gates, 1930: 343.

Typhoeus quiquepertitus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Nyaungyo (Gates 1972), Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus rarus* Gates, 1925**

Eutyphoeus rarus Gates, 1925c: 59.

Typhoeus rarus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype

lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes in USNM 19657, BMNH 1926:6:5:30, ZSIC 1230, 3196, 1178; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus rihnimensis* Rodingpuia et al., 2024**

Eutyphoeus rihnimensis in Rodingpuia et al., 2024: 217.

Type locality. Khawrihnim village, Mizoram State, India (Rodingpuia et al. 2024); **Type depository.** PUCZM A/VI/1050 (Holotype), PUCZM A/VI/1050 to PUCZM A/VI/1056 (Paratypes) (Rodingpuia et al. 2024); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. As per International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 2012) recommendation, the type specimens have to be deposited in permanently curated facility and making them accessible for study (Art 16.4.2., Recommendation 16C and 72.10., Recommendation 72F). It means, type specimens are to be kept in a recognized, national or international research museum or facility or institution that maintains a research collection. But National Biodiversity Authority of India (National Biodiversity Authority 2023) has selected 15 centres as designated repositories for safeguarding every new animal taxon discovered in India. As per the guidelines (National Biodiversity Authority 2023) “any person, who discovers a new taxon of biological resources occurring in India, is required to notify it to the relevant designated repository and deposit its holotype/isotype/paratype there”. Here the types are kept in the university, which is in fact not a recognized national repository for keeping the type collections.

***Eutyphoeus sejunctus* Gates, 1930**

Eutyphoeus sejunctus Gates, 1930: 349.

Typhoeus sejunctus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Thandaung, Kyain State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3089, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus scutarius* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus scutarius Michaelsen, 1907: 186.

Typhoeus scutarius (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Comillah, Bangladesh; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2844/7: ZMUH V 7132; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Pakistan; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus serei* Tiwari, Lone, Thakur, James & Yadav, 2021**

Eutyphoeus serei Tiwari et al., 2021b: 48.

Type locality. Serei village in Dampa Tiger Reserve, Mizoram State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI-CZRC A20049 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDM 272016006 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus shiroensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus shiroensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 137.

Type locality. Shirui Kashong (Peak) in Shiroi National Park, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/15 (Holotype) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus spinulosus* Gates, 1926**

Eutyphoeus spinulosus Gates, 1926: 164.

Typhoeus spinulosus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Bassein (Pathein), Ayeyarwady Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus strigosus* Gates, 1933**

Eutyphoeus strigosus Gates, 1933: 598.

Typhoeus strigosus (Gates): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Shoko, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3104, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus tawi* Tiwari, Lone, Thakur, James & Yadav, 2021**

Eutyphoeus tawi Tiwari et al., 2021b: 50.

Type locality. Close to Chalkhahkawn River in Tawi Wildlife Sanctuary in Hualtu, Mizoram State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI-ZRC A20050 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDM 272016007 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus tengnoupalensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus tengnoupalensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 155.

Type locality. Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/12 (Holotype), MNP17-1079-44A15, MNP17-1080-44A6 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus turaensis* Stephenson, 1920**

Eutyphoeus turaensis Stephenson, 1920: 244.

Typhoeus turaensis (Stephenson): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Tura, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W178/1, W181/1, BM-NH 1933:5:25:280; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Eutyphoeus ukhrulensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus ukhrulensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 141.

Type locality. Shirui Kashong (Peak) in Shiroi National Park, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/16 (Holotype), MNP17-1120-45A17, MNP17-1131-45A29 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus unithecus* Ahmed & Marimuthu, 2025**

Eutyphoeus unithecus Ahmed & Marimuthu in Ahmed et al., 2025: 238.

Type locality. Khowai, Tripura State, India (Ahmed et al. 2025); **Type depository.** ZSI-GNC-An8034/2 (Holotype), ZSI-GNC-An8035/2 (Paratypes) (Ahmed et al. 2025); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus yangoupokpensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Eutyphoeus yangoupokpensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025b: 149.

Type locality. Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/8 (Holotype), MNP17-1085-44A11, MNP17-1089-44A15 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Eutyphoeus waltoni* Michaelsen, 1907**

Eutyphoeus waltoni Michaelsen, 1907: 179 (part).
Eutyphoeus bengalensis Michaelsen, 1907: 183.
Eutyphoeus ibrahimi Stephenson, 1914a: 357.
Typhoeus waltoni (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type locality. Mainpuri, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2849/7,

MNHU 7340 (= ZMB Verm. 7340, 1 Syntype) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), MZUT 101; ZMUH V 7163-5; **Distribution.** India, Pakistan; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Herbottodrilus* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004

Herbottodrilus Julka et al., 2004: 14.

Type species. *Herbottodrilus bahli* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats in Southern India).

***Herbottodrilus bahli* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Herbottodrilus bahli Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 15.

Type locality. Near Herbettu (Hirebettu), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HAZFS ZSI An-801 (Holotype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Hoplochaetella* Michaelsen, 1900

Perichaeta Schmarda: Bourne 1886: 667 (part).
Hoplochaeta Beddard, 1890a: 57.
Hoplochaetella Michaelsen, 1900: 321.
Erythraeodrilus Stephenson, 1915: 100.
Erythraeodrilus Stephenson: Blakemore 2013a: 115.

Type species. *Perichaeta stuarti* Perrier, 1886.

Distribution. India (mainly western coastal plains and Western Ghats in Maharashtra, Goa and Karnataka, Shevaroy Hills in Tamil Nadu, and Nandi Hills in Karnataka, one species is known to occur in Madhya Pradesh).

***Hoplochaetella affinis* Stephenson, 1917**

Hoplochaetella affinis Stephenson, 1917: 399 (part).
Erythraeodrilus suctorius var. *affinis* (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 466 (part).

Hoplochaetella affinis Stephenson: Gates 1940b: 209.

Type locality. Mormugao (Donna Paula Bay), Goa State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W128/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:49; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella anomala* Stephenson, 1920**

Hoplochaetella anomala Stephenson, 1920: 223.

Erythraeodrilus anomalus (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 458.

Hoplochaetella anomala (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 212.

Type locality. Belgaum (Belagavi), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 290/1, BMNH 1933:5:25:863-4; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella bifoveata* Stephenson, 1917**

Hoplochaetella bifoveata Stephenson, 1917: 395.

Erythraeodrilus kemp var. *bifoveatus* (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 462.

Hoplochaetella bifoveata (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 218.

Type locality. Talewadi near Castle Rock, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W129/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella darwini* Ahmed & Julka, 2023**

Hoplochaetella darwini Ahmed et al., 2023b: 175.

Type locality. Yercaud, Tamil Nadu State, India (Ahmed et al. 2023b); **Type depository.** ZSIC-GNC An7269/1 (Holotype), ZSIC-GNC An 7270/1 (Paratypes) (Ahmed et al. 2023b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella inornata* Stephenson, 1917**

Hoplochaetella inornata Stephenson, 1917: 395.

Erythraeodrilus inornatus (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 459.

Hoplochaetella inornata Stephenson: Gates 1940b: 219.

Type locality. Talewadi near Castle Rock, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W130/1; **Distribution.** India; **S.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella karnatakensis* Julka, 1988**

Hoplochaetella karnatakensis Julka, 1988a: 190.

Type locality. Kemmengundi (Kemmanagundi), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1816/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1817/1, HAZFS ZSI An724 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella kemp* Stephenson, 1917**

Hoplochaetella kemp Stephenson, 1917: 392.

Erythraeodrilus kemp (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 460 (part, excluding var. *bifoveatus*).

Hoplochaetella kemp (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 221.

Type locality. Talewadi near Castle Rock, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W 68/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:41; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella khandalaensis khandalaensis* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Erythraeodrilus khandalaensis Stephenson, 1924b: 350.

Hoplochaetella khandalaensis (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 225.

Hoplochaetella khandalaensis khandalaensis (Stephenson): Julka 1988a: 196.

Type locality. Khandala, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1137/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:122; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella khandalaensis dichordarius* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Erythraeodrilus khandalaensis f. *dichordarius* Stephenson, 1924b: 352.

Hoplochaetella khandalaensis dichordarius (Stephenson): Julka 1988a: 198.

Type locality. Bombay (Mumbai), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella kinneari* (Stephenson, 1915)**

Erythraeodrilus kinneari Stephenson, 1915: 100 (part).
Hoplochaetella kinneari (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 249.

Type locality. Castle Rock (Catslerock), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W26/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality so far.

***Hoplochaetella kurmagarensis* Gates, 1945**

Hoplochaetella kurmagarensis Gates, 1945a: 88.

Type locality. Kurmagar (Kurumagad) Island, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Hoplochaetella lavellei* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Hoplochaetella lavellei Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 20.

Type locality. Near Herbetu (Hirebetu) on way to Karni, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HAZFS ZSI An806 (Holotype), HAZFS ZSI An807 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella londensis* Julka, 1988**

Hoplochaetella londensis Julka, 1988a: 203.

Type locality. Londa, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An 1818/1 (Holotype),

ZSIC An 1819/1, HARC-ZSI An-729 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Hoplochaetella mullani* Stephenson, 1924**

Erythraeodrilus mullani Stephenson, 1924b: 348.
Hoplochaetella mullani (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 233.

Type locality. Matheran, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1136/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:78; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella panchganiensis* Julka, 1988**

Hoplochaetella panchganiensis Julka, 1988a: 207.

Type locality. Panchgani, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1820/1 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An730, HARC-ZSI An731 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Hoplochaetella powelli* (Stephenson, 1925)**

Erythraeodrilus powelli Stephenson, 1925a: 898.
Hoplochaetella powelli (Stephenson): Gates 1940b: 236.

Type locality. Bombay (Mumbai), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1136/1, BMNH 1924:2:14:13-8; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella righii* Julka, 1988**

Hoplochaetella righii Julka, 1988a: 213.

Type locality. Kotegehar (Kottigehara), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1821/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1822/1, HARC-ZSI An725 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella sanvordemensis* Julka, 1988**

Hoplochaetella sanvordemensis Julka, 1988a: 216.

Type locality. Sanvordem, Goa State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1823 (Holotype), ZSIC An1824/1, HARC-ZSI An732 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella stuarti* (Bourne, 1886)**

Perichaeta stuarti Bourne, 1886: 667.
Hoplochaetella stuarti (Bourne): Gates 1940b: 239.

Type locality. Yercaadu (Yercaud), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH 9673; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Hoplochaetella suctoria* Stephenson, 1917**

Hoplochaetella suctoria Stephenson, 1917: 388.
Erythraeodrilus suctorius (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 464 (part, excluding var. *affinis* = *H. affinis* Stephenson).
Hoplochaetella suctoria Stephenson: Gates 1940b: 244.

Type locality. Sanvordem, Goa State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W67/1, BMNH 1933:5: 25:857–62; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Karmiella* Julka, 1983

Karmiella Julka, 1983: 48.

Type species. *Karmiella karnatakensis* Julka, 1983.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats in Southern India).

***Karmiella karnatakensis* Julka, 1983**

Karmiella karnatakensis Julka, 1983: 48.

Type locality. Tirthahalli (Thirthahalli), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HAZFS ZSI An395 (Holotype), HAZFS ZSI An396 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Karmiella sulvalliensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Karmiella sulvalliensis Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 22.

Type locality. Sulvalli, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An 808 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An 809 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Konkadrilus* Julka, 1988

Konkadrilus Julka, 1988a: 226.

Type species. *Howascolex stephensoni* Soota & Julka, 1972.

Distribution. India (Goa and Western Karnataka).

***Konkadrilus bahli* (Soota & Julka, 1972)**

Howascolex bahli Soota & Julka, 1972: 402.
Konkadrilus bahli (Soota & Julka): Julka 1988a: 229.

Type locality. Satpalli, Goa State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An154/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An155/1, ZSIC An156/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Konkadrilus gatesi* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Konkadrilus gatesi Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 19.

Type locality. Near Herbetu (Hirebetu), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An804 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An805 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Konkadrilus shimogensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Konkadrilus shimogensis Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 16.

Type locality. Sulvalli, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An802 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An803 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Konkadrilus stephensoni* (Soota & Julka, 1972)**

Howascolex stephensoni Soota & Julka, 1972: 401.
Konkadrilus stephensoni (Soota & Julka): Julka 1988a: 232.

Type locality. Valpoi, Goa State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An152/1 (Holotype), An153/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Konkadrilus tirthahalliensis* Julka, 1988**

Konkadrilus tirthahalliensis Julka, 1988a: 235.

Type locality. Tirthahalli (Thirthahalli), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1827/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1828/1, HARC-ZSI An737 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Konkadrilus zicsii* Julka, 1988**

Konkadrilus zicsii Julka, 1988a: 237.

Type locality. Castle Rock, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1825/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1826/1, HARC-ZSI An735 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Kotegeharia* Julka, 1988

Kotegeharia Julka, 1988a: 239.

Type species. *Kotegeharia gatesi* Julka, 1988.

Distribution. India (Karnataka in southern India).

***Kotegeharia gatesi* Julka, 1988**

Kotegeharia gatesi Julka, 1988a: 240.

Type locality. Kotegehar (Kottigehara), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1829/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1830/1, HARC-ZSI An738 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Lennogaster* Gates, 1940

Eudichogaster Michaelsen: Stephenson 1920: 246 (part).

Lennogaster Gates, 1940a: 183.

Type species. *Eudichogaster yeicus* Stephenson, 1931.

Distribution. India (from Myanmar boarder through the Gangetic plain into northern portions of the peninsula and lower western Himalaya), Myanmar; Bangladesh. Perhaps the only peregrine is *Lennogaster pusilla*, known from India and from Sumba Island, Indonesia (Blakemore 2012a).

***Lennogaster chittagongensis* (Stephenson, 1917)**

Eudichogaster chittagongensis Stephenson, 1917: 411.
Lennogaster chittagongensis (Stephenson): Gates 1940a: 192.

Type locality. Rangamati, Bangladesh; **Type depository.** ZSIC W71/1, BMNH 1933:5:25:344-5; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Lennogaster dashi* Senapati, Julka & Dash, 1990**

Lennogaster dashi Senapati, Julka & Dash, 1990: 467.

Type locality. Bargarh, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An812 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An813 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Lennogaster elongata* Gates, 1945**

Lennogaster elongatus Gates, 1945b: 248.

Lennogaster elongata (Gates): Blakemore 2007a: 17.

Type locality. Nowgong (Grain Market in Gola Bazaar), Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3631; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Lennogaster falcifer* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Eudichogaster falcifer Stephenson, 1920: 252.
Lennogaster falcifer (Stephenson): Gates 1940a: 184.

Type locality. Jabulpore (Jabalpur), Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W297/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:94; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Lennogaster pusilla* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Eudichogaster pusillus Stephenson, 1920: 253.
Eudichogaster barkudensis Stephenson, 1921a: 765.
Lennogaster pusillus (Stephenson): Gates 1945b: 252.
Lennogaster pusilla (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 18.

Type locality. Saugor (Sagar), Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:5:25:346-7; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Indonesia; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Lennogaster trichochaeta* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Eudichogaster trichochaetus Stephenson, 1920:249.
Lennogaster trichochaetus (Stephenson): Gates 1940a: 185.
Lennogaster trichochaeta (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 18.

Type locality. Palchar (Palghar), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W277/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:111; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Lennogaster yeica* (Stephenson, 1931)**

Eudichogaster yeicus Stephenson, 1931c: 193.
Lennogaster yeicus (Stephenson): Gates 1940a: 186.
Lennogaster yeica (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 18.

Type locality. Chaungson, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1930:12: 27:36-7; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Mallehulla* Julka & Rao, 1982

Mallehulla Julka and Rao, 1982: 67.

Type species. *Mallehulla indica* Julka & Rao, 1982.

Distribution. India (South-western India).

***Mallehulla indica* Julka & Rao, 1982**

Mallehulla indica Julka & Rao, 1982: 70.

Type locality. Moodabidri (Mudbidri), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HAZFS ZSI An322 has been transferred to ZSI-Kolkata with register number ZSIC An1507/1 (Holotype), HAZFS ZSI An323 to An332, two exemplars of HAZFS ZSI An323 has been transferred to ZSI-Kolkata with register number ZSIC An1508/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Microcolex* Rosa, 1887

Microcolex Rosa, 1887: 1.

Type species. *Microcolex modestus* Rosa, 1887 (= *Lumbricus phosphoreus* Dugès, 1837) (Blakemore 2012a).

Distribution. Circum-antarctic, origin in southern South America, with two peregrine species due to transportation (Blakemore 2012).

***Microcolex dubius* (Fletcher, 1887)**

Eudrilus(?) dubius Fletcher, 1887: 378.
Microcolex dubius: Rosa, 1891: 388.
For synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Sydney, Australia; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar? Pakistan;

Elsewhere. Circummundane in warmer regions of the world (Blakemore 2012a) and the supposed home of this species is in southern S. America (Gates 1972); Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira Island (Portugal), South Africa; Americas: Argentina, South America, USA; Asia: Israel, Japan, Jordan, Turkiye; Europe: Mediterranean Europe, Greece, North Macedonia, Spain; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand, Norfolk Island (Australia); **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Microscolex phosphoreus* (Dugès, 1837)**

Lumbricus phosphoreus Dugès, 1837: 17, 24.

Microscolex modestus Rosa, 1887: 1.

Deltania troyeri Eisen, 1893: 251.

Microscolex phosphoreus (Dugès): Michaelsen 1900: 141.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Montpellier, France; **Type depository.** None; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar? Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Widely distributed peregrine species mainly in the subtropics and the Mediterranean regions, probably indigenous to southern South America (Gates 1972); Africa: Algeria, Canary islands (Spain), Lesotho, South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, El Salvador, Mexico, Paraguay, South Patagonia, USA; Asia: Middle East, Israel, Japan, Turkiye; Europe: Southern Europe, Bulgaria, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Jersey, Poland, Switzerland, Yugoslavia; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii (USA), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Octochaetoides* Michaelsen, 1922

Octochaetus Beddard: Michaelsen 1900: 319 (part).

Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) Michaelsen, 1922: 37 (part).

Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) Michaelsen: Stephenson 1923: 371 (part).

Octochaetoides Gates, 1962b: 14.

Type species. *Benhamia aitkeni* Fedarb, 1898.

Distribution. India (Kerala in south west India).

***Octochaetoides aitkeni* (Fedarb, 1898)**

Benhamia aitkeni Fedarb, 1898a: 432.

Octochaetus aitkeni (Fedarb): Michaelsen 1899a: 242.

Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) aitkeni (Fedarb): Michaelsen 1922: 37.

Octochaetoides aitkeni (Fedarb): Gates 1962b: 14.

Type locality. Travancore, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:20:240; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Octochaetona* Gates, 1962

Octochaetus Beddard: Michaelsen 1909: 203 (part).

Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) Michaelsen: Stephenson 1923: 371 (part).

Octochaetoides Gates 1945a: 75 (part).

Octochaetona Gates, 1962b: 211.

Type species. *Octochaetus surensis* Michaelsen, 1910.

Distribution. Mainly in Peninsular India (but extended to other parts of the country), also Pakistan, Nepal, Malay Peninsula, Myanmar, Philippines, Vietnam etc., presumably due to transportation of the type species and *O. beatrix* (Julka 1988a).

***Octochaetona albida* (Gates, 1945)**

Octochaetoides albidus Gates, 1945a: 77.

Octochaetona albida (Gates): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3660/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona barkudensis* (Stephenson, 1916)**

Octochaetus barkudensis Stephenson, 1916: 340.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) barkudensis (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 373.
Octochaetona barkudensis (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Barkuda Island in Chilka Lake, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV 6575/7, BMNH 1933:2:16:4-5; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona barnesi* (Stephenson, 1925)**

Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) barnesi Stephenson, 1925b: 68.
Octochaetona barnesi (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Horsleykonda (Horsley Hills, Yenugulla Mallamma Konda), Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:2:23: 478-480; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona beatrix* (Beddard, 1902)**

Octochaetus beatrix Beddard, 1902: 456.
Octochaetus fermori Michaelsen, 1907: 171.
Octochaetus hodgarti Michaelsen, 1907: 172.
Octochaetus pittnyi Michaelsen, 1910: 86.
Octochaetus dasi Stephenson, 1914a: 346.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) fermori tetracystis Stephenson, 1924b: 343.
Octochaetus lunatus Gates, 1929: 24.
Octochaetoides beatrix (Beddard): Gates 1945b: 48.
Octochaetona beatrix (Beddard): Gates 1962b: 213.
 Further synonyms in Gates (1972), Julka (1988a) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Calcutta (Kolkata), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:242; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: Malaysia, Philippines, Vietnam; Oceania: Australia; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Octochaetona compta* (Gates, 1945)**

Octochaetoides comptus Gates, 1945a: 80
Octochaetona compta (Gates): Gates, 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Nellore, Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3661/1. **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona excavata* (Stephenson, 1925)**

Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) excavatus Stephenson, 1925b: 69.
Octochaetona excavata (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Horsleykonda (Horsley Hills, Yenugulla Mallamma Konda), Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:2:23: 481-3; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality (Julka 1988a).

***Octochaetona maindroni* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Octochaetus maindroni f. *typica* Michaelsen, 1907: 168.
Octochaetus maindroni var. *chaperi* Michaelsen, 1907: 169.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) maindroni (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 382.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) maindroni var. *chaperi* (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 383.
Octochaetona maindroni (Michaelsen): Gates 1962a: 213.

Type locality. Gingi (Gingee), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona paliensis* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Octochaetus phillotti Michaelsen, 1907: 169 (part).
Octochaetus paliensis Stephenson, 1920: 228.
Octochaetus paliensis var. *riparius* Stephenson, 1920: 231.
Octochaetus ganeshae Stephenson, 1920: 238.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) paliensis (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 385.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) var. riparius (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 386.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) phillotti (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 390 (part).
Octochaetona paliensis (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Palia, Madhya Pradesh, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1938:5:25:886-8; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona parva* (Gates, 1945)**

Octochaetoides parvus Gates, 1945a: 84.
Octochaetona parva (Gates): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Nellore, Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3662/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona pattoni* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Octochaetus pattoni Michaelsen, 1907: 170 (part).
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) pattoni (Michaelsen):
Stephenson 1923: 388 (part).
Octochaetona pattoni (Michaelsen): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Madras (Chennai) city, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV 2856-2862/7, BMNH 1925: 5: 12: 124, MNHU 7336 (= ZMB Verm. 7336, 1 Syntype in 3 fragments) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), ZMUH 7159; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona phillotti* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Octochaetus phillotti Michaelsen, 1907: 169 (part).
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) phillotti (Michaelsen):
Stephenson 1923: 390 (part).
Octochaetona phillotti (Michaelsen): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Hyderabad, Telangana State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2853/7, BMNH 1925: 5: 12: 42, MNHU 7343 (= ZMB Verm. 7343, posterior fragment of one 1 syntype) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), ZMUH, 7138; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona prashadi* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Octochaetus prashadi Stephenson, 1920: 233.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) prashadi (Stephenson):
Stephenson 1923: 392.
Octochaetona prashadi (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Kalayan (Kalyan), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W267/1,

BMNH 1933:5:25:897-901; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona serrata* (Gates, 1945)**

Octochaetus pattoni Michaelsen, 1907: 170 (part).
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) pattoni (Michaelsen):
Stephenson 1923: 388 (part).
Octochaetoides serratus Gates, 1945a: 87.
Octochaetona serrata (Gates): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Madras (Chennai) city, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Octochaetona surensis* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Octochaetus surensis Michaelsen, 1910: 88.
Octochaetus surensi (mispr.): Stephenson 1916: 338.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) surensis (Michaelsen):
Stephenson 1923: 394.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) birmanicus Gates, 1925c: 55.
Octochaetoides surensis (Michaelsen): Gates 1955: 78.
Octochaetona surensis (Michaelsen): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Sur (Sar or Sara) Lake in Puri, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3602 (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Introduced to Myanmar (Gates 1972).

***Octochaetona thurstoni* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Octochaetus thurstoni Michaelsen, 1907: 173.
Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) thurstoni (Michaelsen):
Stephenson 1923: 396.
Octochaetona thurstoni (Michaelsen): Gates 1962b: 213.

Type locality. Madras (Chennai) city, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV 2855/7, ZMUH V 7158; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Octonochaeta* Julka, 1988

Octonochaeta Julka, 1988a: 298.

Type species. *Octochaetus (Octochaetoides) roseus* Stephenson, 1926.

Distribution. India (Deccan region of Andhra Pradesh and Telangana).

***Octonochaeta rosea* (Stephenson, 1926)**

Octochaetus (*Octochaetoides*) *roseus* Stephenson, 1926: 259.

Octochaetona rosea (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 213.

Octochaetoides sudarshensis Sharma & Chacko, 1970: 2.

Octonochaeta rosea (Stephenson): Julka 1988a: 299.

Type locality. Secunderabad, Telangana Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3152 /1; BMNH 1973:2:23:472-3; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Parryodrilus* Julka, Giri, Panigrahi & Senapati, 1997

Parryodrilus Julka et al., 1997: 142.

Type species. *Parryodrilus lavellei* Julka, Giri, Panigrahi & Senapati, 1997.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats of Kerala in southwestern India).

***Parryodrilus lavellei* Julka, Giri, Panigrahi & Senapati, 1997**

Parryodrilus lavellei Julka et al., 1997: 142.

Type locality. Nilambur, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An815 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An816 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Pellogaster* Gates, 1940

Eudichogaster Michaelsen: Stephenson 1920: 246 (part).

Eudichogaster Michaelsen: Stephenson 1923: 402 (part).

Pellogaster Gates, 1940a: 200.

Type species. *Eudichogaster bengalensis* Michaelsen, 1910.

Distribution. India (North-eastern portion of the Peninsular India from Jabalpur to Odisha and West Bengal, and the Western Ghats in Maharashtra). *P. bengalensis* is reported from Bangladesh.

***Pellogaster bengalensis* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Eudichogaster bengalensis Michaelsen, 1910: 96.

Pellogaster bengalensis (Michaelsen): Gates 1940a: 201.

Pellogaster bengalensis f. *orissanus* Gates, 1940a: 205.

Pellogaster bengalensis f. *jubbulporensis* Gates, 1940a: 206.

Pellogaster bengalensis (Michaelsen): Julka 1978: 194.

Type locality. Tribeni, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV 3506/7; ZMUH V 3608; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Pellogaster isabellae* Gates, 1945**

Pellogaster isabellae Gates, 1945b: 245.

Type locality. Naini, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3667/1, W3668 /1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Pellogaster simsi* Julka, 1988**

Pellogaster simsi Julka, 1988a: 308.

Type locality. Panchgani, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1833/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1834/1, HARC-ZSI An754 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Priodochaeta* Gates, 1940

Perichaeta Bourne, 1894a: 13 (part).

Diporochoeta Beddard: Michaelsen 1900: 207 (part).

Diporochoeta Beddard: Stephenson 1923: 315 (part).

Priodochaeta Gates, 1940c: 116.

Type species. *Perichaeta pellucida* Bourne, 1894.

Distribution. India (known only from three localities in the Nilgiri Hills of Western Ghats, in Tamil Nadu State, India).

***Priodochaeta pellucida* (Bourne, 1894)**

Perichaeta pellucida Bourne, 1894a: 13.

Diporochoeta pellucida (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900: 207.

Priodochaeta pellucida (Bourne): Gates 1940c: 116.

Type locality. Coonoor, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1895:9:3:11; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Priodoscolex* Gates, 1940

Priodoscolex Gates, 1940c: 122.

Type species. *Priodoscolex montanus* Gates, 1940.

Distribution. India (known only from the Nandi Hills of Karnataka, in southern India).

***Priodoscolex maduraiensis* Ahmed & Marimuthu, 2025**

Priodoscolex maduraiensis Ahmed & marimuthu in Ahmed et al., 2025: 242.

Type locality. Madurai, Tamil Nadu State, India (Ahmed et al. 2025); **Type depository.** ZSI–GNC–An8036/2 (Holotype), ZSI–GNC–An 8037/2 (Paratypes) (Ahmed et al. 2025); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Priodoscolex montanus* Gates, 1940**

Priodoscolex montanus Gates, 1940c: 123.

Type locality. Nandydroog (Nandi Hills), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** Type is

currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

Genus *Ramiella* Stephenson, 1921

Octochaetus Beddard: Stephenson 1914a: 347 (part).

Ramiella Stephenson, 1921b: 109.

Ramella (lapsus pro *Ramiella*) Stephenson: Michaelsen 1922: 37.

Type species. *Octochaetus bishambari* Stephenson, 1914.

Distribution. India (Indo-Gangetic Plain, Peninsula and Coorg); extended to Myanmar, Christmas Island, Philippines and China, probably as a result of transportation of the type species.

***Ramiella bishambari* (Stephenson, 1914)**

Octochaetus bishambari Stephenson, 1914a: 347.

Octochaetus pachpaharensis Stephenson, 1920: 239.

Ramiella bishambari (Stephenson): Stephenson 1921b: 109.

?*Ramiella parva* Stephenson 1924b: 344.

Ramiella cultrifera Stephenson, 1931c: 187.

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012).

Type locality. Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:5:25: 918-9; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Christmas Island (Australia), Philippines, Vietnam; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Ramiella heterochaeta* Michaelsen, 1922**

Ramella heterochaeta Michaelsen, 1922: 51.

Ramiella heterochaeta Michaelsen: Stephenson 1923: 399.

Type locality. Somavarpatna (Somwarpet, Somwarpet), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH 9154 (Julka 1988a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Ramiella nainiana* Gates, 1945**

Ramiella nainiana Gates, 1945b: 232.

Type locality. Naini, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W3639/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Ramiella pallida* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Octochaetus pallidus Stephenson, 1920: 236.

Ramiella pallida (Stephenson): Stephenson 1921b: 109.

Type locality. Panchgani, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W260/1, BMNH 1933:5:25:906-8; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Ramiella sundargarhensis* Julka, 1978**

Ramiella sundargarhensis Julka, 1978: 190.

Type locality. Sundargarh, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An307/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An308/1 (Paratype) (Julka 1978); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Rillogaster* Gates, 1940

Eudichogaster (part) Michaelsen: Stephenson 1924b: 345.

Rillogaster Gates, 1940a: 207.

Type species. *Eudichogaster matheranensis* Stephenson, 1924.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats in Maharashtra and Goa).

***Rillogaster eastoni* Julka, 1988**

Rillogaster eastoni Julka, 1988a: 329.

Type locality. Sanvordem, Goa State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An-1835/1 (Holotype),

ZSIC An1836/1, HARC-ZSI An750 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Rillogaster matheranensis* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Eudichogaster matheranensis Stephenson, 1924b: 346.

Rillogaster matheranensis (Stephenson): Gates 1940a: 208.

Type locality. Matheran, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1155/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:5; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Scolioscolides* Gates, 1937

Megascolides McCoy: Michaelsen 1907: 150.

Megascolides McCoy: Stephenson 1923: 192 (part).

Scolioscolides Gates, 1937b: 305.

Type species. *Megascolides bergtheili* Michaelsen, 1907.

Distribution. India (mainly in the Himalaya east of Darjeeling, in West Bengal, India) and Nepal.

***Scolioscolides bergtheili* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Megascolides bergtheili Michaelsen, 1907: 150.

Scolioscolides bergtheili (Michaelsen): Gates 1937b: 307.

Type locality. Sandakphu, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2951/7, ZMUH V 7173; **Distribution.** India, Nepal; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Senapatiella* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004

Senapatiella Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 4.

Type species. *Senapatiella alfredi* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats of Karnataka in southern India).

***Senapatiella alfredi* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Senapatiella alfredi Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 5.

Type locality. 4 km from Kogar down to Bhatkal, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An791 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An 792 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Senapatiella ghatensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Senapatiella ghatensis Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 8.

Type locality. 12 km W Kogar down to Bhatkal, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An793 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An 794 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Senapatiella herbettuensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Senapatiella herbettuensis Julka et al., 2004: 9.

Type locality. Herbettu (Hirebettu), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An795 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An796 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Shimodrilus* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004

Shimodrilus Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 9.

Type species. *Shimodrilus bhatkalensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats of Karnataka in southern India).

***Shimodrilus bhatkalensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Shimodrilus bhatkalensis Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 11.

Type locality. Bhatkal road, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An797 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An798 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Shimodrilus karniensis* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Shimodrilus karniensis Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 13.

Type locality. Near Karni, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An799 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An800 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Travoscolides* Gates, 1940

Megascolides McCoy (part): Stephenson 1915: 63.
Travoscolides Gates, 1940c: 137.

Type species. *Megascolides chengannures* Aiyer, 1929.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats of Kerala in south western India).

***Travoscolides chengannures* (Aiyer, 1929)**

Megascolides chengannures Aiyer, 1929: 54.
Travoscolides chengannures (Aiyer): Gates 1940c: 139.

Type locality. Chengannur, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1514/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Travoscolides cochiniensis* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Megascolides cochiniensis Michaelsen, 1910: 56.

Travoscolides cochinchensis (Michaelsen): Gates 1940c: 141.

Type locality. Foot of Nelliampathis (Nelliampathy) Hills, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3598 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Travoscolides duodecimalis* (Stephenson, 1915)**

Megascolides duodecimalis Stephenson, 1915: 65.
Travoscolides duodecimalis (Stephenson): Gates 1940c: 142.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6596/7, BMNH 1933:5:25:80; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Travoscolides pilatus* (Stephenson, 1915)**

Megascolides pilatus Stephenson, 1915: 68.
Travoscolides pilatus (Stephenson): Gates 1940c: 142.

Type locality. Parambikulam, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV6919, BMNH 1933:5:25:86; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the Type depository.

Genus *Wahoscolex* Julka, 1988

Wahoscolex Julka, 1988a: 342.

Type species. *Howascolex corethrurus* Michaelsen, 1922.

Distribution. India (Western Ghats and Nandi Hills in Karnataka, Southern India).

***Wahoscolex* (?) *bidens* (Michaelsen, 1922)**

Howascolex bidens Michaelsen, 1922: 38.
Wahoscolex (?) *bidens* (Michaelsen): Julka 1988a: 346.

Type locality. Shiboga (Shivamogga), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 9161; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Wahoscolex bouchei* Julka, 1988**

Wahoscolex bouchei Julka, 1988a: 347.

Type locality. Kemmengundi, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1808/1 (Holotype), ZSIC 1809/1, HARC-ZSI An756 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality so far.

***Wahoscolex corethrurus* (Michaelsen, 1922)**

Howascolex corethrurus Michaelsen, 1922: 42.
Wahoscolex corethrurus (Michaelsen): Julka 1988a: 349.

Type locality. Somavarapatna (Somwarpet, Somwarpet), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 9163 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Wahoscolex curgensis* Julka, 1988**

Wahoscolex curgensis Julka, 1988a: 352.

Type locality. Mercara (Madikeri), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1810/1 (Holotype); HARC-ZSI An758 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Wahoscolex* (?) *ditheca* (Michaelsen, 1922)**

Howascolex corethrurus f. *ditheca* Michaelsen, 1922: 42.
Wahoscolex (?) *ditheca* (Michaelsen): Julka 1988a: 354.

Type locality. Shimoga (Shivamogga), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 9158 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Wahoscolex horai* Julka, 1988**

Wahoscolex horai Julka, 1988a: 356.

Type locality. Bhagamandala, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1811/1 (Holotype), HAZFS ZSI An759 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Wahoscolex* (?) *merkaraensis* (Michaelsen, 1922)**

Howascolex merkaraensis Michaelsen, 1922: 47.

Wahoscolex (?) *merkaraensis* (Michaelsen): Julka 1988a: 359.

Type locality. Merkara (Madikeri), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 9155, 9156; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Wahoscolex michaelseni* Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004**

Wahoscolex michaelseni Julka, Blanchart & Chapuis-Lardy, 2004: 23.

Type locality. Near Herbettu (Hirebettu), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An810 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An811 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Wahoscolex nandiensis* Julka, 1988**

Wahoscolex nandiensis Julka, 1988a: 360.

Type locality. Nandi Hills, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1812/1 (Holo-

type), ZSIC An1813/1, HARC-ZSI An760 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Wahoscolex veereshi* Julka, 1988**

Wahoscolex veereshi Julka, 1988a: 362.

Type locality. Kemmengundi, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1814/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An1815/1 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Family ALMIDAE Duboscq, 1902

Genus *Glyphidrilus* Horst, 1889

Glyphidrilus Horst, 1889: 86.

Bilimba Rosa, 1890a: 386

Annadrilus Horst, 1893: 44.

Progizzardus Nair, 2010: 54. **syn. nov.**

Type species. *Glyphidrilus weberi* Horst, 1889.

Distribution. Africa: Tanzania; Asia: Cambodia, China (Hainan), India, Indonesia (Sumatra, Java, Flores, Borneo, Sulawesi); Laos, Malay peninsula, Myanmar, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Vietnam.

Remarks. *Progizzardus* Nair, 2010, is a monotypic genus described by Nair *et al.* (2010) from the state of Kerala, India. Narayanan *et al.* (2023a) have already suggested that its type species *Progizzardus varadimensis* is probably a synonym of *Glyphidrilus annandalei* Michaelsen, 1910. Hence we critically reviewed the original description and reinvestigated the type materials of *P. varadimensis*. It revealed that the type materials are undissected immature specimens of a *Glyphidrilus* species, most probably of *G. annandalei* Michaelsen, 1910. Hence the genus *Progizzardus* is synonymised with *Glyphidrilus*. Details of the the same is furnished below.

***Glyphidrilus* sp. juv.**

Progizzardus vardiamensis Nair, 2010 in Nair et al. 2010: 54–55.

Material examined. *Progizzardus vardiamensis* Nair, 2010, genus et. sp. nov., **Holotype.** Aclitellate, undissected, Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.-INV.2056; **Paratypes.** Aclitellates, undissected, Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.-INV.2057 and ZSI/WGRC/I.R.-INV.2058. Loc. Vardiam, Thrissur district, Kerala State, India, Leg. Vijayakumar Nair K., Jaya M. and Aja M., date of collection. 17-03-2006.

Remarks. The taxonomic description of *Progizzardus vardiamensis* was based on three type specimens (Nair et al. 2010). Our examination of the holotype and paratypes showed that it was not dissected, and anatomical characteristics of the species were presumably based on some other materials, but details of such materials are not provided in the original description. As per the label, the type specimens are named ‘*Glyphidrilus*’ instead of the newly proposed name ‘*Progizzardus*’. The author may have initially retained the new species under *Glyphidrilus*, and later moved them to the new genus *Progizzardus*.

Dissection was performed on the holotype, and one paratype (ZSI/WGRC/I.R.-INV.2058) and it revealed some errors in the description of the species relating to the following important characteristics. i) All the materials are aclitellates, but as per the original publication all are clitellates; ii) male pore not visible but Nair et al. (2010) stated that male pore is minute and present on segment 13; iii) none of the type materials possess any genital markings but it is stated that genital markings are present on segments 21–26 and even shown in figure 1.1 in the original description; iv) gizzard is present, well developed, in the region of 7/8, mostly in segment 8 but as per the original description it is at segment 4; v) seminal vesicles are in segments 9, 10, 11, 12, whereas it is in segments 9, 11, 12, 13; vi) calciferous glands are absent the dissected specimens but it is present in original description (in segment 6–11 or

extending upto segment 33). From the above mentioned features it is clear that the type materials are completely immature and obviously a glyphidrilid species. Due to its immature state its exact species cannot be determined. Even though due to the absence of dorsal pores, male pores, presence of well developed gizzard mainly in segment 8 and the presence of seminal vesicles in segments 9, 10, 11, 12, it can be referred to the widespread *Glyphidrilus* species, most probably of *G. annandalei* Michaelsen, 1910.

***Glyphidrilus annandalei* Michaelsen, 1910**

Glyphidrilus annandalei Michaelsen, 1910: 101.
Glyphidrilus achencoili Cognetti, 1911: 506 (*lapsus*).
Glyphidrilus rarus Rao, 1922: 64.
Glyphidrilus safforensis Rao, 1922: 66.
Progizzardus vardiamensis Nair, 2010: 54. **syn. nov.**

Type locality. Quilon (Kollam), India; **Type depository.** ZMH 3600 (Lectotype), ZMH 3600.1 (Paralectotype) (Chanabun et al. 2013); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Glyphidrilus birmanicus* Gates, 1958**

Glyphidrilus birmanicus Gates, 1958c: 61.
Glyphidrilus birmanicus Gates: Gates 1972: 236.
Glyphidrilus birmanicus Gates: Chanabun et al. 2020: 215.

Type locality. Burma (Myanmar); **Type depository.** USNM 124766, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Glyphidrilus ceylonensis* Gates, 1945**

Glyphidrilus ceylonensis Gates, 1945e: 89.

Type locality. Pelmadulla, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Glyphidrilus elegans* Rao, 1922**

Glyphidrilus elegans Rao, 1922: 62.
Glyphidrilus elegans Rao: Chanabun *et al.* 2013: 29.

Type locality. Sandy islets in the Cauvery River in Dubari forests at Fraserpett (= Kushalnagar), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1922:4:20:9, ZMUH 9171; but as per Chanabun *et al.* (2013) at BMNH [as NHM] 1922:4:20:10 (Lectotype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Glyphidrilus fluviatilis* Rao, 1922**

Glyphidrilus fluviatilis Rao, 1922: 53.
Glyphidrilus annandalei Rao: Stephenson 1922b: 387.
Glyphidrilus fluviatilis Rao: Chanabun *et al.* 2013: 27.

Type locality. Sandy banks of Harangi River in Madapur, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1922:4:20:5, ZMUH 419, ZMUH 9174; according to Chanabun *et al.* (2013) at BMNH [as NHM] 1922:4:20:618 (Lectotype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Glyphidrilus gangeticus* Gates, 1958**

Glyphidrilus papillatus (Rosa): Stephenson 1920: 258.
Glyphidrilus papillatus (Rosa): Stephenson 1923: 493 (part, excluding all but Lucknow worms).
Glyphidrilus gangeticus Gates, 1958c: 55.

Type locality. Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India, Nepal; **Status.** Endemic.

***Glyphidrilus horsti* Stephenson, 1930**

Glyphidrilus horsti Stephenson, 1930: 4.
Glyphidrilus horsti Stephenson: Chanabun *et al.* 2020: 213.

Type locality. Pulau Berhala, Straits of Malacca (Chanabun *et al.* 2020); **Type depository.**

RNHL 1595; Distribution. Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand (Chanabun *et al.* 2020); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Glyphidrilus papillatus* (Rosa, 1890)**

Bilimba papillata Rosa, 1890a: 386.
Glyphidrilus papillatus (Rosa): Michaelsen 1896: 195.
Glyphidrilus papillatus (Rosa): Gates 1972: 236.
Glyphidrilus papillatus (Rosa): Chanabun *et al.* 2020: 210.

Type locality. Cobapo Village (Carin Cheba or Biapo), Myanmar (Rosa 1890a); **Type depository.** RNHL 1595; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand (Chanabun *et al.* 2020); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Glyphidrilus spelaeotes* Stephenson, 1924**

Glyphidrilus spelaeotes Stephenson, 1924a: 133.

Type locality. Siju Cave, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1155-6, BMNH 1925:5:12:96-7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Glyphidrilus tonywhitteni* Chanabun & Panha, 2020**

Glyphidrilus tonywhitteni Chanabun & Panha in Chanabun *et al.*, 2020: 207.

Type locality. Bank of Paalaung River at Mandalay, Mandalay Region, Myanmar (Chanabun *et al.* 2020); **Type depository.** CUMZ 3801 (Holotype), CUMZ 3812, LKCNHM, ZMH 14585, NHMUK (Chanabun *et al.* 2020); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Glyphidrilus tuberosus* Stephenson, 1916**

Glyphidrilus tuberosus Stephenson, 1916: 349.

Type locality. Kendupatna Canal and ponds at Pubhans near Cuttack, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6517; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

Family BENHAMIIDAE Michaelsen, 1897

Genus *Dichogaster* Beddard, 1888

Dichogaster Beddard, 1888b: 251.

Microdrilus Beddard, 1893: 683.

Type species. *Dichogaster damonis* Beddard, 1888.

Distribution. Tropical Africa and Mid- and South America. Species of *bolau* group widely transported to various parts of the world.

***Dichogaster affinis* (Michaelsen, 1890)**

Benhamia affinis Michaelsen, 1890b: 9.

Dichogaster sinuosus Stephenson, 1931b: 74.

Dichogaster sinensis Chen, 1938: 421.

Dichogaster (Diplotheocodrilus) affinis (Michaelsen): Csuzdi 1996: 357.

Further synonyms in Csuzdi (2010).

Type locality. Quilimane (Quelimane), Mozambique; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 303; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: West, East and Southwest Africa; Canary Islands (Spain), Cape Verde Islands, Comoro Island, Kenya, Madagascar, Nigeria, South Africa, Zanzibar (Tanzania); Americas: North, Central and South America; Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, French Guiana, Galapagos (Ecuador), Guadeloupe (France), Hispaniola (Haiti), Mexico, Martinique Island (France), Nicaragua, St. Thomas Island, USA; Asia: Sumatra (Indonesia), Thailand, Vietnam; Oceania: various Pacific islands, Australia, Fiji, New Caledonia (France), Samoa; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Dichogaster annae* (Horst, 1893)**

Benhamia annae Horst, 1893: 32.

Benhamia travancorensis Fedarb, 1898a: 433.

Dichogaster annae (Horst): Michaelsen 1900a: 347.

Dichogaster curgensis Michaelsen, 1922: 54.

Dichogaster (Diplotheocodrilus) annae (Horst): Csuzdi 1995: 112.

Further synonyms in Csuzdi (2010).

Type locality. Java, Indonesia; **Type depository.** RNHL 1798; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: West and East Africa; Cameroon, Ghana, Grande Terre Island (France), Kenya, São Tomé, Seychelles, South Africa, Uganda; Americas: South and Central America, Guadeloupe (France); Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Ecuador, Guatemala, Martinique Island (France), Mexico, Nicaragua, Venezuela; Asia: Java (Indonesia), Batanta Island (Indonesia); Oceania: Australia, New Caledonia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Dichogaster bolau* (Michaelsen, 1891)**

Benhamia bolavi (corr. *bolau*) Michaelsen, 1891a: 9.

Dichogaster malayana Horst, 1893: 35.

Dichogaster bolau *malabaricus* Stephenson, 1920: 257.

Dichogaster bolau var. *malabarica* Stephenson: Stephenson 1923: 473.

Dichogaster (Diplotheocodrilus) bolau (Michaelsen): Csuzdi 1995: 102.

Dichogaster vellanikkarae Jaya, Aja & Nair, 2011: 72.

syn. nov.

Further synonyms in Csuzdi (2010) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Bergedorf, Germany; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 285, BMNH 1924:3:1:244, MNHU 7334 (= ZMB Verm. 7334, dried fragments of 2 syntypes) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), MZUT 52, NHRS 1247, RNHL, USNM 34166; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** East African origin (Csuzdi *et al.* 2008); Pan-tropical; Africa: Angola, Cameroon, Cape Verde Island, Comoros Island, Congo, Gabon, Kenya, Madagascar, Mozambique, Nigeria, São Tomé, Seychelles, South Africa, Togo, Uganda, Zimbabwe; Americas: Argentina, Belize, Bolivia, Bonaco - a little island in the Bay of Honduras, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Curacao (Netherlands), Dominican Republic, El Salvador, French Guiana, Galapagos (Ecuador), Guadeloupe Island (France), Guyana, Haiti, Honduras, Jamaica, Martinique Island (France), Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, St. Thomas, St. Vincent, Trinidad, USA, Venezuela; Asia: China, Christmas Island (Australia), Indonesia, Israel, Japan, Korea, Malay Peninsula,

Oman, Philippines, Vietnam; Europe: Europe including Scandinavia; England, Finland, Hungary, Ireland, Germany; Oceania: Australia, Caroline Islands, Easter Islands (Chile), Hawaii Islands (USA), Mariana Islands, New Caledonia (France), New Ireland (Papua New Guinea), Palau, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tonga, Vanuatu; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. *Dichogaster vellanikkarae* Jaya, Aja & Nair, 2011, is a species described by Jaya et al. (2011) from Vellanikkara in the Thrissur District of Kerala state, India. The family Benhamiidae itself is an exotic family to South Asia-Myanmar region, it is naturally distributed in Tropical Africa and Central and South America (Csuzdi 1996) and the species of the *bolau* group is widely transported to various parts of the world (Julka 1988a). Narayanan et al. (2023a) already stated that *D. vellanikkarae* can be a synonym of *D. bolau*. We critically reviewed the original description and reinvestigated the type material and it revealed that the types are undissected and *D. vellanikkarae* is actually a junior synonym of *D. bolau*. The taxonomic description of *D. vellanikkarae* was based on three type specimens (Jaya et al. 2011). Our examination of the holotype and paratypes showed that it was not dissected, and anatomical characteristics of the species were presumably based on some other materials, but details of such materials are not provided in the original description and concluded that *Dichogaster vellanikkarae* Jaya, Aja & Nair, 2011, is a junior synonym of the African peregrine species *D. bolau* (Michaelsen, 1891).

***Dichogaster modiglianii* (Rosa, 1896)**

Benhamia modiglianii Rosa, 1896: 510.
Dichogaster doveri Stephenson, 1931a: 276
Dichogaster modiglianii (Rosa): Stephenson 1931b: 65.
 For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012).

Type locality. Padang, Indonesia; **Type depository.** MGDG 44050; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Pan-tropical, original home in Africa (Gates 1972);

Africa: Angola, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ghana, Kenya, Madagascar, São Tomé, South Africa, Sudan; Americas: Brazil, Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador? French Guiana, Mexico, Peru, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Christmas Island (Australia), Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Vietnam; Oceania: Hawaii Islands (USA), New Caledonia (France), New Britain (Papua New Guinea), New Zealand? Samoa? Vanuatu; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Dichogaster saliens* (Beddard, 1893)**

Microdrilus saliens Beddard, 1893: 683.
Dichogaster crawi Eisen, 1900: 228.
Dichogaster saliens (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 343.
 Further synonyms in Csuzdi (2010).

Type locality. Type locality not designated, but specimens were found by Mr Thistleton Dyer at Kew Gardens in soil from Singapore, Java and Penang (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:536–40; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Angola, Congo, Gabon, Kingdom of Eswatini (Swaziland), Madagascar, South Africa, Uganda; Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Cuba, El Salvador, Galapagos (Ecuador), Martinique Island (France), Mexico, Panama, Peru, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Christmas Island (Australia), Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan, Vietnam; Europe: Sweden; Oceania: Australia, New Caledonia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Family EUDRILIDAE Claus, 1880

Genus *Eudrilus* Perrier, 1871

Eudrilus Perrier, 1871: 1175.

Type species. *Eudrilus decipiens* Perrier, 1871 (= *E. eugeniae*).

Distribution. Mainly confined to tropical West Africa (Upper Guinea, Sierra Leone, Liberia, Ivory Coast, Togo, Nigeria, Cameroon), but the type species is cosmopolitan in tropics by introduction.

***Eudrilus eugeniae* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Lumbricus eugeniae Kinberg, 1867: 98.
Eudrilus decipiens Perrier, 1871: 1176.
Eudrilus eugeniae (Kinberg): Beddard 1895a: 604.
For further synonyms see Gates (1972), Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. St. Helena Island, South Atlantic; **Type depository.** NHRS 1237, BMNH 1904.10.5.550; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar? Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Cosmopolitan, West African origin, transported as a compost worm and peregrine in many countries; Africa: Cape Verde, Cameroon, Comoros Islands, Fernando Po Island (Equatorial Guinea), Gabon, Grande Terre Island (France), Great Comoros, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Mayotte Island, Sao Tome Island, Madagascar, Nigeria, São Tomé, St Helena (Britain), Sierra Leone, South Africa, Togo, Upper Guinea; Americas: Antilles, Bahamas, Belize, Bermuda, Brazil, Colombia, Cuba, French Guiana, Guadeloupe (France), Guyana, Hispaniola (Dominical Republic, Haiti), Martinique, Mexico, Panama, Paraguay, Puerto Rico, St Pierre and Miquelon (France), St Thomas, Surinam, Trinidad, USA, Virgin Islands, Venezuela; Asia: Philippines, Vietnam; Europe: rarely from greenhouses - Denmark, Hungary; Oceania: Australia, New Caledonia (France), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Family LUMBRICIDAE Rafinesque, 1815
sensu van Haaren et al. (2021)

Genus *Allolobophora* Eisen, 1874

Allolobophora Eisen, 1874: 46.

Type species. *Enterion chloroticum* Savigny, 1826, designated by Omodeo in 1956.

Distribution. Europe and Asia-minor (Blakemore 2012a).

***Allolobophora chlorotica* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion chloroticum Savigny, 1826: 182/3.
Octolasion hortensis Bretschler, 1901: 221.
Allolobophora chlorotica (Savigny): Tétray 1937: 145.
For further synonyms see Csuzdi & Zicsi (2003) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar?; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Algeria; Canaries (Spain), Madeira (Portugal), St Helena (Britain), Tristão da Cunha Islands; Americas: Bermuda, Bolivia, Canada, Chile, Guatemala, Mexico, Peru, Uruguay, USA; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand; Asia: Iran, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey; Europe: Whole Europe, Albania, Georgia, Greenland, Iceland, Isle of Man, Malta, Scandinavia and Russia, Romania; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details. A native of the Palaearctics (Reynolds 2022).

Genus *Aporrectodea* Örley, 1885

Aporrectodea Örley, 1885: 22.

Type species. *Lumbricus trapezoides* Dugès, 1828 designated by Gates (1975) by elimination (ICZN Art. 69A.3.)

Distribution. Europe and Asia-minor with several cosmopolitan species by transportation (Blakemore 2012a).

***Aporrectodea caliginosa* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion caliginosum Savigny, 1826: 180.
Enterion carneum Savigny, 1826: 180.
Helodrilus (Allolobophora) caliginosus (part) (Savigny): Michaelsen 1900a: 482.
Nicodrilus (Nicodrilus) caliginosus alternisetosus Bouché, 1972: 333.
Aporrectodea caliginosa caliginosa (part?) (Savigny): Easton 1983: 476.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris region, France; **Type depository.** MHNG 3/77; types are missing (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2023); **Distribution.** Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar? Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Algeria, Egypt to Morocco, South Africa, Canaries Islands (Spain), Madeira Islands (Portugal); Reunion Island, South Africa, St Helena Islands (Britain); Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Equador, Falkland Islands, Mexico, Paraguay, Uruguay, USA, Venuzuela; Asia: China, Iran, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Korea, Palestine, Qatar, Syria, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Sweden, Western Europe (England, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands etc.); Oceania: Australia, Hawaii (USA), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. *A. caliginosa* and *A. trapezoides* are hard to differentiate on morphology and DNA barcoding is needed to finalize this issue (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2023). Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Aporrectodea jassyensis* (Michaelsen, 1891)**

Allolobophora jassyensis Michaelsen, 1891a: 15.
Allolobophora jassyensis var. nov. *orientalis* Michaelsen, 1897: 69.
Aporrectodea jassyensis jassyensis Michaelsen: Easton 1983: 477.

Type locality. Jassy, Romania; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 142, ZMUH Ol 13101 (Paralectotype) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Afghanistan; **Elsewhere.** Native of the Palaearctics and widely distributed in southern Eurasia and northern Africa (Csuzdi & Zisci 2003), Africa: Egypt; Asia: Central Asia, Cyprus, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine, South Russia, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, East Mediterranean, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Moldavia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, the Balkans, Switzerland; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Aporrectodea longa* (Ude, 1885)**

Allolobophora terrestris (Savigny, 1826) f. *longa* Ude, 1885: 136.
Helodrilus (Allolobophora) longus: Michaelsen 1900a: 483.
Allolobophora longa: Gerard, 1964: 28.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Göttingen, Germany; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Myanmar? Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Palaearctic from Scandinavia, Iceland, and throughout the British Isles to northern Italy to Siberia (Russia), Africa: Algeria, South Africa; Americas: North and Central America, Canada, Mexico, USA; Asia: Siberia (Russia); Europe: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, England, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Jersey, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherland, Norway, Poland, Russia, Scotland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Wales; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand (Gates 1972; Blakemore 2012a); **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Aporrectodea rosea rosea* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion roseum Savigny, 1826: 182.
Eisenia rosea prashadi Stephenson, 1922a: 440.
Aporrectodea rosea rosea (Savigny): Easton 1983: 477.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Afghanistan, Myanmar? India, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Native of the Palaearctic region (most probably western Palaearctic is its original home, Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2023) but introduced in many regions; Africa: Northern and Southern Africa, Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Morocco, South Africa, Tristão da Cunha Islands; Americas: Central and South America (e.g. Argentina, Bermuda, Bolivia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Equador, Mexico, Peru, Uruguay, USA); Asia: Middle East, Iraq, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: cosmopolitan in Europe, the Mediterranean region; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii, New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Aporrectodea trapezoides* (Dugès, 1828)**

Lumbricus trapezoides Dugès, 1828: 289.

Lumbricus capensis Kinberg, 1867: 100.

Allolobophora trapezoides (Dugès): Gates 1972: 76.

Aporrectodea caliginosa trapezoides (Dugès): Easton 1983: 477.

For further synonyms see Marchán *et al.* (2025).

Type locality. Jardin des Plantes (Botanical Garden) Montpellier, France (Marchán *et al.* 2025); **Type depository.** MNHN (Neotype) (Marchán *et al.* 2025); **Distribution.** Afghanistan, India, Myanmar? Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Indigenous to the Palearctic region but introduced to many parts of the world; Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Egypt, South Africa, St Helena Islands (Britain); Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Costa Rica, French Guiana, Guyana, Mexico, North America, Peru, Uruguay, USA; Asia: China, Iran, Iraq, Japan, South Korea, Lebanon, Taiwan, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Bulgaria, Croatia, England, Greece, Italy, Malta, Mediterranean Europe, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii Islands (USA), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. *A. caliginosa* and *A. trapezoides* are hard to differentiate on morphology; refer to *A. caliginosa*. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Bimastos* Moore, 1893

Bimastos Moore, 1893: 333.

Bimastos Moore: Michaelsen 1900a: 501 (invalid emendation of *Bimastos*).

Type species. *Bimastos palustris* Moore, 1895 (= *Bimastos* sp. Moore, 1893).

Distribution. Indigenous to North America; southeast USA east of the Allegheny Range but

several peregrine species show world-wide distribution.

***Bimastos eiseni* (Levinsen, 1884)**

Lumbricus eiseni Levinsen, 1884: 241.

Allolobophora (Bimastos) eiseni (Levinsen): Friend 1892: 302.

Allolobophoridella eiseni (Levinsen): Mr íc 1990: 255
For further synonyms see Csuzdi *et al.* (2017).

Type locality. Deer garden (Jægersborg Dyrehave) near Copenhagen, Denmark; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar?; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira Islands (Portugal); South Africa, St Helena Islands (Britain); Americas: USA; Europe: widespread in western Europe from Denmark to Balkans (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, etc.), Italy, Portugal and Poland, British Isles, Romania; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii islands (USA), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Bimastos parvus* (Eisen, 1874)**

Allolobophora parva Eisen, 1874: 46.

For further synonyms see Csuzdi *et al.* (2017).

Type locality. Mt Lebanon (New Lebanon), New York, USA; **Type depository.** USNM (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** Afghanistan, India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Native of North America; Africa: Algeria, Mauritius, St Helena (Britain), St Paul Island (France), South-west Africa, South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Canada, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Mexico, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Central Asia, China, Israel, Japan, Java (Indonesia), Kazakhstan, Korea, Malaysia, Siberia (Russia), Taiwan, Tibet, Uzbekistan, Vietnam; Europe: British Isles, Croatia, France, Iceland, Ireland, Russia; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii islands (USA), Tahiti (France); **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Bimastos rubidus* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion rubidum Savigny, 1826: 182.

Allolobophora norvegica Eisen, 1874: 48.

Dendrodrilus rubidus rubidus (Savigny): Easton 1983: 479.

Bimastos rubidus (Savigny): Csuzdi et al. 2017: 20.

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** MNHN, but Tetry (1937) did not find the types and probably lost (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2023); **Distribution.** Bhutan, India, Myanmar? Nepal, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Cosmopolitan species-complex, probably indigenous to Holarctic; Africa: Northern and Southern regions, Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal), Madagascar, Reunion Island (France), South Africa, Tristão da Cunha Islands; Americas: North, Central and South Americas (Argentina, Bermuda, Bolivia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Falkland Islands, French Guiana, Guatemala, Mexico, Peru, Uruguay, USA, Venezuela; Asia: China, Japan, Korea, Siberia (Russia), Turkey; Europe: throughout Europe, Albania, Andora, Austria, Azores (Portugal), Belgium, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Britain, Bulgaria, Caucasus, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, England, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Jersey, Jugoslavian countries, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Scotland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, Wales; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii islands (USA), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Dendrobaena* Eisen, 1873

Dendrobaena Eisen, 1873: 53.

Type species. *Dendrobaena boeckii* Eisen, 1873 (= *Enterion octaedrum* Savigny, 1826).

Distribution. Palearctic to Middle East and Levant, a few of the species are cosmopolitan by transportation.

***Dendrobaena byblica* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora (Dendrobaena) byblica Rosa, 1893: 4.

Helodrilus (Dendrobaena) byblicus: Michaelsen 1900a: 492.

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Ain el Sultan (near Jericho), Palestine; **Type depository.** MZUT 463; **Distribution.** Afghanistan; **Elsewhere.** One of most widely distributed species in the circum-Mediterranean and Middle-east and Asia-minor regions (Blakemore 2012a). Africa: Algeria, Morocco, Tenerife in Canary Islands (Spain); Asia: Cyprus, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Macedonia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Dendrobaena fedtschenkoi* (Michaelsen, 1900)**

Allolobophora fedtschenkoi Michaelsen, 1900b: 7.

For further synonyms see Szederjesi et al. (2018b).

Type locality. Upper flow of Zeravshan River, Pamir Mts, Tajikistan (Szederjesi et al. 2018b); **Type depository.** HNHM/12665 (Szederjesi et al. 2018b); **Distiburction.** Afghanistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: Iran, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan; **Status.** Native peregrine?

***Dendrobaena hortensis* (Michaelsen, 1890)**

Allolobophora subrubicunda var. *hortensis* Michaelsen, 1890a: 15.

Eisenia veneta var. *hortensis* (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 477.

Eisenia veneta hibernica Michaelsen, 1900a: 477.

Dendrobaena hortensis (Michaelsen): Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003: 119.

Further synonyms in Christoffersen (2011).

Type locality. Hamburg (and Berlin), Germany (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** ZMUH V 50 (3 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026) and Turin, 618 (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal), South Africa; Americas: North and South American countries (e.g. Argentina, Chile), Canada, USA; Asia: Iran, Turkey; Europe:

Albania, Azores Island (Portugal), Bulgaria, England, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Macedonia, North Macedonia, Portugal, Russian steppes and Caucasus, Serbia, Slovakia; Oceania: Australia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Dendrobaena octaedra* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion octaedrum Savigny, 1826: 183.
Lumbricus flaviventris Leuckart, 1849: 159.
Dendrobaena camerani Rosa, 1882: 172.
Dendrobaena octaedra (Savigny): Tètry 1937: 144.
Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** MNHN (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** Afghanistan? India, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Madeira (Portugal), South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, USA; Asia: Japan, Uzbekistan; Europe: Austria, British Isles, Bulgaria, Czechia, Croatia, Denmark, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Ireland, Macedonia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Scandinavia, Spain, Switzerland; Oceania: Hawaii; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Eisenia* Malm, 1877

Eisenia Malm, 1877: 45.

Type species. *Enterion fetidum* Savigny, 1826.

Distribution. Palaearctic. A few species are widely distributed (Blakemore 2012a).

***Eisenia andrei* Bouche, 1972**

Eisenia foetida var. *unicolor* André, 1963: 24.

Eisenia fetida andrei Bouché, 1972: 381.
Eisenia andrei Bouché: Christoffersen 2011: 155.

Type locality. ?; **Type depository.** OECO 79-1388-4321 (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Libya; Americas: South America, Brazil, Chile, USA; Asia: Korea, Mongolia; Europe: Croatia, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Norway; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. *E. andrei* and *E. fetida* looks very similar and are hard to distinguish. DNA barcoding is the only way to correctly distinguish these two species (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2023).

***Eisenia fetida* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion fetidum Savigny, 1826: 182.
Lumbricus semifasciatus Burmeister, 1835: 33.
Helodrilus (Eisenia) foetidus (Savigny): Michaelsen 1913b: 551.
Allolobophora (Eisenia) fetida (Savigny): Stephenson 1923: 499.
Eisenia fetida (Savigny): Römbke *et al.* 2016: 7.
Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Myanmar? Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Originally of Eurasian origin now cosmopolitan; Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal), Morocco, South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Bermuda, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Mexico, Nicaragua, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Cambodia, China, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Lebanon, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Siberia (Russia), Uzbekistan, Vietnam; Europe: Albania, Austria, Azores (Portugal), Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, England, Finland, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Jersey, Yugoslavian countries, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Scotland, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Transcaucasia, Ukraine, Wales; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii Islands (USA), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. *E. andrei* and *E. fetida* looks very similar and are hard to distinguish. DNA barcoding is the only way to correctly distinguish these two species (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2023). Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Eiseniella* Michaelsen, 1900

Eiseniella Michaelsen, 1900a: 471.

Type species. *Enterion tetraedrum* Savigny, 1826.

Distribution. Palaearctic, all native *Eiseniella* species are from the Balkan region (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2023). With one cosmopolitan species (Blakemore 2012a).

Eiseniella tetraedra (Savigny, 1826)

Enterion tetraedrum Savigny, 1826: 184.

Lumbricus amphisbaena Dugès, 1828: 293.

Lumbricus agilis Hoffmeister, 1843: 191.

Tetragonurus pupa Eisen, 1874: 47.

Eiseniella tetraedra (Savigny): Easton 1983: 481.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Afghanistan, Myanmar? India; **Elsewhere.** Western Palaearctic, Scandinavia to Pri-urals; Adriatic and Mediterranean also the Levant many locations; Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Cape Verde, Libya, Morocco, St Helena Island (Britain), South Africa, Tristão da Cunha Islands; Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Canada, Colombia, Chile, Ecuador, Falkland Islands, Juan Fernandez Islands (Chile), Mexico, Peru, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Iran, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Lebanon, Syria, Taiwan, Tajikistan, Turkestan, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Albania, Austria, Azores (Portugal), Belgium, Bulgaria, Channel Islands, Croatia, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, England, Estonia, Faroe Island (Denmark), Finland, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Guernsey, Hungary, Iceland, Isle of Man, Jersey, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Poland,

Portugal, Russia, Romania, Serbia, Scotland, Sweden, Ukraine, Wales, Yougoslavia; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand. **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list, without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Lumbricus* Linnaeus, 1758

Lumbricus (part) Linnaeus, 1758: 647.

Type species. *Lumbricus terrestris* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation (Stiles & Hassall 1905).

Distribution. Palaearctic, with cosmopolitan species (Blakemore 2012a).

Lumbricus castaneus (Savigny, 1826)

Enterion castaneum Savigny, 1826: 180.

Lumbricus josephinae Kinberg, 1867: 98.

Lumbricus castaneus (Savigny): Michaelsen 1900a: 510.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing from MNHN (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** Bangladesh, Myanmar? India; **Elsewhere.** Palaearctic, from Siberia (Boganida River?) to Scandinavia, Faeroes, Iceland and North America, spreading throughout Nearctic; Africa: St Helena Island (Britain), South Africa; Americas: Bermudas, Canada, Mexico, USA; Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovia, British Isles, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Isle of Man, Isle of May and Channel Isles, Italy, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list, without any specific collection locations or details.

Lumbricus rubellus Hoffmeister, 1843

Lumbricus rubellus Hoffmeister, 1843: 187.

Enterion rubellum var. *parvum* + var. *magnum* Örley, 1881: 588, 589.

Lumbricus rubellus var. *curticaudatus* Friend, 1892: 312.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Unknown (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** Unknown (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Myanmar? Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** A native of the Palearctic, now wide spread in Europe and Russia (Reynolds 2022); Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal), Tristão da Cunha Islands, South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Canada, Colombia, Chile, Falkland Islands, Mexico, Uruguay, USA; Asia: Black Sea region, Iran, Kazakhstan, Siberia (Russia), Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Channel Islands, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, England, Estonia, Faroe Island, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Isle of Man, Italy, Jersey, Yugoslavian countries (Bosnia and Herzegovina), Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Scotland, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, Wales; Oceania: Australia, Chatham Island (New Zealand), Kermadec Islands (New Zealand), New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. First record of this species in South Asia was by Rosa (1891) from the Nicobar Island of India. This specimen is still in the Natural History Museum Vienna (NHMV Inv. No. **V5154**) (Szedejesi 2025). Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list, without any specific collection locations or details.

***Lumbricus terrestris* Linnaeus, 1758**

Lumbricus terrestris (part) Linnaeus, 1758: 647.

Lumbricus americanus Perrier, 1872: 44.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Uppasala, Sweden (Blakemore 2013b, 2014); **Type depository.** Neotype BMNH 1973:1:1 (Sims 1973; Blakemore 2013b, 2014), Neotype, apparently misplaced; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar? Pakistan; **Else-**

ewhere. Holarctic; Africa: Algeria, Egypt, Madeira (Portugal), Sudan, Tristão da Cunha Islands (Britain), South Africa; Americas: Central and South America; Argentina, Canada, Chile, Falkland Islands, Mexico, Uruguay, USA; Asia: Japan, Siberia (Russia); Europe: Albania, Austria, Azores (Portugal), Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, England, Faroe Island, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Isle of Man, Italy, Jersey, Latvia, Lithuania, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, North Macedonia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Scotland, Serbia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkiye, Ukraine, Wales; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. There is some confusion over the designation of the type specimen of this species. Since its original type is non-existent, Sims (1973) assigned a neotype (BMNH 1973:1:1), but later James *et al.* (2010) assumed that this neotype was lost and designated another 'neo-neotype'. However, Blakemore (2013b, 2014) rediscovered the supposed missing neotype designated by Sims (1973) on a shelf of the BMNH and confirmed its identity as designated by Sims. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Octolasion* Örley, 1885

Octolasion Örley, 1885: 10, 13.

Type species. *Lumbricus terrestris* var. *lacteus* Örley, 1881 (= *O. lacteum*) by ICZN Opinion 1403 (Szedejesi & Csuzdi 2025)

Distribution. Palearctic, European by origin two or three species are cosmopolitan by adventitious transportation (Blakemore 2012a).

***Octolasion cyaneum* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion cyaneum (part) Savigny, 1826: 181.

Lumbricus cyaneus (Savigny): Dugés, 1837: 17.

Helodrilus (Dendrobaena) kempfi Stephenson, 1922a: 441.

Octolasion cyaneum (Savigny): Michaelsen 1900a: 506.
Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Paris, France (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar? Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Of European origin, now widespread in Africa: Madeira (Portugal), South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Ecuador, Mexico, Tierra del Fuego (Argentina), Uruguay, USA; Asia: Siberia (Russia), Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Azores (Portugal), Belgium, Channel Islands, Croatia, Czech and Slovak Republics, Denmark, England, Faroe, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Scotland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Wales; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Octolasion lacteum* (Örley, 1881)**

Lumbricus terrestris var. *lacteus* Örley, 1881: 584.

Allolobophora profuga Rosa, 1884: 47.

Octolasion lacteum (Örley): Michaelsen 1900a: 506 (part).

Eophila himalayana Cernovitov, 1937: 109.

Further synonyms in Csuzdi & Zicsi (2003) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Hungary (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** Type was destroyed in a fire out break (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2026) **Distribution.** India, Myanmar? Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal), South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Bolivia, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Panama, Peru, Uruguay, USA, Venezuela; Asia: China, Iran, Myanmar, Siberia (Russia), Turkestan, Turkiye, Uzbekistan; Europe: Widely distributed from Pyrenees, eastern France through to Central Europe, Albania, Austria, Azores (Portugal), Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Channel Islands, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Molda-

via, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Scotland, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Yugoslavia; Oceania: Australia, New Zealand; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. Based on the recent suggestions put forwarded by Szederjesi & Csuzdi (2025), here we consider all the records of *O. tyrtaeum* from the South Asia as *O. lacteum*. For more details, see Narayanan et al. (2023a) and Szederjesi & Csuzdi (2025). Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list, without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Perelia* Easton, 1983

Allolobophora (*Svetlovia*) Perel, 1976: 833.

Perelia Easton, 1983: 484.

Alpodinaridella (*Alpodinaridella*) Mr íc, 1987: 63.

Alpodinaridella (*Dinaridella*) Mr íc, 1987: 63.

For further details, see Csuzdi & Pavlíček (2005a).

Type species. *Eophila arnoldiana* Perel, 1971, by original designation (Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a).

Distribution. Mainly Central Asia, also Western Asia and nearby European portions. Asia: Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Israel, Iran, Palestine, Russia, Turkiye; Europe: Croatia, Greece, Montenegro, North Macedonia.

***Perelia kaznakovi* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Helodrilus (*Eophila*) *kaznakovi* Michaelsen, 1910b: 65.

Eophila asiatica Malevic, 1949: 398.

Allolobophora (*Svetlovia*) *kaznakovi* (Michaelsen): Perel 1976: 833.

Perelia kaznakovi: Easton 1983: 484.

Type locality. Silva Pisamé a and Nurana in Schemacha (= Shamakhi/ Şamaxı) District near Baku, Azerbaijan (Michaelsen 1910b); **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India (in Pakistan Occupied Kashmir region); **Elsewhere.** Asia: Azerbaijan, Iran, Kyrgystan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan; **Status.** Unknown, introduced

to the present location, a native of central Asia, it is likely to occur naturally in Afghanistan and Balochistan region.

Family MEGASCOLECIDAE Rosa, 1891

Genus *Aiyeriella* Narayanan & Julka, 2025

Aiyeriella Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2025c: 521.

Type species. *Aiyeriella quadritheca* Narayanan & Julka, 2025.

Distribution. India (western slopes of the southern Western Ghats in Kerala State).

***Aiyeriella longiprostata* Narayanan & Julka, 2025**

Aiyeriella longiprostata Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2025c: 526.

Type locality. Below Muttidichantheri in Pappara Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala State, India (Narayanan et al. 2025c); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.10330 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.10331 (Paratypes) (Narayanan et al. 2025c); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Aiyeriella quadritheca* Narayanan & Julka, 2025**

Aiyeriella quadritheca Narayanan & Julka in Narayanan et al., 2025c: 523.

Type locality. Kottavasal, Kerala State, India (Narayanan et al. 2025c); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.10328 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.10329 (Paratypes) (Narayanan et al. 2025c); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Amyntas* Kinberg, 1867

Amyntas Kinberg, 1867: 97.

Amyntas Kinberg 1867: 101.

Nitocris Kinberg, 1867: 102.

Pheretima (part) Kinberg, 1867: 102.

Perichaeta Schmarda (part): Beddard 1895a: 388.

Pheretima Kinberg (part): Michaelsen 1900b: 234.

Pheretima (*Pheretima*) Kinberg (part): Michaelsen 1928: 8.

Pheretima (*Metapheretima*) (part) Michaelsen, 1928: 8.

Amyntas Kinberg: Sims & Easton 1972: 211.

Pheretima (*Terrata*) (part) Thai, 1983: 123.

Type species. *Amyntas aeruginosus* Kinberg, 18.

Distribution. Widely distributed in the Oriental, Australasian and Oceania regions, with disproportionately high numbers of peregrine species.

***Amyntas aculeatus* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima aculeata Gates, 1936: 390.

Amyntas aculeatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Port Blair, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Union Territory, India; **Type depository.** ZSIK; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Amyntas alexandri* Beddard, 1901**

Amyntas alexandri Beddard, 1901b: 999.

Pheretima lignicola Stephenson, 1914b: 399.

Pheretima alexandri (Beddard): Stephenson 1923: 291.

Pheretima suctoria mullani Stephenson, 1924b: 340.

Amyntas alexandri var. *gracilior* Gates, 1931: 371.

Amyntas alexandri alexandri (Beddard): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Calcutta (Kolkata), India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:757; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: Thailand; Europe: England; **Status.** Exotic peregrine to South Asian region, naturally found in Myanmar?

Remarks. Gates (1931: 371) described a subspecies *A. alexandri gracilior* from Myanmar, but it differs from the nominate by having >14 setae

between spermathecal and male pores. As per Blakemore (2006a) this taxon apparently overlooked or omitted by Gates (1972), possibly because it is synonymous with the nominate subspecies. Here it is treated as a synonym of *A. alexandri*.

***Amyntas analectus analectus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima analecta Gates, 1932: 501.

Pheretima analecta analecta Gates, 1932: 501; 1972: 161.

Amyntas analectus analectus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Ko Haw Der, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3120, but as per Gates (1972) no types; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas analectus promotus* (Gates, 1933)**

Pheretima analecta var. *promota* Gates, 1933: 494.

Pheretima promotus Gates: Gates 1936: 451.

Pheretima pannosa Gates, 1936: 441.

Pheretima analecta promotus Gates: Gates 1960: 250; 1972: 160.

Amyntas analectus promotus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Pegu (Bago) Yomas, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas analectus rufulus* (Gates, 1933)**

Pheretima rufula Gates, 1933: 543.

Pheretima analecta rufula Gates: Gates 1960: 250; 1972: 160.

Amyntas rufulus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Type locality. Pegu Yomas in vicinity of Su Law and Pray Law (Gates 1972), Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3113, but as per Gates (1972) no types; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas andersoni* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Pheretima andersoni Michaelsen, 1907: 167.

Pheretima nemoralis Gates, 1932: 531.

Pheretima velata var. *alveata* Gates, 1932: 539.

Pheretima andersoni Michaelsen: Gates 1972: 159.

Amyntas andersoni (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 240.

Type locality. Amherst (Kyaikkhami), Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 534, ZMUH 7167; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Laos (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas aspergillum* (Perrier, 1872)**

Perichaeta aspergillum Perrier, 1872: 118.

Perichaeta takatorii Goto & Hatai, 1898: 76.

Pheretima aspergillum (Perrier): Michaelsen 1900a: 253

Amyntas aspergillum (Perrier): Blakemore 2007b: 9.

Amyntas aspergillum (Perrier): Narayanan et al. 2024a: 98.

For further synonyms see Chang et al. (2009), Blakemore (2012a) and Nguyen et al. (2016).

Type locality. Amoy and Kowloon, China (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** MNHN 575; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Taiwan, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas balteolatus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima balteolata Gates, 1932: 425.

Pheretima andersoni Gates: Gates 1972: 170.

Amyntas balteolatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 241.

Type locality. Pang Wo, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas bellatulus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima bellatula Gates, 1932: 427.

Pheretima bellatula Gates: Gates 1972: 170.

Amyntas bellatulus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 241.

Type locality. Teung Cong, Yunnan Province, China; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Chi-

na, Vietnam (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas bournei* (Rosa, 1890)**

Perichaeta bournei Rosa, 1890b: 110.
Pheretima bournei Rosa: Michaelsen, 1900a: 257.
Amyntas bournei Rosa: Sims & Easton, 1972: 234.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Cobapo, Myanmar; **Type depository.** MGDG 44040. **Distribution.** Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Vietnam; **Status.** Native peregrine?

Remark. Sometimes considered as a synonym of *A. gracilis*, for more details see Nguyen et al. (2016: 18).

***Amyntas canaliculatus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima canaliculata Gates, 1932: 408.
Amyntas canaliculatus Gates: Sims & Easton 1972: 234

Type locality. Blachi, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3088. **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic, probably introduced to India.

***Amyntas carinensis* (Rosa, 1890)**

Perichaeta carinensis Rosa, 1890b: 107.
Amyntas carinensis (Rosa): Beddard 1900a: 625.
Pheretima carinensis (Rosa): Michaelsen 1903a: 95.
Pheretima pinguis Gates, 1930: 319.
Amyntas carinensis (Rosa): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. Meteleo, Myanmar; **Type depository.** MGDG 44014, MZUT 150, MNHU 2275 (= ZMB Verm. 2275; 1 Syntype) (Hartwich & Kiliass 1989); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Status.** Endemic, probably introduced to India and Pakistan.

***Amyntas choprai* (Stephenson, 1929)**

Pheretima andersoni choprai Stephenson, 1929: 233.
Pheretima choprai Stephenson: Gates 1932: 532.
Amyntas choprai Stephenson: Blakemore 2007b: 22.

Amyntas andersoni choprai Stephenson: Sims & Easton 1972: 241; Tiwari et al. 2024: 5.

Type locality. Nyaungbin a village at the north end of the Indawgyi Lake, Myanmar (Stephenson 1929); **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic, probably introduced to India.

***Amyntas comptus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima compta Gates, 1932: 511.
Pheretima compta Gates: Gates 1972: 162.
Amyntas comptus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 241.

Type locality. Blachi, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Thailand; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas corticis* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Perichaeta corticis Kinberg, 1867: 102.
?Perichaeta mirabilis Bourne, 1886: 668
Amyntas diffringens Baird: Easton 1979: 119.
Amyntas corticis (Kinberg): Easton 1982a: 726.
For full list of synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Oahu, Hawaii Island; **Type depository.** NHRS 1947, possibly immature (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** According to Blakemore (2012), this species is the most widely distributed of the allochthonous species of the pheretimoid group, having been recorded from temperate and tropical regions throughout the world; Africa: Anjouan (Comoros), Canary Islands (Spain), Cape Verde Islands, Egypt, Madagascar, Reunion Island (France), Sao Tome and Principe, South Africa, St Helena (Britain), Zimbabwe; Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guadeloupe Island (France), Guatemala, Hispaniola (Dominican Republic), Jamaica, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Peru, Trinidad, USA, Venezuela; Asia: China, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Iraq, Japan, Korea, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkiye, Vietnam; Europe: Azores

(Portugal); England, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Sardinia (Italy), Scotland, Sweden, Wales; Oceania: Australia, Fiji, Hawaii (USA), New Caledonia (France), New Zealand, Papua New Guinea; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Cosmopolitan species (Blakemore 2012a).

Amyntas defectus (Gates, 1930)

Pheretima defecta Gates, 1930: 176.

Pheretima jacita Gates, 1931: 391.

Pheretima defecta Gates: Gates 1972: 176.

Amyntas defectus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 241.

Type locality. Labaw, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Amyntas doliarius doliarius (Gates, 1931)

Pheretima doliaria Gates, 1931: 374.

Pheretima referta Gates, 1931: 405.

Pheretima doliaria var. *typica* Gates: Gates 1932: 415.

Pheretima doliaria Gates: Gates 1972: 180.

Amyntas doliarius doliarius (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Mong Ko, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China, Laos (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

Remarks. Gates (1932) had described four subspecies viz., *typica* (Gates 1932: 415), *armillata* (Gates 1932: 415), *dolosa* (Gates 1932: 416), *stercoraria* (Gates 1932: 417). But Gates (1972: 180) did not mention anything about these subspecies under *Pheretima doliaria*. Later, Sims & Easton (1972: 234) treated them as subspecies under *Amyntas doliarius*. Even though, Sims & Easton (1972: 234) provisionally kept *Pheretima doliaria dolosa* Gates, 1932: 416, as a synonym of *A. d. doliarius*, without providing any justifications. According to Blakemore's (2006a: 7), this is possibly to avoid the problem of homonymy, since Gates (1932: 443) described another one

species with the name *Pheretima dolosa* in the same work. Hence, recently Blakemore (2007b) suggested *Amyntas gegatesi* nom. nov. as a replacement name for *Pheretima dolosa* Gates (1932: 443). Herein we also keep all the four subspecies of *A. doliarius* as valid names.

Amyntas doliarius armillatus (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima doliaria var. *armillata* Gates, 1932: 415.

Amyntas doliarius armillatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Loi Kaw, Kaya State, Myanmar; **Type depository** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. See remark section of *A. d. doliarius*.

Amyntas doliarius dolosus (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima doliaria var. *dolosa* Gates, 1932: 416. [non *Pheretima dolosa* Gates, 1932: 443 = *Amyntas gegatesi* Blakemore, 2007]

Amyntas doliarius dolosus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Without location details (Gates 1932), Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. See remark section of *A. d. doliarius*.

Amyntas doliarius stercorarius (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima doliaria var. *stercoraria* Gates, 1932: 417.

Amyntas doliarius stercorarius (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Amyntas doliarius stercoraria: Blakemore 2006a: 7 (lapsus).

Type locality. Nam Hpen Noi (Namphan or Na-hpan?), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. See remark section of *A. d. doliaris*.

***Amyntas exiguus exiguus* (Gates, 1930)**

Pheretima minuta Gates, 1929: 18. [non *Amyntas minutus* Beddard, 1900: 906]

Pheretima exigua (Part) Gates, 1930: 310 nom. nov. pro *Pheretima minuta* Gates, 1929 (non *Amyntas minutus* Beddard, 1900 = *Polypheretima polyteca*). Excluding Nyaungbinkin specimens.

Pheretima exigua var. *typica* Gates: Gates 1932: 512.

Pheretima exigua exigua Gates: Gates 1972: 184.

Amyntas exiguus exiguus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 242.

Type locality. Lashio, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Laos? Thailand, Vietnam (Blakemore 2007b, Nguyen et al. 2016); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas exiguus austrinus* (Gates, 1930)**

Pheretima exigua (Part) Gates, 1930: 310. Only Nyaungbinkin specimens.

Pheretima exigua var. *austrina* Gates: Gates 1932: 514.

Pheretima exigua austrina Gates: Gates 1972: 184.

Amyntas exiguus austrinus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Type locality. Leiktho Circle, Kayin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3601, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Thailand, Vietnam (Blakemore 2007b, Nguyen et al. 2016); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas facetus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima faceta Gates, 1932: 422.

Amyntas facetus (Gates): Sims & Easton, 1972: 235.

Type locality. John Lawrence Island, Andaman and Nicobar Islands union territory, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas feae* (Rosa, 1888)**

Perichaeta feae Rosa, 1888: 161.

Amyntas feae (Rosa): Beddard 1900: 266.

Pheretima Feae (Rosa): Michaelsen 1903a: 95.

Pheretima feae: Gates 1972: 185.

Amyntas defectus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 242.

Type locality. Kawkareik, Karen State, Myanmar; **Type depository** MGDG 44042, MNHU 2273; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Adjacent countries; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas fucosus* (Gates, 1933)**

Pheretima fucosa Gates, 1933: 526.

Pheretima fucosa: Gates 1972: 187.

Amyntas fucosus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 242.

Type locality. In region between Kyaukme-daung and Kameik (Gates 1972), Sagaing Division, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3091, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas glabrus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima glabra Gates, 1932: 395.

Pheretima tenellula Gates, 1932: 398.

Pheretima vieta Gates, 1936: 462.

Pheretima glabra: Gates 1972: 187.

Amyntas fucosus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 242.

Type locality. Nam Hpen Noi (Namphan or Na-hpan?), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China, Japan, Vietnam (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas gracilis* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Nitocris gracilis Kinberg, 1867: 102.

Perichaeta hawayana Rosa, 1891: 396.

Pheretima hawayana (Rosa): Stephenson 1913: 271.

Amyntas hawayanus (Rosa): Beddard 1900a: 645.

Amyntas gracilis (Kinberg): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; **Type depository.** NHRS 1944; but according to Nguyen *et al.* (2016) in RNHL; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** From tropical and warm temperate localities on most continents (Blakemore 2012a); Africa: Canary Islands (Spain), Egypt, Madeira (Portugal), Mauritius, South Africa, St Helena (Britain); Americas: Argentina, Barbados, Bermuda, Brazil, Chile, Cuba, Colombia, El Salvador, French Guiana, Guatemala, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Uruguay, USA, Venezuela; Asia: China, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Iraq, Japan, South Korea, Malaysia, Myanmar, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkiye, Vietnam; Europe: mainly to greenhouses, Denmark, England, France, Greece, Poland, Russia; Oceania: Australia, Fiji, Hawaii (USA), Kermadec (New Zealand), New Caledonia, New Guinea, New Zealand, Raoul Island (New Zealand), Samoa, Tahiti, Tonga **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas hupeiensis* (Michaelsen, 1895)**

Pherichaeta hupeiensis Michaelsen, 1895: 35.
Amyntas hupeiensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1899b: 6.
Pheretima hupeiensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 273.
Amyntas hupeiensis (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. Shi-hui-yao (Shihuiyao), China (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** unknown (Nguyen *et al.* 2016); **Distribution.** India, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Americas: Mexico, USA; Asia: China, Japan, Korea, Taiwan, Vietnam; Oceania: New Zealand, Torres Strait islands (Australia); **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas incongruus* (Chen, 1933)**

Pheretima incongrua Chen, 1933: 270.
Amyntas incongruus (Chen): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.

Type locality. Lin-hai-hsien, China (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** USNM (Chang *et al.*

2009); **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Taiwan; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas labosus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima labosa Gates, 1932: 543.
Pheretima labosa: Gates 1972: 164.
Amyntas labosus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 243.

Type locality. Nam Hpen Noi (Namphan or Na-hpan?), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3069, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas longicauliculatus* (Gates, 1926)**

Pheretima sp. Gates, 1926: 162.
Pheretima longicauliculata: Gates, 1931: 395.
Pheretima longicauliculata: Gates 1972: 163.
Amyntas longicauliculatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 243.

Type locality. Tolo Senca, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas luxus* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima luxa: Gates, 1936: 427.
Pheretima luxa: Gates 1972: 165.
Amyntas luxus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 243.

Type locality. Between Mao-Hsao and Namkham, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3277; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas malacus* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima maculosa Gates, 1933: 534 (non *P. maculosus* Hatai 1930).
Pheretima malaca Gates, 1936: 429 (nom. nov. pro *maculosa*).
Amyntas malacus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. Between Kyaukmeduang and Kameik, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas manicatus manicatus* (Gates, 1931)**

Pheretima sutoria var. *manicata*: Gates, 1931: 414.
Pheretima manicata var. *typica*: Gates 1932: 526 comb. nov. pro. *P. sutoria* var. *manicata*.
Pheretima manicata manicata: Gates 1972: 201.
Amyntas manicatus manicatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 244.

Type locality. Moulmein (Mawlamyine), Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3115, 3598, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Thailand, Vietnam, possibly Laos (Blakemore 2007b); **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas manicatus decorosus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima manicata var. *decorosa*: Gates, 1932: 528.
Pheretima manicata decorosa: Gates 1972: 201.
Amyntas manicatus decorosus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Type locality. Teung Cong, Yunnan Province, China; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas masatakae* (Beddard, 1892)**

Perichaeta masatakae Beddard, 1892d: 761.
Amyntas masatakae Beddard: Chuang & Chen, 2002: 74.
Amyntas tralfamadore Blakemore, 2012: 143.
Amyntas scaberulus Sun & Jiang, 2021: 462.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012b) and Chang *et al.* (2024).

Type locality. Blachi, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10.5.912 (Lectotype), BMNH 1904:10.5.913 (Paralectotype) (Blakemore 2012b); **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** China, Japan, Korea, Taiwan (Chang *et al.* 2024); **Status.** Native peregrine.

Remarks. Its presence in India is confirmed by Chang *et al.* (2024). As per Chang *et al.* (2024), the molecular data submitted to NCBI website (Acc. No. 444905) from northeastern India as *A. hawayanus* (= *A. gracilis*) by Vabeiryureilai *et al.* (2020) is actually belongs to *A. masatakae*.

***Amyntas minimus* (Horst, 1893)**

Perichaeta minima Horst, 1893: 66.
Pheretima enchytraeoides Michaelsen, 1916: 33.
Pheretima zoysiae Chen, 1933: 288.
Amyntas minimus: Easton, 1979:119; Ahmed *et al.* 2026: 378.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Tjibodas, Java Island, Indonesia; **Type depository.** Leiden Museum: 1836; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Cote d'Ivoire, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, South Africa, Swaziland; Americas: USA; Asia: recorded in East and Southeast Asia, China, Indonesia, Japan? Singapore, Taiwan; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii (USA), Papua New Guinea, Samoa; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Original home of this species is unknown (Gates 1972).

***Amyntas morrisi* (Beddard, 1892)**

Perichaeta morrisi Beddard, 1892b: 166.
Pheretima barbadensis (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 254 (part).
Pheretima morrisi (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 287.
Pheretima hawayana var. *lineata* Gates, 1926a: 154.
Amyntas morrisi (Beddard): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.
Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a, 2014).

Type locality. Kew Gardens from Penang Malaysia; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5: 199-201, now in NHM (Nguyen *et al.* 2016); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Probably originally from China (Nguyen *et al.* 2016); Africa: Canary Islands (Spain), Cape Verde Island, Madeira (Portugal), São Tomé, South Africa, St Helena (Britain); Ame

ricas: Argentina, Barbados, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Guatemala, Guyana, Mexico, Peru, USA; Asia: China, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Japan, Laos, Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkiye, Vietnam; Europe: England, Italy, Spain; Oceania: Australia, Hawaii (USA), Marshal Island, New Guinea; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas nugalis* (Gates, 1931)**

Pheretima nugalis Gates, 1931: 402.
Pheretima nugalis: Gates 1972: 203.
Amyntas nugalis (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.

Type locality. Kyaikmaraw, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas osmastoni* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Pheretima osmastoni Michaelsen, 1907: 163.
Amyntas osmastoni (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. Wimberleyganj bay, Andaman and Nicobar Islands union territory, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7171, ZSIC 2832, MNHU 7465 (= ZMB Verm. 7465, presumably 1 Syn-type, dried specimen) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas pallidus* (Michaelsen, 1892)**

Perichaeta pallida Michaelsen, 1892: 227.
Perichaeta cupidifera Fedarb, 1898b: 445.
Amyntas pallidus (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2014: 135.
Amyntas pallidus (Michaelsen): Narayanan et al. 2025g: 226.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2014).

Type locality. Porto Alegre, Brazil; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Myanmar; Americas: Brazil, Chile; **Status.** Exotic peregrine, probably originally from China (Blakemore 2014).

***Amyntas papilio papilio* (Gates, 1930)**

Pheretima papilio Gates, 1930: 316.

Pheretima papilio var. *typica* Gates, 1932: 401.
Pheretima papilio papilio: Gates, 1972: 205.
Amyntas papilio papilio (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.
Amyntas papilio (Gates): Blakemore 2012a: 394.

Type locality. San Hlan, Tanintharyi Region, Myanmar (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now (Halder 1999); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Taiwan; **Status.** Native peregrine? introduced to India.

***Amyntas papilio hiulcus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima papilio var. *hiulca* Gates, 1932: 401.
Pheretima papilio var. *fracta* Gates, 1933: 539.
Pheretima papilio hiulca: Gates, 1960: 270.
Pheretima papilio hiulca: Gates, 1972: 206.
Amyntas papilio hiulcus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.

Type locality. Blachi, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3094, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas papilio vespertilio* Blakemore, 2006**

Pheretima papilio var. *insignis* Gates, 1932: 404.
Pheretima papilio insignis Gates: Gates, 1960: 270.
Amyntas papilio insignis (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.
Pheretima papilio vespertilio Blakemore, 2006: 9. nom. nov. pro *Pheretima papilio insignis* Gates, 1932 (non *Pheretima insignis* Michaelsen, 1921).

Type locality. Thaton, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3066, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Amyntas papulosus* (Rosa, 1896)**

Perichaeta papulosa Rosa, 1896: 525.
Pheretima composita Gates, 1932: 430.
Pheretima papulosa (Rosa): Michaelsen 1900a: 291.
Amyntas papulosus (Rosa): Easton 1981: 56.
Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Balighe, Indonesia (Nguyen *et al.* 2016); **Type depository.** MGDG 44034; other material in British Museum (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Widespread in eastern Asian countries, Asia: China, Hong Kong? Japan, Myanmar, Sumatra (Indonesia), Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas pauxillulus* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima pauxillula Gates, 1936: 442.

Pheretima digna Chen, 1946: 132.

Amyntas pauxillulus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.

Type locality. Kutkai, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3304; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Vietnam; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas rimosus rimosus* (Gates, 1931)**

Pheretima rimosus Gates, 1931: 408.

Pheretima rimosus var. *typica* Gates, 1932: 534.

Pheretima rimosus: Gates 1972: 215.

Amyntas rimosus rimosus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.

Type locality. Mong Ko, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3099, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Amyntas rimosus effeminatus* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima rimosus var. *effeminata* Gates, 1932: 537.

Amyntas rimosus effeminatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 236.

Type locality. Nam Hpen Noi (Namphan or Na-hpan?), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3103; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Probably a synonym of the nominate species (Blakemore 2007b).

***Amyntas robustus* (Perrier, 1872)**

Perichaeta robusta Perrier, 1872: 112.

Amyntas löhri Michaelsen, 1899b: 12.

Megascolex robustus (Perrier): Vaillant 1889: 76.

Pheretima himalayana Stephenson, 1925a: 893.

Pheretima ornata Gates, 1927: 20.

Amyntas robustus (Perrier): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Île de France (Isle de France) (Mauritius) (Nguyen *et al.* 2016); **T.** MNHN 587-8; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Probable homeland is China (Gates 1972); Africa: Madagascar, Mauritius, Reunion Island; Americas: Brazil?; Asia: China, Hong Kong, Japan, Korea, Laos, Philippines, Taiwan, Vietnam; Europe: France; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Amyntas rodericensis* (Grube, 1879)**

Perichaeta rodericensis Grube, 1879: 554.

Pheretima rodericensis (Grube): Michaelsen 1900a: 299.

Amyntas rodericensis (Grube): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Further synonymies in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Rodriguez (Rodrigues), Mauritius (Nguyen *et al.* 2016); **Type depository.** WUMW (Syntypes); **Distribution.** Myanmar? India; **Elsewhere.** Cosmopolitan species (Blakemore 2012a). Africa: Canary Islands (Spain), Eswatini (Swaziland), Grande Terre Island (France), Ivory Coast, Lagos, Mauritius, Madagascar, Moheli (Comoros), Rodriguez (Mauritius), São Tomé, Seychelles; South Africa; Americas: Barbados, Bermuda, Hispaniola (Dominican Republic), French Guiana, Grenada, Guadeloupe Island (France), Guatemala, Guadeloupe (France), Guyana, Jamaica, Martinique (France), Puerto Rico, St Kitts, Surinam, Trinidad, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Christmas Island (Australia), Japan, Myanmar, Vietnam; Europe: Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, UK; Oceania: Australia, Marshal Island, New Caledonia (France), Samoa; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

***Amyntas sonellus* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima sonella Gates, 1936: 458.

Pheretima sonella: Gates 1972: 164.

Amyntas sonellus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Type locality. Namkham, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3583; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. According to Blakemore (2007b) this species is of doubtful identity needing further investigation.

Amyntas subtilis (Gates, 1943)

Pheretima subtilis Gates, 1943: 104.

Pheretima subtilis: Gates 1972: 219.

Amyntas subtilis (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Type locality. Meung Nawng (Mong Nawng?), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Amyntas suctorius suctorius (Michaelsen, 1907)

Pheretima suctoria Michaelsen, 1907: 165.

Amyntas suctorius suctorius (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Type locality. Andaman Islands, Andaman and Nicobar Islands union territory, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2828, ZMUH V 7168; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Amyntas sulcatus (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima sulcata Gates, 1932: 424.

Pheretima sulcata: Gates 1972: 220.

Amyntas sulcatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 234.

Type locality. Kawkariiek, Karen State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Amyntas terrigenus (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima terrigena Gates, 1932: 482.

Pheretima terrigena: Gates 1972: 221.

Amyntas terrigenus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. Karen Hills (Gates 1972), Myanmar; **Type depository** ZSIC 3708, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Amyntas velatus (Gates, 1930)

Pheretima velata Gates, 1930: 321.

Pheretima velata var. *clavata* Gates, 1930: 541.

Pheretima velata: Gates 1972: 161.

Amyntas velatus (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Type locality. Thandaung, Kayin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3134, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Amyntas youngi (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima youngi Gates, 1932: 406.

Pheretima youngi: Gates 1972: 224.

Amyntas youngi (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. Pang Wo (Pang War/ Pangwa/ Pang Wah), Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3077, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** China; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

Amyntas whitteni Bantaowong, Chanabun & Panha, 2020

Amyntas whitteni Bantaowong, Chanabun & Panha, 2020: 17.

Type locality. Pathen Mountain, Mon State, Myanmar (Bantaowong *et al.* 2020); **Type depository.** CUMZ 3805 (Holotype), CUMZ 3806, ZRC (Bantaowong *et al.* 2020); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Argilophilus* Eisen, 1893

Argilophilus Eisen, 1893: 97.

Type species. *Argilophilus marmoratus ornatus* Eisen, 1893

Distribution. Chiefly North America, India, Myanmar and Sri Lanka (Gates 1972; Julka & Paliwal 2011).

Remark. Taxonomic history of *Plutellus* Perrier, 1873 and *Argilophilus* is complicated (Gates 1972; Narayanan et al. 2023a). Gates (1972), recommended placing Indo-Oriental species of *Plutellus* under genus *Argilophilus*. However, the presence of the North American *Argilophilus* in the Indian Subcontinent is dubious (Narayanan et al. 2021a). Blakemore (2006b) commented that the Indo-Oriental *Argilophilus* species should be placed in another genus, probably a new one but such a change is deferred pending resolution of the North American taxa and comparison with the Asian ones. Further molecular work should be carried out to simplify the status of these species and thus require a taxonomic revision of species of *Plutellus* and *Argilophilus*.

***Argilophilus aborensis* (Stephenson, 1914)**

Plutellus aborensis Stephenson, 1914b: 384.
Argilophilus aborensis (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Rotung (Rottung), Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5443; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus ambiguus* (Gates, 1931)**

Plutellus ambiguus Gates, 1931: 357.
Plutellus ambiguus: Gates 1972: 40.
Argilophilus ambiguus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Unknown, possibly from the northern portion of Chindwin Valley (Gates 1972), Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus aquatilis* (Stephenson, 1921)**

Plutellus aquatilis Stephenson, 1921a: 756.
Argilophilus aquatilis (Stephenson): Blakemore, 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Kotagiri, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:5:25:1328, ZSIC 552; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus bahli* (Julka, 1981)**

Plutellus bahli Julka, 1981: 10.
Argilophilus bahli (Julka): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Tumbia, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An88 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An89, An90 (Paratypes) (Julka 1981a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus campsiaulus* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Plutellus campsiaulus Stephenson, 1924b: 328.
Argilophilus campsiaulus (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Vanderavu (Bander), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:2:23:388, ZSIC 1113, JWRC 3439, *typus translatus* as NMNS 1978-261 (= JWRC 3439); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus compositus* (Gates, 1933)**

Plutellus inflexus var. *compositus* Gates, 1933: 477.
Plutellus compositus Gates: Gates 1955: 61.
Argilophilus compositus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Tonbo, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus comptus* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus comptus Gates, 1955: 62.
Plutellus comptus Gates: Gates 1972: 41.
Argilophilus comptus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Hlegu, Yangon Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus daminensis* (Julka, 1981)**

Plutellus daminensis Julka, 1981: 11.
Argilophilus daminensis (Julka): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Damin, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC ZSI An-91 (Holotype) (Julka 1981a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus dubariensis* (Michaelsen, 1922)**

Plutellus dubariensis Michaelsen, 1922: 61.
Argilophilus dubariensis (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. River Cauvery – Dubari (Dubare), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 9159; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus exilis* (Gates, 1945)**

Plutellus exilis Gates, 1945b: 224.
Argilophilus exilis (Gates): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Daraganj, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus geminatus* (Gates, 1961)**

Plutellus geminatus Gates, 1961a: 418.
Plutellus geminatus Gates: Gates 1972: 41.
Argilophilus geminatus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Thazi, Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** TTRS 1572 (= USNM 124770), JWRC 3440 (= NMNS 1978–262); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus ghumensis* (Julka, 1975)**

Plutellus ghumensis Julka, 1975: 24.
Argilophilus ghumensis (Julka): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Jorpokri, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 211-4; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus halyi* (Michaelsen, 1899)**

Megascolides halyi Michaelsen, 1899c: 142.
Plutellus halyi (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900: 165.
Argilophilus halyi (Michaelsen): Blakemore, 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Colombo museum garden, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 5015 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Argilophilus himalayanus* (Gates, 1945)**

Plutellus himalayanus Gates, 1945a: 71.
Argilophilus himalayanus (Gates): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Changu, Sikkim State, India (Gates 1945a); **Type depository.** ZSIC 3672; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus indicus indicus* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Plutellus indicus f. *typica* Michaelsen, 1907: 148.
Argilophilus indicus indicus (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7146; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus indicus silvestris* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Plutellus indicus var. *silvestris* Michaelsen, 1907: 149.
Argilophilus indicus silvestris (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Tiger Shola near Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2920; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus inflexus* (Stephenson, 1931)**

Plutellus inflexus Stephenson, 1931c: 179.
Plutellus inflexus var. *typici* Gates, 1933: 477.
Plutellus inflexus Stephenson: Gates 1955: 64.
Plutellus inflexus Stephenson: Gates 1972: 42.
Argilophilus inflexus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Kalewa, Sagaing Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1930:12:27:48–55; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus kempii* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Plutellus kempii Stephenson, 1924b: 327.
Argilophilus kempii (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1112; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus leucaspis* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus leucaspis Gates, 1955: 418.
Plutellus leucaspis Gates: Gates 1972: 42.
Argilophilus leucaspis (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Yandoon, Ayeyarwady Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus longus* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus sp. Gates, 1933: 484.
Plutellus longus Gates, 1955: 66.
Argilophilus longus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 4.

Type locality. Chaukan near Pegu, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus macer* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus macer Gates, 1955: 67.
Argilophilus macer (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Lashio, Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus macrochaetus macrochaetus* (Stephenson, 1925)**

Plutellus macrochaetus Stephenson, 1925b: 54.
Argilophilus macrochaetus macrochaetus (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Korangumudi EState - Valparai, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1208, BMNH 1933:2: 23:390-2; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus macrochaetus simplicisetus* (Jamieson, 1977)**

Diporochaeta macrochaeta simpliciseta Jamieson, 1977b: 482.
Argilophilus macrochaetus simplicisetus (Jamieson): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Border between Kerala State and Tamil Nadu, Vandaravu range, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Paris Museum AH323 (Holotype), AH324-327, BJ 1976.5.5-6 (Paratype) (Jamieson 1977b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus mishmiensis* (Julka, 1976)**

Plutellus mishmiensis Julka, 1976a: 236.
Argilophilus mishmiensis (Julka): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Tihun, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An115/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An116/1, An117/1, An118/1, An119/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus montanus* (Gates, 1961)**

Plutellus montanus Gates, 1961a: 419.
Argilophilus montanus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Mount Poa, Myanmar; **Type depository.** TTRS 1570 (= USNM 36915) but as per Gates (1972) no types; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus palniensis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Plutellus palniensis Michaelsen, 1907: 150.
Argilophilus ? palniensis (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Tiger Shola near Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2918, ZMUH V 7142; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus pandus* (Gates, 1933)**

Plutellus pandus Gates, 1933: 419.
Plutellus pandus: Gates 1972: 44.
Argilophilus pandus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Yangon region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3047, but as per Gates (1972) no types; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus pauxillulus* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus pauxillulus Gates, 1955: 70.
Plutellus pauxillulus: Gates 1972: 44.
Argilophilus pauxillulus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Aungsaing, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus pratensis* (Gates, 1932)**

Plutellus pratensis Gates, 1932: 70.
Plutellus pratensis: Gates 1972: 44.
Argilophilus pratensis (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Toungoo, Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus rallus* (Gates, 1945)**

Plutellus rallus Gates, 1945a: 72.
Argilophilus rallus (Gates): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1263; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus richikensis* (Julka, 1981)**

Plutellus richikensis Julka, 1981: 12.
Argilophilus richikensis (Julka): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Richik, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An92 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An93 to An98 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus rudis* (Gates, 1961)**

Plutellus rudis Gates, 1961a: 420.
Plutellus rudis: Gates 1972: 45.
Argilophilus rudis (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Unknown, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus sadhupulensis* (Julka & Paliwal, 1994)**

Plutellus sadhupulensis Julka & Paliwal, 1994: 217.
Argilophilus sadhupulensis (Julka & Paliwal): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Sadhupul, Himachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An789 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An790 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus sikkimensis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Plutellus sikkimensis Michaelsen, 1907: 147.
Argilophilus sikkimensis (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Sandakphu, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2921, ZMUH V 7182, BMNH 1925:5:12:128-9; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus singhalensis* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Megascolides singhalensis Michaelsen, 1897a: 174.
Plutellus singhalensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900: 165.
Argilophilus singhalensis (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 28.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4644 (Cs. Csuzdi *in itt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Argilophilus subtilis* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus subtilis Gates, 1955: 73.
Plutellus subtilis: Gates 1972: 46.
Argilophilus subtilis (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Kyaikto, Mon State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus taksingensis* (Julka, 1981)**

Plutellus taksingensis Julka, 1981: 14.
Argilophilus taksingensis (Julka): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Taksing, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An99 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI A-100 to An-109 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus tenuis* (Gates, 1961)**

Plutellus tenuis Gates, 1961a: 422.
Plutellus tenuis: Gates 1972: 46.
Argilophilus tenuis (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Tharrawaddy (Thayarwaddy), Bago Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** TTRS 1568 (= USNM 136916), JWRC 3441 (= NMNS

1978–263); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus thanbularanus* (Gates, 1955)**

Plutellus thanbularanus Gates, 1955: 422.
Plutellus thanbularanus: Gates 1972: 46.
Argilophilus thanbularanus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.

Type locality. Thanbula (Thayetmyo), Magway Region, Myanmar; **Type depository** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Argilophilus timidus* (Cognetti, 1911)**

Plutellus timidus Cognetti, 1911: 497.
Argilophilus timidus (Cognetti): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Muvattupuzha, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1911:4:16:2-13; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Argilophilus variabilis* (Aiyer, 1929)**

Plutellus variabilis Aiyer, 1929: 51.
Argilophilus variabilis (Aiyer): Blakemore 2007a: 29.

Type locality. Tenmalai (Thenmala), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1512; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Barogaster* Gates, 1940

Megascolides Stephenson 1920: 202.
Megascolides Stephenson 1923: 192 (part).
Eudichogaster Stephenson 1923: 402 (part).
Barogaster Gates, 1940a: 154.

Type species. *Eudichogaster barodensis* Stephenson, 1914.

Distribution. Peninsular India.

***Barogaster annandalei* (Stephenson, 1921)**

Megascolides annandalei Stephenson, 1921a: 757.
Barogaster annandalei (Stephenson): Gates 1940c: 130.

Type locality. Dowlaishweram (Dowleswaram, Dhavaleswaram, Dowlaiswaram), Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W 562/1, BMNH 1933:5:5:25 1340; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Barogaster barodensis* (Stephenson, 1914)**

Eudichogaster barodensis Stephenson, 1914a: 358.
Barogaster barodensis (Stephenson): Gates 1940a: 156.

Type locality. Baroda (Vadodara), Gujarat State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W27/1, BMNH 1925:5:12:64; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Barogaster prashadi* (Stephenson, 1920)**

Megascolides prashadi Stephenson, 1920: 202.
Barogaster prashadi (Stephenson): Gates 1940c: 135.

Type locality. Sakarwari, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W291/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Celeriella* Gates, 1958

Spenceriella Stephenson 1923: 190 (part).
Celeriella Gates 1958b: 612.

Type species. *Spenceriella duodecimalis* Michaelsen, 1907.

Distribution. India (Palani Hills of southern India) and Australia.

***Celeriella bursata* Jamieson, 1977**

Celeriella bursata Jamieson, 1977b: 487.
Celeriella bursata Jamieson: Narayanan et al. 2024d: 51.

Type locality. Border between Kerala and Tamil Nadu States Vandaravau range, India; **Type depository.** Paris Museum AH 328 (Holotype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Celeriella ditheca* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Spenceriella duodecimalis f. *ditheca* Stephenson, 1924b: 332.
Celeriella ditheca (Stephenson): Gates 1958b: 613.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1118/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Celeriella duodecimalis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Spenceriella duodecimalis Michaelsen, 1907: 152.
Celeriella duodecimalis (Michaelsen): Gates 1958b: 613.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2950/7, ZMUH V 7148; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Celeriella kempi* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Spenceriella kempi Stephenson, 1924b: 332.
Celeriella kempi (Stephenson): Gates 1958b: 613

Type locality. Marian Shola, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1119/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

***Celeriella punctata* Jamieson, 1977**

Celeriella punctata Jamieson, 1977b: 489.

Type locality. Gundar Shola, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Paris Museum AH329 (Holotype), Paris Museum AH330-331, BJ 1976.5.7-8 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic

***Celeriella quadripapillata* Stephenson, 1924**

Spenceriella duodecimalis f. *quadripapillata* Stephenson, 1924b: 331.
Celeriella quadripapillata (Stephenson): Gates 1958b: 613.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1117/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Myanmar record never have been confirmed, it may have been brought from India in soil with plants (Gates 1972).

***Celeriella regularis* Stephenson, 1924**

Spenceriella duodecimalis f. *regularis* Stephenson, 1924b: 330.
Celeriella regularis (Stephenson): Gates 1958b: 613.

Type locality. Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1115-1116/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. So far known only from the type locality.

Genus *Comarodrilus* Stephenson, 1915

Comarodrilus Stephenson, 1915: 69.

Type species. *Comarodrilus graveleyi* Stephenson, 1915.

Distribution. India (Kerala, in south western India).

***Comarodrilus graveleyi* Stephenson, 1915**

Comarodrilus graveleyi Stephenson, 1915: 69.

Type locality. Trichur (= Thrissur), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6591; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Dashiella* Julka, 1988

Dashiella Julka, 1988a: 94.

Type species. *Dashiella khandalaensis* Julka, 1988.

Distribution. India (Northern Western Ghats).

***Dashiella khandalaensis* Julka, 1988**

Dashiella khandalaensis Julka, 1988a: 94.

Type locality. Khandala, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An1831-32/1 (Holotype and 6 paratypes), HAZFS ZSI An717 to An718 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Kanchuria* Julka, 1988

Kanchuria Julka, 1988b: 85.

Type species. *Kanchuria turaensis* Julka, 1988.

Distribution. North-eastern India (mainly to Khasi and Garo Hills of Meghalaya, Tripura and also in Manipur).

***Kanchuria antrophyes* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Megascolides antrophyes Stephenson, 1924a: 130.
Megascolides antrophyes Stephenson: Gates 1972: 233.

Kanchuria antrophyes (Stephenson): Julka 1988b: 91.

Type locality. Siju Cave, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1151/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria daribokgrensis* Lone, Tiwari, Thakur, Pearlson, Pavlíček & Yadav, 2020**

Kanchuria daribokgrensis Lone et al., 2020: 273.

Type locality. Daribokgre in Nokrek National Park, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI-CZRC 190101 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDM 272016001 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Kanchuria karorensis* Lone, Tiwari, Thakur,
Pearlson, Pavlíček & Yadav, 2020**

Kanchuria karorensis Lone *et al.*, 2020: 274.

Type locality. Rumra Husan in Baghmara Reserve Forest, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI-CZRC 190102 (Holotype), DHS GV-ZDM 272016002 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria makhulensis* Lone, Tiwari, Thakur,
Pearlson, Pavlíček & Yadav, 2020**

Kanchuria makhulensis Lone *et al.*, 2020: 274.

Type locality. Makhulkaula in Baghmara Reserve Forest, Meghalaya State, India (Lone *et al.* 2020); **Type depository.** ZSI-CZRC 190103 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDM 272016003 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria mohiskulensis* Lone, Tiwari,
Thakur, Pearlson, Pavlíček & Yadav, 2020**

Kanchuria mohiskulensis Lone *et al.*, 2020: 275.

Type locality. Jamrangdari in Balpakram National Park, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC 190104 (Holotype), DHS-GV ZDM 272016004 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria octotheca* Julka, 1988**

Kanchuria octotheca Julka, 1988b: 88.

Type locality. Tura, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An2197/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An2198/1, HARC-ZSI An769 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria priyasankari* Narayanan, Paliwal &
Julka, 2025**

Kanchuria priyasankari Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka in Narayanan *et al.*, 2025d: 107.

Type locality. Kamalpur, Tripura State, India (Narayanan *et al.* 2025d); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.28500 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.28501 (Paratypes) (Narayanan *et al.* 2025d); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Kanchuria sumeriana* Julka, 1988**

Kanchuria sumerianus Julka, 1988b: 89.
Kanchuria sumeriana Julka: Narayanan *et al.* 2025d: 102.

Type locality. Sumer, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An2199/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An2200/1, HARC-ZSI An771 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria tripuraensis* Narayanan, Paliwal &
Julka, 2025**

Kanchuria tripuraensis Narayanan, Paliwal & Julka in Narayanan *et al.*, 2025d: 103.

Type locality. Lankamura, Tripura State, India (Narayanan *et al.* 2025d); **Type depository.** ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.28502 (Holotype), ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.28503, ZSIK Reg. No. ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV. 28504 (Paratypes) (Narayanan *et al.* 2025d); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Kanchuria turaensis* Julka, 1988**

Kanchuria turaensis Julka, 1988b: 89.

Type locality. Tura, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An2201/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An2202/1, HARC-ZSI An772 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Lampito* Kinberg, 1867

Lampito Kinberg, 1867: 103.

Type species. *Lampito mauritii* Kinberg, 1867.

Distribution. India (majority of the species are endemic to Palani and Cardamom Hills of the Western Ghats in southern India). The type-species is a circumtropical peregrine by transportation, having been recorded from the tropics of the Indo-Asiatic region, Pacific Isles and Indian Ocean (Blakemore 2012a).

***Lampito bouchei* Jamieson, 1977**

Lampito bouchei Jamieson, 1977b: 497.

Type locality. Vandaravu - border between Kerala State and Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Paris Museum AH 337 (Holotype), BJ 1976.5.13 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Lampito kempi* Gates, 1938**

Lampito kempi Gates, 1938b: 407.

Type locality. Near Neutral Saddle near Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Lampito kumiliensis* (Aiyer, 1929)**

Megascolex kumiliensis Aiyer, 1929: 70.
Lampito kumiliensis (Aiyer): Gates 1938b: 408.

Type locality. Kumili, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:2:17:1-2, ZSIC 1522; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Lampito marianae* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Megascolex sylvicola var. *marianae* Stephenson, 1924b: 336.

Lampito marianae (Stephenson): Gates 1938b: 411.

Type locality. Marian Shola, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1121. **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Lampito mauritii* Kinberg, 1867**

Lampito mauritii Kinberg, 1867: 103.
Perichaeta armata Beddard, 1883: 216.
Perichaeta bivaginata Bourne, 1886: 666.
Perichaeta salettensis Bourne, 1886: 669.
Megascolex mauritii (Kinberg): Michaelsen 1900a: 227.
Lampito mauritii zeylanica Stephenson, 1913: 262.
Lampito trilobata Stephenson, 1914a: 340.
For further synonyms see Gates (1972) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Mauritius; **Type depository.** NHRS 162; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Maldives, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere:** Africa: Mauritius, Madagascar, Comoro Islands, Seychelles, South Africa, Zanzibar Island (Tanzania); Asia: Cambodia, China, Christmas Island (Australia), Hong Kong, Laos, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Indonesia, Thailand, Vietnam; Oceania: Hawaii (USA), Marshal Island, New Caledonia (France); **Status.** Native peregrine.

Remark. Its wide distribution clearly resulted from transoceanic carriage and the agent probably was man during the last 2,000 years and its original home is assumed to be somewhere in Palani and Cardamom Hills of Western Ghats in South India (Gates 1972).

***Lampito palniensis* (Stephenson, 1924)**

Notoscolex palniensis Stephenson, 1924b: 333.
Lampito palniensis (Stephenson): Gates 1938b: 420.

Type locality. Marian Shola near Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1120; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Lampito sylvicola* Michaelsen, 1907**

Lampito sylvicola Michaelsen, 1907: 161.
Megascolex sylvicola (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 273.

Type locality. Tiger Shola near Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2941; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Lampito vilpattiensis* Michaelsen, 1907**

Lampito vilpattiensis Michaelsen, 1907: 160.
Megascolex vilpattiensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1916: 52.

Type locality. Vilpatti, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC ZEV2934/1 (Gates 1938b), ZMB Verm. 7357 (1 Syntype) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), ZMUH V 7144 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Lenoscolex* Gates, 1960

Lenoscolex Gates, 1960: 241.

Type species. *Woodwardiella pumila* Stephenson, 1931.

Distribution. Presumably South India (Travancore and Cochin only? = present day Kerala State) (Gates 1972), but yet to be reported from India. Two species now inhabit in Myanmar, and one also reported from Java (Indonesia), perhaps after recent unintentional introduction by man (Gates 1972).

***Lenoscolex javanica* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Woodwardia javanica Michaelsen, 1910c: 93.
Woodwardiella javanica (Michaelsen): Gates 1942: 108.
Lenoscolex javanica (Michaelsen): Gates 1960: 243; 1972: 136.
Notoscolex javanica (Michaelsen): Gates 1961: 57.

Type locality. Buitenzorg, Java Island, Indonesia; **Type depository** ZMUH V 6447 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Java (Indonesia); **Status.** Unknown, introduced to Myanmar and Java but yet to be reported from India.

***Lenoscolex pumila* (Stephenson, 1931)**

Woodwardiella pumila Stephenson, 1931b: 51.
Notoscolex pumila (Stephenson): Gates 1945d: 48.
Lenoscolex pumila (Stephenson): Gates 1960: 242; 1972: 136.

Type locality. Bhamo, Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository** BMNH 1930:5:9:14; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic, probably introduced to Myanmar from South India.

Genus *Megascolex* Templeton, 1844

Megascolex Templeton, 1844: 89.

Type species. *Megascolex caeruleus* Templeton, 1844.

Distribution. Peninsular India (chiefly to southern Western Ghats) and Sri Lanka

***Megascolex acanthodriloides* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex acanthodriloides Michaelsen, 1897a: 235.

Type locality. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4660 (2 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex adami* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex adami Michaelsen, 1910a: 64.

Type locality. Bulutota, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3623 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex auriculatus* Aiyer, 1929**

Megascolex auriculata Aiyer, 1929: 64.

Type locality. Vandiperiyar, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1519; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex aviculus* Aiyer, 1929**

Megascolex avicula Aiyer, 1929: 66.

Type locality. Peermade (Peerumedu), India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex bifoveatus* Stephenson, 1913**

Megascolex bifoveatus Stephenson, 1913: 266.

Type locality. Pattipola, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5084; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex brachycyclus* (Schmarda, 1861)**

Perichaeta brachycycla Schmarda, 1861: 14.
Megascolex brachycyclus (Schmarda): Beddard 1895a: 382.

Type locality. Ratnapura, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex cochinensis* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex cochinensis Stephenson, 1915: 96.
Megascolex cochinensis cochinensis Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 33.

Type locality. Forest Tramway, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6593; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex caeruleus* Templeton, 1844**

Megascolex caeruleus Templeton, 1844: 89.

Type locality. Alpine region of Ceylon (Sri Lanka); **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex campester* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex campester Stephenson, 1915: 78.

Type locality. Horton Plains, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6186; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex ceylonicus* (Beddard, 1886)**

Perichaeta ceylonica Beddard, 1886a: 89.
Megascolex ceylonica (Beddard): Beddard 1895a: 385.
Megascolex ceylonicus (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900: 228.

Type locality. Unknown, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904.10.5.17, 1904.10.20.677-81; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex cingulatus* (Schmarda, 1861)**

Perichaeta cingulata Schmarda, 1861: 14
Megascolex cingulatus (Schmarda): Beddard 1895a: 382.

Type locality. East of Badulla, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** MNH; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex eunephrus* Cognetti, 1911**

Megascolex eunephrus Cognetti, 1911: 498.

Type locality. Coorloon (nr. south east of Thiruvananthapuram), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1911:4:16:8; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex escherichi escherichi* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex escherichi Michaelsen, 1910a: 66.

Megascolex escherichi (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 241.

Megascolex escherichi escherichi (Michaelsen): Blake-more 2007a: 33.

Type locality. Hidana near Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description

***Megascolex escherichi papillifer* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex escherichi papillifer Stephenson, 1915: 77.

Type locality. Horton Plains, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6187, 6926; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex filicisetus* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex filiciseta Stephenson, 1915: 94.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6605; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex funis* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex funis Michaelsen, 1897a: 210.

Type locality. Kandy, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMH V 4658 (one of the two syntypes); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex hakgallanus* Gates, 1941**

Megascolex hakgallanus Gates, 1945e: 49.

Type locality. Hakgalla (Hakgala), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex hendersoni* Michaelsen, 1907**

Megascolex hendersoni Michaelsen, 1907: 162.

Megascolex hendersoni Michaelsen: Narayanan et al. 2023c: 178.

Type locality. Tiger Shola near Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7149, ZSIC 2925; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex hortonensis* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex hortonensis Stephenson, 1915: 83.

Type locality. Horton Plains, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6928; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex imperatrix* (Bourne, 1894)**

Mahbenus imperatrix Bourne, 1894a: 12.

Megascolex imperatrix (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 233.

Type locality. amb's Rock - Coonoor, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex insignis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex insignis Michaelsen, 1910a: 78.

Megascolex kavalaiamus Stephenson, 1915: 91. **syn. nov.**

Megascolex trivandranus Stephenson, 1916: 330. **syn. nov.**

Type locality. Trivandrum (Thiruvananthapuram), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 4176; **Distribution.** India, Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic;

Remarks. *M. kavalaiamus* Stephenson, 1915, and *M. trivandranus* Stephenson, 1916 are two small species of the genus described in first

quarter of the last century by Stephenson (1915, 1916), from the present day Kerala State, India. Re-examination of the type materials deposited at the National Zoological Collections of Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata, by one of the authors (JMJ) revealed that they are actually junior synonyms of *M. insignis*. Details of these are given below.

The description of *Megascolex kavalaianus* was based on a single specimen (Stephenson 1915). Later, Stephenson (1923) opined that ‘it may ultimately have to be united with *M. insignis*’. The chief difference is in the male field and the hearts (the last in xiv in this form); other details in which the two differ are the oesophageal swellings, the point of commencement of the intestine, and the absence of thickened septa in the present form. The apparent differences in the spermathecae are perhaps not very important, as this organ is variable in *M. insignis*.’ In the re-examination of the the type material (Reg. No. ZEV6592/7 (now ZSIC 2832)) by one of the author (JMJ), found that the septa 5/6 delicate, 6/7 slightly muscular, 7/8–12/13 muscular (vs no septa noticeably thickened); gizzard in segment 5 (vs 6); intestine origin in segment 14 or 15 (vs in segment 19); last pair of hearts in segment 13 (vs 14); prostate is in segment 18 or lightly extending to 19; no typhlosole. Thus, as suggested by Stephenson (1923), herein *M. kavalaianus* is synonymized with *M. insignis*.

In the original description of *M. trivandranus*, Stephenson (1916) stated that he had two specimens available but provided the dimension only of a single specimen. The re-examination of the type material (Reg. No. ZEV7236/7 (now ZSIC 7236)) has revealed that there is only one a clitellate individual is in the container. But Stephenson (1916) clearly stated the extension of the clitellum in the species, hence we will have to assume that one specimen is missing from the container. Following details were noted from the specimen: female pore paired. Septum 5/6 delicate, 6/7 slightly muscular, 7/8–12/13 muscular. Gizzard in segment 5; intestine begins in segment 16, valvular in 15. No typhlosole. From

the original description and the re-examination of the type material, it is clear that *M. trivandranus* differs from *M. insignis* only in the intestinal origin. Intestinal origin in this specimen can be of some kind of abnormality, hence, this species considered here as a synonym of *M. insignis*.

***Megascolex jamiesoni* Narayanan & Paliwal, 2024**

Megascolex jamiesoni Narayanan & Paliwal in Narayanan et al., 2024c: 110.

Type locality. Jeypore Ghati, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV. 26204 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.26786 (Paratype) (Narayanan et al. 2024c); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex jeyporeghatiensis* Narayanan & Paliwal, 2024**

Megascolex jeyporeghatiensis Narayanan & Paliwal in Naik et al., 2024: 573.

Type locality. Jeypore Ghati, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV. 25144 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.25145 (Paratypes) (Naik et al. 2024); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex kempi* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex kempi Stephenson, 1915: 84.

Type locality. Horton Plains, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex konkanensis* Fedarb, 1898**

Megascolex konkanensis Fedarb, 1898a: 434.

Megascolex konkanensis konkanensis Fedarb: Stephenson 1923: 253.

Type locality. Somewhere in North Konkan in Maharashtra, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex lawsoni* (Bourne, 1886)**

Perichaeta lawsoni Bourne, 1886: 664 (part).
Pheretima lawsoni (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 316.
Megascolex curgensis Michaelsen, 1922: 64.
Megascolex lawsoni (Bourne): Easton 1982b: 1.
Megascolex lawsoni (Bourne): Narayanan et al. 2019a: 69.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** UMOU 1608, BMNH 1980.19.33-38; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex leucocyclus* (Schmarda, 1861)**

Perichaeta leucocyclus Schmarda, 1861: 13
Megascolex leucocyclus (Schmarda): Michaelsen 1897a: 215.

Type locality. Kandy, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex longiseta* Michaelsen, 1907**

Megascolex longiseta Michaelsen, 1907: 163.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex longus* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex konkanensis var. *longus* Stephenson, 1915: 97.
Megascolex konkanensis longus Stephenson: Blake-more 2007a: 35.
Megascolex longus Stephenson: Narayanan et al. 2025f: 2.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6602; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex lorenzi* Rosa, 1894**

Megascolex lorenzi Rosa, 1894: 5.

Type locality. Kandy, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex multispinus* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex multispinus Michaelsen, 1897a: 221.

Type locality. Peradeniya? Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** MNHU 7473 (= ZMB Verm. 7473), 1 Cotype (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989) but currently it is missing/cannot be located now, ZMUH V 4657 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex nureliyensis* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex nureliyensis Michaelsen, 1897a: 232.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4647 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex papparensis* Lone, Thakur, Tiwari, James & Yadav, 2022**

Megascolex papparensis Lone et al., 2022: 13.

Type locality. Mannoorkara close to Peppara Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/21 (Holotype) (Lone et al. 2025), DHSGV-ZDM 272015-013, DHSGV-ZDM 272015-014 (Paratypes) (Lone et al. 2022); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Only known from the type locality.

***Megascolex pattipolensis* Stephenson, 1913**

Megascolex pattipolensis Stephenson, 1913: 265.

Type locality. Pattipola, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 4894; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex peermadensis* Aiyer, 1929**

Megascolex peermadensis Aiyer, 1929: 68.

Type locality. Peermade (Peerumedu) (9.5783°N, 77.0154°E), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1521; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex pentagonalis* Stephenson, 1916**

Megascolex pentagonalis Stephenson, 1916: 331.

Megascolex travancorensis var. *pentagonalis* Stephenson: Stephenson 1923: 278.

Megascolex travancorensis pentagonalis Stephenson: Blakemore, 2007a: 37.

Megascolex pentagonalis Stephenson: Narayanan et al. 2023b: 11.

Type locality. Trivandrum (Thiruvananthapuram), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 7234; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex peranellus* Gates, 1945**

Megascolex peranellus Gates, 1945e: 78.

Type locality. Hakgalla (Hakgala), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex peranus* Gates, 1941**

Megascolex peranus Gates, 1941a: 52.

Type locality. Hakgalla (Hakgala), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Species inquirenda.

***Megascolex pharetratus* Rosa, 1894**

Megascolex pharetratus Rosa, 1894: 3.

Type locality. Kandy, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex phaseolus* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex phaseolus Stephenson, 1915: 93.

Megascolex cochinchensis var. *phaseolus* Stephenson: Stephenson 1923: 238.

Megascolex cochinchensis phaseolus Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 33.

Megascolex phaseolus Stephenson: Narayanan et al. 2025f: 6.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6601; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex pheretima* Michaelsen, 1922**

Megascolex pheretima Michaelsen, 1922: 66.

Type locality. Manakoti, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH 9151; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex polytheca polytheca* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex polytheca Stephenson, 1915: 89.

Megascolex polytheca polytheca Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 36.

Type locality. Kavalai in forest tramway, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6921, BMNH 1933:5:25:91; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex polytheca uniuus* Aiyer, 1929**

Megascolex polytheca var. *uniuus* ? Aiyer, 1929: 71.
Megascolex polytheca uniuus Aiyer: Blakemore 2007a: 36.

Type locality. Kumili, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex polytheca zonatus* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex polytheca var. *zonatus* Stephenson, 1915: 90.
Megascolex polytheca zonatus Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 36.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6604, BMNH 1933:5:25:92; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex porphyrozonus* Stephenson, 1924**

Megascolex porphyrozonus Stephenson, 1924b: 337.

Type locality. Nandi Hills, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1925:5:12:4; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex pumilio* Stephenson, 1916**

Megascolex pumilio Stephenson, 1916: 333.

Type locality. Trivandrum (Thiruvananthapuram), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 7238; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex quadripapillatus* Narayanan & Paliwal, 2024**

Megascolex quadripapillatus Narayanan & Paliwal in Naik et al., 2024: 570.

Type locality. Raniduduma, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV. 25142 (Holotype), ZSI/WGRC/I.R.INV.25143 (Paratype) (Naik et al. 2024); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex quintus* Stephenson, 1913**

Megascolex quintus Stephenson, 1913: 268.

Type locality. Pattipola, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5081 **Distribution** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex ratus* Cognetti, 1911**

Megascolex ratus Cognetti, 1911: 500.

Type locality. Coorloon (nr. south east of Thiruvananthapuram), Kerala State, India; **T.** BMNH 1911:4:16:9-10, ZSIC 4782; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex sarasinorum* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex sarasinorum Michaelsen, 1897a: 224.

Type locality. Trincomali (Trincomalee), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:475 but currently missing/cannot be located now, ZMUH V 4637, 4640 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. But as per Gates (1945e) type locality is undesignated.

***Megascolex schmardae* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex schmardae Michaelsen, 1897a: 208.

Type locality. Ratnapura, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** WNHM 3970 (Jirapatrasilp 2024: p 214); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex sextus* Stephenson, 1913**

Megascolex sextus Stephenson, 1913: 270.

Type locality. Pattipola, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5083; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex singhalensis* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex singhalensis Michaelsen, 1897a: 227.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** WNHM 3971, ZMUH V 4645 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex spectabilis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex spectabilis Michaelsen, 1910a: 80.

Type locality. Vaxvella (Wakwella), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** MNHU 7441, ZMUH V 3506 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex templetonianus* Rosa, 1892**

Megascolex templetonianus Rosa, 1892: 1.

Type locality. Ceylon (Sri Lanka); **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex travancorensis travancorensis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex travancorensis f. *typica* Michaelsen, 1910a: 72.

Megascolex travancorensis travancorensis Michaelsen: Blakemore 2007a: 37.

Type locality. Pallode (Palode), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 4160, ZMUH V

3615 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex travancorensis bonaccordensis* Michaelsen, 1913**

Megascolex travancorensis var. *bonaccordensis* Michaelsen, 1913a: 84.

Megascolex travancorensis bonaccordensis Michaelsen: Blakemore 2007a: 36.

Type locality. Bonaccord (Bonacaud, Bonakad), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V8094 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic;

***Megascolex travancorensis ghatensis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex travancorensis var. *ghatensis* Michaelsen, 1910a: 75.

Megascolex travancorensis ghatensis Michaelsen: Blakemore 2007a: 37.

Type locality. Maddathoray (Madathara), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 4163, ZMUH V 3617 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex travancorensis proboscidea* Aiyer, 1929**

Megascolex travancorensis var. *proboscidea* Aiyer, 1929: 62.

Megascolex travancorensis proboscidea Aiyer: Blakemore 2007a: 37.

Type locality. Tenmalai (Thenmala), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1518; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex travancorensis quilonensis* Michaelsen, 1910**

Megascolex travancorensis var. *quilonensis* Michaelsen, 1910a: 74.

Megascolex travancorensis quilonensis Michaelsen:
Blakemore 2007a: 37.

Type locality. Shasthancottah (Sathamkotta), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3616 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex triangularis* Stephenson, 1925**

Megascolex triangularis Stephenson, 1925b: 56.

Type locality. Kavalai, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex tripartitus* Stephenson, 1925**

Megascolex tripartitus Stephenson, 1925b: 58.

Type locality. Tirumalai Hills, Andhra Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ?. **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. *Species inquirenda* (Blakemore 2007a). Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex varians varians* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex varians Michaelsen, 1897a: 201.
Megascolex varians varians (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 37.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** MNHU 7258 (= ZMB Verm. 7258, Holotype, dried specimen, in fragments), MNHU 7466 (= ZMB Verm. 7466, 1 Cotype) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), ZMUH V 4649 (2 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026), RNHL; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex varians insolitus* Stephenson, 1915**

Megascolex varians insolitus Stephenson, 1915: 86.

Type locality. Horton Plains, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6918; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex varians simplex* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex varians simplex Michaelsen, 1897a: 207.
Megascolex annandalei Stephenson, 1913: 263.
Megascolex curtus Stephenson, 1913: 267.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka. **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4648 (2 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Megascolex vazhichlensis* Lone, Thakur, Tiwari, James & Yadav, 2022**

Megascolex vazhichlensis Lone *et al.*, 2022: 14.

Type locality. Mannoorkara close to Peppara Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/22 (Holotype) (Lone *et al.* 2025); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Megascolex* (?) *viridis* (Schmarda, 1861)**

Perichaeta viridis Schmarda, 1861: 13.
Megascolex (?) *viridis* (Schmarda): Michaelsen 1897a: 242.

Type locality. Near Belligamme (Valikamam, Valligamam, Valikaamam), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. *Species inquirenda* (Blakemore 2007a). Michaelsen (1897a) commented that, if it is not *Megascolex*, it should be assigned to *Perionyx*. In that case, since there is already a species with the name *viridis* in *Perionyx*, a new name should be proposed to avoid homonymy.

***Megascolex willeyi* Michaelsen, 1909**

Megascolex willeyi Michaelsen, 1909: 96.

Type locality. Labugama, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3114 (5 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Megascolex zygochaetus* Michaelsen, 1897**

Megascolex zygochaetus Michaelsen, 1897a: 199.

Type locality. Ratnapura, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** WNHM 3977; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Metaphire* Sims & Easton, 1972

Metaphire Sims & Easton, 1972: 215. (Nom. nov. pro *Rhodopis* Kinberg, 1867 non Reichenbach, 1845 (Aves) nec. Thomson, 1857 (Insecta))

Type species. *Rhodopis javanica* Kinberg, 1867, by monotypy (Sims & Easton 1972).

Distribution. The genus is widely distributed in the Oriental region, from Japan through to the Indo-Australian archipelago, with a dozen of cosmopolitan species.

***Metaphire andamanensis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Pheretima andamanensis Michaelsen: Gates 1972: 157.

Metaphire andamanensis (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

Type locality. North Cinque Island, Andaman and Nicobar Islands union territory, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 7169, ZSIC 2823; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Myanmar record is from Aung (2014), and there are no details on taxonomic features, hence this record requires further corroboration.

***Metaphire agrestis* (Goto & Hatai, 1899)**

Perichaeta agrestis Goto & Hatai, 1899: 17.

Pheretima agrestis (Goto & Hatai): Michaelsen 1900a: 313.

Amyntas agrestis (Goto & Hatai): Beddard 1900a: 637.

Amyntas agrestis (Goto & Hatai): Sims & Easton 1972: 235.

Metaphire agrestis (Goto & Hatai): Han *et al.* 2026: 241.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a) and Han *et al.* (2026).

Type locality. From Okayama-ken, Saitama-ken and Ibaraki-ken, Japan (Blakemore 2012a); **Type depository.** unknown (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** India, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** A native of four main islands of Japan and the Korean Peninsula (Reynolds 2022); Americas: Canada, USA; Asia: China, Japan, Korea; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Metaphire anomala* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Pheretima anomala Michaelsen, 1907: 167.

Metaphire anomala anomala (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 237.

For further synonyms see Gates (1972) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Botanical gardens, Sibpur (Shibpur) near Kolkata, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** MNHU 4273 (= ZMB Verm. 4273) (4 syntypes, dried specimen) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989), ZMUH V 185; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Asia: Cambodia, China, Laos, Thailand, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Metaphire bahli* (Gates, 1945)**

Pheretima bahli Gates, 1945e: 85.

Pheretima saigonensis Omodeo, 1957: 327.

Metaphire bahli (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Metaphire saigonensis (Omodeo): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Type locality. Colombo, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Probably lost (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Afghanistan, India, Sri Lanka; **Else**

where. Asia: Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Myanmar, Philippines, Thailand, Vietnam; Oceania: Australia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Metaphire bipora* (Beddard, 1900)**

Amyntas biporus Beddard, 1900b: 908.

Pheretima gemella Gates, 1931: 379.

Metaphire bipora (Beddard): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

For further synonyms see Gates (1972) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Malay Peninsula, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:15–6 (dried specimens), UZMC, BM. (= BMNH) 1969.2.1/5 (Sims & Easton 1972), see Blakemore (2012a) for more details; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Malaysia, Thailand, Singapore; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

***Metaphire birmanica* (Rosa, 1888)**

Perichaeta birmanica Rosa, 1888: 164.

Amyntas birmanicus (Rosa): Beddard 1900a: 637.

Pheretima birmanica (Rosa): Michaelsen 1900a: 255.

Metaphire birmanica (Rosa): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

Type locality. Bhamo, Myanmar; **Type depository.** MGDG 44041, MNHU 2274 (= ZMB Verm. 2274) 1 Syntype (Hartwich & Kilius 1989); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Laos, Thailand, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Metaphire californica* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Pheretima californica (part) Kinberg, 1867: 102.

Metaphire californica (Kinberg): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Sausalita (Sausalito) Bay, California, United States of America; **Type depository.** NHRS 160; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Ascension Island (Britain), Canary Islands (Spain), Egypt, Madeira (Portugal), Reunion Island (France), South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Barbados, Brazil, Costa

Rica, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Peru, USA, Venezuela; Asia: China, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Lebanon, Malaysia, Taiwan, Turkey, Vietnam; Europe: Azores Island (Portugal), Denmark, Greece; Oceania: Australia, Cook Islands (New Zealand), Easter Island (Chile), Hawaii Islands (USA), Marquesas Islands (France), New Guinea? Samoa, Tonga; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Probably indigenous to China or Japan (Blakemore 2012a).

***Metaphire churachandpurensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Metaphire churachandpurensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025c: 174.

Type locality. Churachandpur, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025c); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/23 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDN-272016018, DHSGV-ZDN-272016019, DHSGV-ZDN-272016020 (Paratypes) (Tiwari et al. 2025c); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Metaphire harrietensis* (Stephenson, 1925)**

Pheretima harrietensis Stephenson, 1925b: 59.

Metaphire harrietensis (Stephenson): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

Type locality. Mount Harriet (Mount Manipur National Park), Andaman and Nicobar Islands union territory, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1222; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Metaphire houletti* (Perrier, 1872)**

Perichaeta houletti Perrier, 1872: 99.

Megascolex houletii (Perrier): Vaillant 1889: 75.

Perichaeta crescentica Fedarb, 1898b: 447.

Amyntas kelantanensis Beddard, 1900b: 902.

Pheretima wimberleyana Stephenson, 1925b: 62.

Pheretima campanulata var. *penetralis* Gates, 1931: 435.

Pheretima campanulata var. *meridiana* Gates, 1932: 457.

Metaphire houlleti houlleti (Perrier): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Calcutta (Kolkata), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Comoros, Madagascar, Sierra Leone; Americas: Bahamas, Belize, Cuba, El Salvador, French Guiana, Guadeloupe (France), Mexico, Nicaragua, USA; Asia: Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Martinique Island (France), Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam; Europe: France; Oceania: Australia, Fiji, Papua New Guinea; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Indigenous to Myanmar and South-east Asia (Blakemore 2012a).

Metaphire inclara (Gates, 1932)

Pheretima inclara Gates, 1932: 439.

Pheretima porrecta Gates, 1932: 444.

Metaphire inclara (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Type locality. Peng Sai, Myanmar (Gates 1972); **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Myanmar; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

Remark. Hasan *et al.* (2024) reported it from Arunachal Pradesh of India without any locality name and the figures provided with are not of quality to distinguish the species.

Metaphire manipurensis Tiwari & Yadav, 2025

Metaphire manipurensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari *et al.*, 2025c: 169.

Type locality. Lamdeng Makhaleikai Forest Range, Manipur State, India (Tiwari *et al.* 2025c); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/20 (Holotype), DHSGV-ZDN-272016015, DHSGV-ZDN-272016016, DHSGV-ZDN-272016017 (Paratypes) (Tiwari *et al.* 2025c); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Metaphire peguana (Rosa, 1890)

Perichaeta peguana Rosa, 1890b: 113

Amyntas peguanus (Rosa): Michaelsen, 1899b: 7

Metaphire peguana (Rosa): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Burma (Myanmar); **Type depository.** MGDG 44037; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Americas: French Guiana; Asia: Cambodia, Indonesia, Japan, Laos, Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam; Oceania: Australia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine, to South Asian region.

Metaphire planata (Gates, 1926)

Pheretima planata Gates, 1926b: 411.

Metaphire planata (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Type locality. Rangoon (Yangon), Myanmar; **Type depository.** USNM 19312, BMNH 1928: 4:2:1, ZSIC 3084; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Asia: Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Original homeland unknown (Blakemore 2012a).

Metaphire posthuma (Vaillant, 1868)

Perichaeta posthuma Vaillant, 1868: 228.

Megascolex posthumus (Vaillant): Vaillant 1889: 72.

Pheretima posthuma (Vaillant): Michaelsen 1900a: 295.

Pheretima incerta Beddard, 1912: 197.

Metaphire posthuma (Vaillant): Sims & Easton 1972: 239

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Java, Indonesia; **Type depository.** MNHN 656-71; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Myanmar, Pakistan; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Egypt; Americas: Argentina, Bahamas, Santa Cruz Island (USA), USA; Asia: China, Christmas Island (Australia), Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam; Europe: England, France; Oceania: Tinian Islands (USA), Vanuatu; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. According to Gates (1972) its original home is probably Southeast Asia, comprising Thailand and the states formerly in French Indo-China.

***Metaphire quadrigemina* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima quadrigemina Gates, 1932: 486.
Metaphire quadrigemina (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

Type locality. Victoria Point (Kawthaung), Tanintharyi Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Metaphire scitula* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima scitula Gates, 1936: 457.
Metaphire scitula (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.

Type locality. Port Blair, Andaman and Nicobar Islands union territory, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3308; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Myanmar, Vietnam; **Status.** Sub-endemic? **Remark.** Introduced to Vietnam? For more details, see Nguyen *et al.* (2016).

***Metaphire thabiensis* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Metaphire thabiensis Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari *et al.*, 2025c: 178.

Type locality. Yangoupokpi-Lokchao Wildlife Sanctuary, Manipur State, India (Tiwari *et al.* 2025c); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/7 (Holotype) (Tiwari *et al.* 2025c); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Metaphire umbraticola* (Gates, 1932)**

Pheretima umbraticola Gates, 1932: 484.
Metaphire umbraticola (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 239.

Type locality. Kawkariak, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.**

Bangladesh, Myanmar; Status. Endemic, probably introduced to Bangladesh.

***Metaphire virgo* (Beddard, 1932)**

Amyntas virgo Beddard, 1900b: 895.
Pheretima mamillana Gates, 1931: 400.
Pheretima virgo Gates 1972: 222.
Metaphire virgo (Beddard): Sims & Easton 1972: 238.
For further synonyms see Gates (1972) and Blakemore (2007a).

Type locality. Tale, Songkhala Sytate, Thailand; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:197, BMNH 1924: 3:1:211–3 UZMC; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Malaysia, Thailand; **Status.** Sub-endemic.

Genus *Nellogaster* Gates, 1938

Nellogaster Gates, 1938b: 427.

Type species. *Woodwardiella bahli* Stephenson, 1925.

Distribution. Sri Lanka (Gates 1938b).

***Nellogaster bahli* (Stephenson, 1925)**

Woodwardiella bahli Stephenson, 1925a: 888.
Nellogaster bahli (Stephenson): Gates 1938b: 428.
Notoscolex bahli (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 43.

Type locality. Ceylon University College - Colombo, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:2:23:379-85, ZSIC 1207; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Nelloscolex* Gates, 1939

Nelloscolex Gates, 1939b: 37.

Type species. *Woodwardia burkilli* Michaelsen, 1907.

Distribution. India (mainly Khasi Hills of Meghalaya and Tripura) and Myanmar.

***Nelloscolex burkilli* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Woodwardia burkilli Michaelsen, 1907: 152.
Nelloscolex burkilli (Michaelsen): Gates 1939b: 38.

Type locality. Buthidaung, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2952, ZMUH V 7166; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Nelloscolex ditheca* Ahmed & Julka, 2026**

Nelloscolex ditheca Ahmed & Julka in Ahmed et al. 2026a: 885.

Type locality. Jowai, Meghalaya State, India (Shakoor et al. 2026a); **Type depository.** ZSI-GNC-An8515/2 (Holotype), ZSI-GNC-An8516/2 (7 Paratypes) (Shakoor et al. 2026a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Nelloscolex strigosus* Gates, 1939**

Nelloscolex strigosus Gates, 1939: 40.

Type locality. Dumpep, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC3588; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Notoscolex* Fletcher, 1886

Notoscolex Fletcher, 1886a: 546.

Type species. *Notoscolex camdenensis* Fletcher, 1886.

Distribution. Primarily an Australian genus with representatives in Sri Lanka and southern India as well as New Zealand.

***Notoscolex ceylanensis* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Cryptodrilus ceylanensis Michaelsen, 1897a: 183.
Notoscolex ceylanensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 194.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** RNHL 1678, BMNH 1903:4:28:1, ZMB Verm. 7450 (1 Cotype; dried specimen) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex crassicystis* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Cryptodrilus crassicystis Michaelsen, 1897a: 194.
Notoscolex crassicystis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 195.

Type locality. Nuwara Eliya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex dambullaensis* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Cryptodrilus dambullaensis Michaelsen, 1897a: 181.
Notoscolex dambullaensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 196.

Type locality. Dambulla, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4635 (Cs. Csuzdi, in litt. 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex decipiens* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Cryptodrilus decipiens Michaelsen, 1897a: 197.
Notoscolex decipiens (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 191.

Type locality. Peradeniya? Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** MZUT 145, MNHU 7405 (= ZMB Verm. 7405, Cotype, dried specimen) (Harwich & Kiliyas 1989); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex gravelyi* Stephenson, 1916**

Notoscolex gravelyi Stephenson, 1916: 325.

Type locality. ady Blake's Drive - Kandy, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6569; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex hakgallanus* Gates, 1941**

Notoscolex hakgallanus Gates, 1941a: 43.

Type locality. Hakgalla (Hakgala), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Notoscolex hastatus* (Stephenson, 1915)**

Megascolides hastatus Stephenson, 1915: 63.

Woodwardia hastata (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 186.

Notoscolex hastatus (Stephenson): Gates 1960: 240.

Type locality. Parambikulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:5-25:81-3, ZSIC 6603; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex jacksoni* (Beddard, 1890)**

Deodrilus jacksoni Beddard, 1890b: 479.

Cryptodrilus jacksoni (Beddard): Michaelsen 1897a: 190.

Notoscolex jacksoni (Beddard): Michaelsen 1900a: 196.

Type locality. Ceylon (Sri Lanka); **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex kayankulamensis* (Aiyer 1929)**

Woodwardiella kayankulamensis Aiyer, 1929: 53.

Notoscolex kayankulamensis (Aiyer): Gates 1960: 240.

Type locality. Kayankulam (Kayamkulam), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1513; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex kraepelini* (Michaelsen, 1904)**

Trinephrus kraepelini Michaelsen, 1904: 128.

Notoscolex kraepelini (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 211.

Type locality. Between Matale and Anuradhapura, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 6475; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex lautus* Gates, 1945**

Notoscolex lautus Gates, 1945e: 71.

Type locality. Varigama Kanda, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Notoscolex minimus* Aiyer, 1929**

Notoscolex minimus Aiyer, 1929: 60.

Type locality. Peermade (Peerumedu), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1517; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex peermadensis* Aiyer, 1929**

Notoscolex peermadensis Aiyer, 1929: 58.

Type locality. Peermade (Peerumedu), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1516, BMNH 1933:2:17:14-7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex plenus* Gates, 1945**

Notoscolex plenus Gates, 1945e: 73.

Type locality. Varigama Kanda, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Notoscolex ponmudianus* Michaelsen, 1913**

Notoscolex ponmudianus var. *typicus* Michaelsen, 1913a: 79.

Type locality. Ponmudi, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 8093; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic; **Remark.** Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex sarasinorum* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Cryptodrilus sarasinorum Michaelsen, 1897a: 177.
Notoscolex sarasinorum (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 192.
Woodwardia sarasinorum (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 188
Woodwardiella sarasinorum (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 50.

Type locality. Peradeniya? Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4665 (6 Syntypes) (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Notoscolex scutarius* Michaelsen, 1907**

Notoscolex scutarius Michaelsen, 1907: 153.

Type locality. Vilpatti, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** MNHU 4238, ZMUH V 7145; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex tenmalai tenmalai* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Megascolides tenmalai Michaelsen, 1910a: 55.
Notoscolex ponmudianus var. *nanus* Michaelsen, 1913a: 83.
Notoscolex tenmalai (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1916: 50.
Notoscolex tenmalai (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 219.
Notoscolex tenmalai tenmalai (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 44.

Type locality. Tenmalai (Thenmala), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 4159, ZMUH V3611 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex tenmalai ghatensis* Aiyer, 1929**

Notoscolex tenmalai var. *ghatensis* Aiyer, 1929: 56
Notoscolex tenmalai ghatensis (Aiyer): Blakemore 2007a: 44.

Type locality. Tenmalai (Thenmala), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Notoscolex tenmalai karakulamensis* (Stephenson, 1916)**

Megascolides tenmalai var. *karakulamensis* Stephenson, 1916: 311.
Notoscolex tenmalai var. *karakulamensis* (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 219.
Notoscolex tenmalai karakulamensis (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 44.

Type locality. Karakulam, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 237, BMNH 1933:5:25:77-9; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Notoscolex termiticola* Michaelsen, 1910**

Notoscolex termiticola Michaelsen, 1910a: 63.

Type locality. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 3684 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description

***Notoscolex travancorensis* Aiyer, 1929**

Notoscolex travancorensis Aiyer, 1929: 59.

Type locality. Peermade (Peerumedu), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1515 (182); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Notoscolex trincomaliensis* (Michaelsen, 1897)**

Cryptodrilus trincomaliensis Michaelsen, 1897a: 188.

Notoscolex trincomaliensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1900a: 190.

Type locality. Trincomali (Trincomalee), Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZMUH V 4636 (Cs. Csuzdi *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Notoscolex uzeli (Michaelsen, 1903)

Plutellus uzeli Michaelsen, 1903b: 4.
Woodwardia uzeli (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1910a: 57.
Notoscolex uzeli (Michaelsen): Gates 1960: 240.
Woodwardiella uzeli (Michaelsen): Blakemore 2007a: 50.

Type locality. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Perionyx* Perrier, 1872

Perionyx Perrier, 1872: 126.

Type species. *Perionyx excavatus* Perrier, 1872.

Distribution. Mainly endemic to South Asia, especially in India (from Shimla Hills in the Western Himalaya through north east India, also in peninsular India), Sri Lanka and also Myanmar and Malaysia (Sunda). Four species have a cosmopolitan distribution (Gates 1972; Blakemore 2012a).

Perionyx alatus Stephenson, 1920

Perionyx alatus Stephenson, 1920: 212.

Type locality. Sitong Ridge in Darjeeling Hills, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 272, BMNH 1933:5:25:436; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Perionyx annandalei (Michaelsen, 1907)

Perionychella annandalei Michaelsen, 1907: 154.
Perionyx annandalei (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1910a: 61 (part).

Type locality. Kurseong, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2914; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Perionyx annulatus Stephenson, 1914

Perionyx annulatus Stephenson, 1914b: 386.

Type locality. South of Yembung, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Perionyx arboricola Rosa, 1890

Perionyx arboricola Rosa, 1890b: 119.
Perionyx arboricola: Gates 1972: 141.
Planapheretima arboricola (Part) (Gates): Easton 1979: 76.
Planapheretima arboricola (Part) (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.
Perionyx arboricola Rosa: Jirapatrasilp 2024: 216.

Type locality. Cobapo Village in the Carin (Karen) Mountain, Myanmar; **Type depository.** MGDG 44017 (Holotype) (Easton 1979, Jirapatrasilp 2024); MNHU 2270 (= ZMB Verm. 2270) (Hartwich & Kiliyas 1989) (Paratype, as per Easton 1979); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Until recently it was erroneously synonymised with *Planapheretima arboricola* (Gates, 1936) (see Nguyen *et al.* 2014, 2016). Mubeen & Hatti (2022) recorded this species from India but this record lacked any description of the species and comments on its position in *Perionyx*. Latter, following Mubeen & Hatti (2022), without providing any explanations Narayanan *et al.* (2023a: 218) also retained it in *Perionyx*. However, recently Jirapatrasilp (2024; p 216) stated that, due to various key features *Perionyx arboricola* Rosa, 1890 is distinct from *Planapheretima arboricola* (Gates, 1936) and hence a valid species. Easton (1979) examined the

MGDG syntype and stated that the intestine was poorly preserved (lacking the anterior intestine and most of oesophagus). According to Easton (1979) and Balkemore (2006a), paratype (MNHU 2270) is a juvenile of uncertain identity.

***Perionyx bainii* Stephenson, 1915**

Perionyx bainii Stephenson, 1915: 72.

Type locality. Simla (Shimla), Himachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 312, BMNH 1933:5:24:438; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx barotensis* Julka & Paliwal, 1993**

Perionyx barotensis Julka & Paliwal, 1993: 461.

Type locality. Barot, Himachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An786 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An787 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx browantlerus* Tiwari & Yadav, 2025**

Perionyx browantlerus Tiwari & Yadav in Tiwari et al., 2025d: 157.

Type locality. Shirui Kashong (Peak) in Shiroi National Park, Manipur State, India (Tiwari et al. 2025d); **Type depository.** ZSI CZRC T/17 (Holotype) (Tiwari et al. 2025d); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx ceylanensis* Michaelsen, 1903**

Perionyx ceylanensis Michaelsen, 1903b: 6.

Type locality. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx crassiseptatus* Stephenson, 1925**

Perionyx crassiseptatus Stephenson, 1925b: 65.

Type locality. Chalakudi (Chalakudy), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India, Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx daflaensis* Julka, 1981**

Perionyx daflaensis Julka, 1981: 18.

Type locality. Kolang, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An129 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An130 to An132 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx daminensis* Julka, 1981**

Perionyx daminensis Julka, 1981: 20.

Type locality. Damin (28.0524°N, 93.3237°E), Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An133 (Holotype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx depressus* Stephenson, 1914**

Perionyx depressus Stephenson, 1914b: 394.

Perionyx aborensis Stephenson, 1914b: 392.

Perionyx depressus (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 328.

Type locality. Rotung (Rottung), Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1925:5:12:76, ZSIC 5389-93, 5402-9, 5414-8; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx ditheca* Stephenson, 1931**

Perionyx ditheca Stephenson, 1931: 186.

Perionyx ditheca: Gates 1972: 141.

Type locality. Thandaung, Kyain State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:2:23:453; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Known only from the original account of the syntypes (Gates 1972).

***Perionyx excavatus* Perrier, 1872**

Perionyx excavatus Perrier, 1872: 126.

Perionyx gruenewaldi Michaelsen, 1891a: 33.

Perionyx parvulus Stephenson, 1916: 321.

Perionyx fulvus Stephenson, 1916: 322.

For full list of synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Saigon (Ho Chi Minh City), Vietnam; **Type depository.** MNHN; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Comoros, Madagascar, Reunion (France), South Africa; Americas: Canada, Cuba, Dominica, Guadeloupe Island (France), Martinique Island (France), Mexico, USA; Asia: Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam; Europe: Denmark, England; Oceania: Australia, Cook Islands (New Zealand), Fiji, Hawaii (USA), Samoa, New Caledonia, New Zealand; **Status.** Native peregrine.

Remarks. Attained worldwide distribution, original home of this species is believed to be in the Himalaya (Gates 1972). According to Gates (1972), no other species of earthworm is presently known to live in so many different kinds of climate.

***Perionyx festivus* Gates, 1945**

Perionyx festvius Gates, 1945b: 227.

Type locality. Jubbulpore (Jabalpur), Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Reamark. Known only from the original description.

***Perionyx fossus* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx fossus Stephenson, 1920: 214.

Type locality. Shillong, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 248, BMNH 1933:5:25:446; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx foveatus* Stephenson, 1914**

Perionyx foveatus Stephenson, 1914b: 396.

Type locality. Renging, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5413, 5379, 5445-7, 5431; **Distribution.** India, Nepal; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx gravelyi* Stephenson, 1917**

Perionyx gravelyi Stephenson, 1917: 378.

Type locality. Pashok (Peshok), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 79; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx heterochaetus* Stephenson, 1917**

Perionyx aborensis var. *heterochaetus* Stephenson, 1917: 379.

Perionyx heterochaetus Stephenson: Paliwal 2013: 96.

Type locality. Pashok (Peshok), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 138; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx himalayanus* Michaelsen, 1907**

Perionyx himalayanus Michaelsen, 1907: 158.

Type locality. Sandakphu West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2881; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx horai* Stephenson, 1924**

Perionyx horai Stephenson, 1924b: 342.

Type locality. Cantonment Hill in Cherrapunji, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 1133, BMNH 1925:5:12:123; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx inornatus* Stephenson, 1916**

Perionyx inornatus Stephenson, 1916: 320.

Type locality. Sandakphu, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6554, BMNH 1933:5:25:452; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx jorpokriensis* Julka, 1975**

Perionyx jorpokriensis Julka, 1975: 21.

Type locality. Jorpokri (Jore Pokhri), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An207/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An208/1, 209/1, 210/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx kempii* Stephenson, 1914**

Perionyx kempii Stephenson, 1914b: 389.

Type locality. Kobo, Assam State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6064, BMNH 1925:5:12:70; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx koboensis* Stephenson, 1914**

Perionyx koboensis Stephenson, 1914b: 391.

Type locality. Kobo, Assam State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1912:5:12:110; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx macintoshii* Beddard, 1883**

Perionyx M'Intoshii Beddard, 1883: 217.
Perionyx macintoshii (Beddard): Beddard 1886b: 309.
? *Lampito dubius* (Beddard): Stephenson, 1916: 315.
? *Megascolex dubius* (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 240.
Perionyx m'intoshi Beddard: Gates 1952: 3.
Perionyx macintoshii Beddard: Gates 1972: 144.
For complete synonyms see Gates (1972).

Type locality. Akhyab, Myanmar; **Type depository.** None (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Nepal; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx manebhanjangensis* Ahmed & Julka, 2026**

Perionyx manebhanjangensis Ahmed & Julka in Ahmed et al., 2026b: 373.

Type locality. Mane Bhajang, West Bengal State, India (Shakoor et al. 2026); **Type depository.** ZSI-GNC-An8454/2 (Holotype), ZSI-GNC-An8455/2 (102 Paratypes) (Shakoor et al. 2026b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx millardi* Stephenson, 1915**

Perionyx millardi Stephenson, 1915: 74.
Perionyx igatpuriensis Stephenson, 1920: 220.

Type locality. Malabar Hill in Bombay (Mumbai), Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1933:5:25:457–8; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx minimus* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx minimus Stephenson, 1920: 219.

Type locality. Belgaum (Belagavi), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 250, BMNH 1925:5:12:33; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx modestus* Stephenson, 1922**

Perionyx modestus Stephenson, 1922a: 435.

Type locality. Cherrapunji, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 690, BMNH 1925:5:12:32; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx montanus* Gates, 1954**

Perionyx montanus Gates, 1954: 433.
Perionyx montanus: Gates 1972: 145.

Type locality. Mount Kambaiti, Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** NHRS 213; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx mysorensis* Stephenson, 1921**

Perionyx mysorensis Stephenson, 1921a: 762.

Type locality. Shemoga (Shivamogga), Karnataka, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 578, BMNH 1933:5:25:1341–2; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx nainianus* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Perionychella nainiana Michaelsen, 1907: 155.

Perionyx nainianus (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 346.

Type locality. Nainital, Uttarakhand State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2916, ZMUH 7150; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx nanus* Stephenson, 1917**

Perionyx nanus Stephenson, 1917: 381.

Type locality. Pashok (Peshok), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 78; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx nemoralis* Gates, 1954**

Perionyx nemoralis Gates, 1954: 435.

Perionyx nemoralis: Gates 1972: 146.

Type locality. Mount Kambaiti, Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** NHRS 212 (Holotype); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Known only from a partly macerated anterior portion (Gates 1972).

***Perionyx pallidus* Stephenson, 1917**

Perionyx pallidus Stephenson, 1917: 376.

Type locality. Kalimpong, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 89, BMNH 1925:5:12:36; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx pincernus* Stephenson, 1916**

Perionyx pincerna Stephenson, 1916: 319.

Perionyx pincernus Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 47.

Type locality. Near Ghoom (Ghum), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 7205; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx pokhrianus pokhrianus* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx pokhrianus Stephenson, 1920: 208.

Perionyx pokhrianus pokhrianus (Stephenson): Blakemore 2007a: 47.

Type locality. Jorpokri (Jore Pokhri), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 246; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx pokhrianus affinis* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx pokhrianus var. *affinis* Stephenson, 1920: 210.

Perionyx pokhrianus affinis (Stephenson): Paliwal 2013: 99

Type locality. Sitong Ridge in Darjeeling Hills, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 252; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx polythecus* Stephenson, 1923**

Perionyx polytheca Stephenson, 1923: 351.

Perionyx polythecus Stephenson: Blakemore 2007a: 46.

Type locality. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the original description.

***Perionyx pullus* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx pullus Stephenson, 1920: 217.

Type locality. Belgaum (Belagavi), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 253; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx pulvinatus* Stephenson, 1916**

Perionyx pulvinatus Stephenson, 1916: 317.

Type locality. Near Ghoom (Ghum), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6538, BMNH 1925:5:12:7; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx rahuli* Hasan, Ghosh & Mandal, 2019**

Perionyx rahuli Hasan, Ghosh & Mandal, 2019: 14.

Type locality. Jorpokhri in Darjeeling Hills, West Bengal State, India (Hasan et al. 2019); **Type depository.** ZSIC An5725/1 (Hasan et al. 2019); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. *Taxon inquirendum.* Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx rimatus* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx rimatus Stephenson, 1920: 206.

Type locality. Jor Pokhri (Jorpokhri), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 275; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx rufulus* Gates, 1945**

Perionyx rufulus Gates, 1945a: 74.

Type locality. Khezhabama, Nagaland State, India (Gates 1945a); **Type depository.** Type has

been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx saltans* Bourne, 1886**

Perionyx saltans Bourne, 1886: 669.

Type locality. Ootacamund (Udhagamandalam or Ooty), India. **Type depository.** BMNH 1933.5.25.1317-1318; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx sansibaricus* Michaelsen, 1891**

Perionyx sansibaricus Michaelsen, 1891b: 4.

Type locality. Zanzibar, Tanzania; **Type depository.** ZMH V 366; **Distribution.** India; E. Africa: Zanzibar Island (Tanzania); Asia: China, Philippines, Thailand (Stephenson 1923; Blake-more 2012a; Ahmed et al. 2020); **Status.** Native peregrine.

Remark. Being a composting worm it is widely distributed by the vermicomposting industries worldwide.

***Perionyx setnai* Stephenson, 1931**

Perionyx setnai Stephenson, 1931b: 63.

Type locality. Darjeeling, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx shyamasreetus* Ghosh, Hasan & Mandal, 2018**

Perionyx shyamasreetus Ghosh, Hasan & Mandal, 2018: 158.

Perionyx shyamasreei Ghosh, Hasan & Mandal: Hasan et al. 2019: 15 (lapsus).

Type locality. ?, Bhubaneswar district, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI An5724/1 (Ghosh et al. 2018); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. *Taxon inquirendum.*

***Perionyx shillongensis* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx shillongensis Stephenson, 1920: 213.

Type locality. Shillong, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 247, BMNH 1933:5:25:466; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx sikkimensis sikkimensis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Perionychella sikkimensis Michaelsen, 1907: 156.

Perionyx sikkimensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1910a: 60 (part).

Perionyx sikkimensis sikkimensis (Michaelsen): Blake-more 2007a: 48.

Type locality. Sandakphu in Darjeeling Hills, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2915, ZMUH V 7151; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx sikkimensis michaelseni* Stephenson, 1923**

Perionyx sikkimensis (Michaelsen): Michaelsen 1910a: 60 (part).

Perionyx sikkimensis var. *michaelseni* Stephenson 1923: 359.

Perionyx sikkimensis michaelseni (Stephenson): Blake-more 2007a: 47, 48.

Type locality. Gangtok (27.3314°N, 88.6138°E), Sikkim State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx silvicola* Stephenson, 1925**

Perionyx silvicola Stephenson, 1925b: 67.

Type locality. Dhoni Forest, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Perionyx simlaensis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Perionychella simlaensis Michaelsen, 1907: 157.

Perionyx simlaensis (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 359.

Type locality. Dharmpur (Dharampur), Himachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2988, BMNH 1925:5:12:79, ZMUH V 7141 (Cs. Csuzdi, *in litt.* 2026); **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx tenuis* Gates, 1954**

Perionyx tenuis Gates, 1954: 437.

Perionyx tenuis: Gates 1972: 147.

Type locality. Mount Kambaiti, Kachin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** NHRS 214; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx turaensis* Stephenson, 1920**

Perionyx turaensis Stephenson, 1920: 216.

Type locality. Above Tura, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 177, BMNH 1925:5:12:43; **Distribution.** India; **S.** Endemic.

***Perionyx variegatus* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Perionychella variegata Michaelsen, 1907: 158.

Perionyx variegatus (Michaelsen): Stephenson 1923: 362.

Type locality. Phallut (Phalut) in Darjeeling Hills, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 2917, ZMUH V 7152; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx vidakensis* Julka, 1981**

Perionyx vidakensis Julka, 1981: 27.

Type locality. Vidak (Bidak), Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An134 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An135 to An137 (Paratypes) (Julka 1981a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Perionyx viridis* Gates, 1933**

Perionyx viridis Gates, 1933: 551.

Perionyx tenuis: Gates 1972: 148.

Type locality. Falam, Chin State, Myanmar;
Type depository. ZSIC 3073, but as per Gates (1972) types none; **Distribution.** Myanmar;
Status. Endemic.

Genus *Pheretima* Kinberg, 1867

Pheretima Kinberg, 1867: 102.

Type species. *Pheretima montana* Kinberg, 1867, subsequent designation by Michaelsen in 1907b (Sims & Easton 1972).

Distribution. The Malaysian sub-region to New Guinea with a few peregrine species.

***Pheretima darnleiensis* (Fletcher, 1886)**

Perichaeta darnleiensis Fletcher, 1886b: 966.

Perichaeta vaillantii Beddard, 1890a: 66.

Pheretima (*Pheretima*) *darnleiensis* (Fletcher): Sims & Easton 1972: 260.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Darnley Island (Erub Island) in Torres Straits, Australia; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** tropical Indo-Australasian Archipelago and islands; Asia: Brunei, Christmas Island (Australia), Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore; Oceania: Australia (Torres Strait, Darnley Island); Caroline Islands, Fiji; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Pheretima vungtauensis* Nguyen, Nguyen & Nguyen, 2018**

Pheretima vungtauensis in Nguyen et al., 2018: 252.

Pheretima vungtauensis Nguyen et al.: Tiwari et al. 2022: 1809.

Pheretima vungtauensis Nguyen et al.: Narayanan et al. 2023a: 240.

Type locality. Xa Bang commune, Vietnam;

Type depository. CTU-EW.166.h01 (Holotype), CTU-EW.166.p02 to CTU-EW.166.p07 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine? probably introduced.

Genus *Pithemera* Sims & Easton, 1972

Pithemera Sim & Easton, 1972: 202

Type species. *Perichaeta bicincta* Perrier, 1875, by original designation.

Distribution. Mainly in Pacific Isles (Fiji, New Britain, Philippines, Samoa, Solomon, Vanuatu) and Korea (Sims & Easton 1972; Blakemore 2012a; Nguyen et al. 2016).

***Pithemera bicincta* (Perrier, 1875)**

Perichaeta bicincta Perrier, 1875: 1044.

Pheretima violacea (Beddard): Michaelsen 1909: 188.

Pheretima bicincta (Perrier): Michaelsen 1935: 107.

Pithemera bicincta (Perrier): Sims & Easton 1972: 202.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Mindoro, Philippines; **Type depository.** MNHN 689-92; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Canary Islands (Spain), Grande Terre Island (France), Reunion Island (France); Americas: Argentina, Cuba, Dominica, Grenada, Guadeloupe Island (France), Mexico, St Thomas, Trinidad, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Christmas Island (Australia), Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, Taiwan, Vietnam; Europe: England, Hungary, Ireland, Denmark; Oceania: Australia, Caroline Islands, Cook Islands (New Zealand), Fiji, Hawaii (USA), Marshall Islands, Papua New Guinea, Rarotonga (New Zealand), Samoa, Vanuatu; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Genus *Planapheretima* Michaelsen, 1934

Pheretima (*Planapheretima*) Michaelsen, 1934: 17.

Planapheretima: Sims & Easton 1972: 208.

Planapheretima: Easton 1979: 64.

Type species. *Pheretima moultoni* Michaelsen, 1913, original designation.

Distribution. China (Szechuan), Indonesia (Sumatra, Borneo = Kalimantan, Celebes = Sulawesi), Myanmar, New Guinea, Vanuatu, Vietnam (Blakemore 2012a, Nguyen *et al.* 2016).

***Planapheretima arboricola* (Gates, 1936)**

Pheretima arboricola Gates, 1936: 399.
Pheretima arboricola: Gates 1972: 169.
Planapheretima arboricola (Gates): Sims & Easton 1972: 233.
Planapheretima arboricola (Part) (Gates): Easton 1979: 76.
Planapheretima arboricola (Part) (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 5.
non *Perionyx arboricola* Rosa: Jirapatrasilp 2024: 216.

Type locality. Karen Hills, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype destroyed (Jirapatrasilp 2024); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. Known only from the type locality. Until recently *Planapheretima arboricola* was erroneously synonymised with *Perionyx arboricola* Rosa, 1890. Recently it was resurrected as a valid species (for details see Jirapatrasilp 2024: 216). As per the original description (Gates 1936) this species have four pairs of spermathecal pores in intersegmental furrows 5/6–8/9 and a single genital marking in segment 18. There are records of this species from Vietnam (see, Nguyen *et al.* 2014, 2016). But Nguyen *et al.* (2014, 2016) stated that ‘*The populations in Vietnam differ from the description of Gates (1936) in having spermathecal pores paired in vi and vii, additional genital markings in vi and more setae*’. Hence the species reported as *Planapheretima arboricola* from Vietnam is a different *Planapheretima* species.

Genus *Polypheretima* Michaelsen, 1934

Pheretima (*Polypheretima*) Michaelsen, 1934: 15.
Metapheretima (Michaelsen): Sims & Easton 1972: 205, 233 (part).
Polypheretima (Michaelsen): Easton 1979: 28.

Type species. *Perichaeta stelleri* Michaelsen, 1892, by original designation (Nguyen *et al.* 2016).

Distribution. Philippines, Indonesian archipelago, Papua New Guinea, Malay Peninsula and Vietnam (Nguyen *et al.* 2016).

***Polypheretima elongata* (Perrier, 1872)**

Perichaeta elongata Perrier, 1872: 124.
Megascolex elongatus (Perrier): Vaillant 1889: 81.
Perichaeta acystis Beddard, 1895a: 423.
Amyntas elongatus (Perrier): Beddard 1900a: 650.
Pheretima elongata (Perrier): Michaelsen 1900a: 265.
Metapheretima elongata (Perrier): Sims & Easton 1972: 233.
Polypheretima elongata (Perrier): Easton 1979: 53.
For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Peru; **Type depository.** MNHN 633–44; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Comoros, Egypt, Grande Terre Island (France), Madagascar, Mauritius; Americas: Antigua, Belize, Bonaire (Netherlands), Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominica, French Guiana, Guadeloupe Island (France), Guyana, Hispaniola (Dominican Republic, Haiti), Jamaica, Martinique (France), Nicaragua, Panama, Peru, Puerto Rico, Surinam, Venezuela; Asia: Cambodia, Indonesia, Japan, Laos, Malaysia, Oman, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam; Oceania: Australia, Caroline Islands, Hawaii (USA), New Caledonia (France), Papua New Guinea, Rarotonga (New Zealand), Samoa, Tahiti; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Polypheretima taprobanae* (Beddard, 1892)**

Perichaeta taprobanae Beddard, 1892b: 163.
Amyntas taprobanae (Beddard): Beddard 1900a: 648.
Pheretima taprobanae (Beddard): Stephenson 1923: 312.
Metapheretima taprobanae (Beddard): Sims & Easton 1972: 233.
Polypheretima taprobanae (Beddard): Easton 1979: 45.
For further synonyms see Easton (1979) and Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:163-4, 1972:1:6-11 **Distribution.** India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: Madagascar, Seychelles; Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Martinique Island (France), Mexico; Asia:

Singapore, Vietnam; Europe: England; Oceania: Australia, Cook Islands (New Zealand), Fiji, Hawaii (USA), New Caledonia, Papua New Guinea; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. It possibly originated in either Southeast Asia (Easton 1979) or in Papua New Guinea (Gates 1972); but its real homeland is still unknown (Nguyen *et al.* 2016). According to Blakemore (2006a) this species is not yet known from Myanmar, and is therefore omitted from the Myanmar list.

Genus *Pontodrilus* Perrier, 1874

Pontodrilus Perrier, 1874: 1582.

Type species. *Pontodrilus marionis* Perrier, 1874 (= *Lumbricus litoralis* Grube, 1855).

Distribution. Endemic species area found at Tasmania (Australia), New Zealand, Sri Lanka, China, Thailand and Malaysia and one (*P. litoralis*) is cosmopolitan, occurs over a very wide range of sub-temperate and tropical coastal areas all over the world (Seesamut *et al.* 2018).

***Pontodrilus agnesae* Stephenson, 1915**

Pontodrilus agnesae Stephenson, 1915: 61.

Type locality. Horton Plains, Sri Lanka; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6183, 6190, BMNH 1933:5:25:63; **Distribution.** Sri Lanka; **Status.** Endemic.

***Pontodrilus litoralis* (Grube, 1855)**

Lumbricus litoralis Grube, 1855: 127.

Pontodrilus bermudensis Beddard, 1891: 96.

Cryptodrilus insularis Rosa, 1891: 387.

Pontodrilus michaelseni Eisen, 1895: 73.

Pontodrilus littoralis (Grube): Beddard 1895a: 469.

Pontodrilus laccadivensis Beddard, 1903: 374.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Villa Franca of French Riviera, France; **Type depository.** MNHU 216 (= ZMB Verm. 216, 1 dried Syntype) (Hartwich & Kilius 1989), WUMW 506; **Distribution.** India, Mal-

dives, Myanmar, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Cosmopolitan, coasts of Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Oceans, Mediterranean and Red Seas; Africa: Angola, Canary Islands (Spain), Cape Verde Islands, Congo, Djerba Island (Tunisia), Guinea-Bissau, Madagascar, Mauritania, Mauritius, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania; Americas: Bahamas, Belize, Bermuda, Brazil, British Caymans, Colombia, Galapagos Islands (Ecuador), Guadeloupe (France), Hispaniola (Dominican Republic, Haiti), Jamaica, Mexico, Mona Island (Puerto Rico), USA, Venezuela, Virgin Islands; Asia: China, Borneo, Christmas Island (Australia), Hong Kong, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Kuwait, Malaysia, Oman, Philippines, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkiye, Vietnam; Europe: France, Greece, Iceland? Italy, Monaco, Spain; Oceania: Australia, Chatham Island (New Zealand), Fanning Atoll (Kiribati), Fiji, Guam, Hawaii Island (USA), New Caledonia (France), New Guinea, Palmyra Atoll (USA), Tonga; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. Its circumtropical distribution seems unlikely due to human involvement (Gates 1972). For more details about its origin, dispersion, *etc.* refer to Blakemore (2007c).

Genus *Tonoscolex* Gates, 1933

Tonoscolex Gates, 1933: 484.

Type species. *Notoscolex birmanicus* Gates, 1927.

Distribution. India (Himalaya in the vicinity of Darjeeling to the Khasi Hills of north eastern India) and Myanmar.

***Tonoscolex birmanicus* (Gates, 1927)**

Notoscolex sp. Gates 1926: 151.

Notoscolex birmanicus Gates, 1927: 609.

Tonoscolex birmanicus (Gates): Gates 1933: 484.

Tonoscolex birmanicus (Gates): Gates 1972: 227.

Type locality. Maymyo (Pyin Oo Lwin or Pyin U Lwin), Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3117; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex conversus* (Gates, 1930)**

Notoscolex conversus Gates, 1930: 301.
Tonoscolex conversus (Gates): Gates 1972: 227.

Type locality. At or near Pantha (Panghta), Paungbyin or Mawlaik, Sagaing Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex depressus* (Gates, 1929)**

Notoscolex depressus Gates, 1929: 14.
Notoscolex choprai Stephenson, 1929: 230.
Notoscolex depressus + *N. sp. f. prima*: Gates 1932: 373.
Tonoscolex depressus (Gates): Gates 1933: 484.
Tonoscolex depressus (Gates): Gates 1972: 228.

Type locality. At or near Pantha (Panghta), Paungbyin or Mawlaik, Sagaing Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** BMNH1928:2:4:1 (Holotype) destroyed (Gates 1972), USNM 19256 (Paratypes) (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex ferinus* Gates, 1933**

Tonoscolex ferinus Gates, 1933: 487.
Megascolex ferinus (Gates): Blakemore 2006a: 11.

Type locality. Koopra (Hkapra?), Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3072; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex horai* (Stephenson, 1922)**

Megascolex horai Stephenson, 1922a: 432.
Tonoscolex horai (Stephenson): Gates 1934: 256.
Megascolex horai Stephenson: Blakemore 2006a: 11.

Type locality. Cherrapunji, Meghalaya State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 703; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex indicus* Julka, 1981**

Tonoscolex indicus Julka, 1981: 29.

Type locality. Siki, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An110 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An111 to An116 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex kabakensis* Julka, 1981**

Tonoscolex kabakensis Julka, 1981: 30.

Type locality. Kabak, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** HARC-ZSI An117 (Holotype), HARC-ZSI An118 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Tonoscolex kalimpongensis* Ahmed & Julka, 2022**

Tonoscolex kalimpongensis Ahmed & Julka in Ahmed et al., 2022: 376.

Type locality. Lava in Neora Valley National Park, West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSI GNC-An2203/1 (Holotype), ZSI GNC-An2204/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Tonoscolex lunatus* Gates, 1929**

Notoscolex lunatus Gates, 1929: 16.
Tonoscolex lunatus (Gates): Gates 1933: 490.

Type locality. Maymyo (Pyin Oo Lwin or Pyin U Lwin), Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes BMNH 1928:2:4, USNM 19262; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex michaelsoni* Julka, 1976**

Tonoscolex michaelsoni Julka, 1976a: 233.

Type locality. Wakro, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An112/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An113/1, 114/1 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex monorchis* (Stephenson, 1916)**

Megascolides oneilli var. *monorchis* Stephenson, 1916: 313.

Notoscolex oneilli var. *monorchis* (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 214.

Tonoscolex monorchis (Stephenson): Gates 1972: 230.

Type locality. Darjiling (Darjeeling) to Soom (Ghoom), West Bengal State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 6525, BMNH 1933:5:25:84-5; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex montanus* Gates, 1936**

Tonoscolex montanus Gates, 1936: 381.

Tonoscolex montanus Gates: Gates 1972: 231; Blakemore 2006a: 11.

Type locality. Maymyo (Pyin Oo Lwin or Pyin U Lwin), Mandalay Region, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Holotype lost (Gates 1972), Paratypes BMNH 1928:2:4, USNM 19262; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. *Species inquirenda* (Blakemore 2006a). Gates (1972: 230) listed *Notoscolex* sp. forma *secunda* as a synonym of *T. montanus*, and Reynolds & Cook (1976: 169) kept it as a sub-specific name. Hence as per Blakemore (2006a) *secunda* possibly gets priority under ICZN Code.

***Tonoscolex oneilli* (Stephenson, 1914)**

Megascolides oneilli Stephenson, 1914b: 377.

Notoscolex oneilli (Stephenson): Stephenson 1923: 212 (*lapsus*, part, excluding variety *monorchis* Stephenson, 1916).

Tonoscolex oneilli (Stephenson): Gates 1934: 254.

Type locality. Janakmukh, Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5159; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex parvus* Gates, 1936**

Tonoscolex parvus Gates, 1936: 386.

Tonoscolex parvus Gates: Gates 1972: 231.

Tonoscolex parvus Gates: Blakemore 2006a: 12.

Type locality. Taungyi (Taunggyi), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Types none (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. *Species inquirenda* (Blakemore 2006a). Gates (1972: 231) listed *Notoscolex* sp. f. *tertia* as a synonym of *T. parvus*, and Reynold & Cook (1976: 168) treated it as a sub-specific name. Hence as per Blakemore (2006a) *tertia* possibly competes with *parvus* for priority under ICZN Code.

***Tonoscolex pedongensis* Ahmed & Julka, 2026**

Tonoscolex pedongensis in Ahmed & Julka in Ahmed et al. 2026a: 882.

Type locality. Pedong, West Bengal State, India (Shakoor et al. 2026a); **Type depository.** ZSI-GNC-An8112/2 (Holotype), ZSI-GNC-An 8514/2 (3 Paratypes) (Shakoor et al. 2026a); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex quartus* Gates, 1932**

Notoscolex sp. f. *quarta* Gates, 1932: 374.

Tonoscolex quartus Gates: Gates 1972: 232.

Tonoscolex quartus Gates: Blakemore 2006a: 12.

Type locality. Taungyi (Taunggyi), Shan State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. *Species inquirenda* (Blakemore 2006a). Known only from the type locality.

***Tonoscolex striatus* (Stephenson, 1914)**

Notoscolex striatus Stephenson, 1914b: 380.

Notoscolex stewarti Stephenson, 1914b: 382.

Tonoscolex striatus (Stephenson): Gates 1934: 255.

Type locality. Rotung (Rottung), Arunachal Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 5410, 5384-6; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Tonoscolex triquetrus* Gates, 1932**

Notoscolex depressus? Gates 1930: 299.
Tonoscolex triquetrus Gates, 1932: 370.
Tonoscolex depressus var. *scutatus* Gates, 1933: 485.
Tonoscolex triquetrus Gates: Gates 1972: 232.

Type locality. Between Thandaung and Leiktho (Gates 1972), Kayin State, Myanmar; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3080; **Distribution.** Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Troyia* Jamieson, 1977

Troyia Jamieson, 1977b: 492.

Type species. *Toryia gundarshola* Jamieson, 1977.

Distribution. India (Palni Hills of Western Ghats in southern India).

***Troyia gundarshola* Jamieson, 1977**

Troyia gundarshola Jamieson, 1977b: 494.

Type locality. Gundar Shola, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Paris Museum AH336 (Holotype), BJ 1976.5.12 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Family OCNERODRILIDAE Beddard, 1891

Genus *Aphanascus* Stephenson, 1924

Aphanascus Stephenson, 1924b: 360.
Aphanascus Stephenson: Hernandez-García et al. 2018: 478.

Type species. *Aphanascus oryzivorus* Stephenson, 1924.

Distribution. In Palakkad district of Kerala State, Southwestern Peninsular India.

***Aphanascus oryzivorus* Stephenson, 1924**

Aphanascus oryzivorus Stephenson, 1924b: 360.
Malabararia oryzivora (Stephenson): Gates 1942: 92.

Aphanascus oryzivorus Stephenson: Hernandez-García et al. 2018: 478.

Type locality. Anaikomban paddy field in Kollengode, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1925:5:12:116; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

Genus *Curgiona* Gates, 1941

Curgia Michaelsen, 1922: 59.
Curgiona Gates, 1941b: 497. nom nov pro *Curgia* Michaelsen, 1922 non *Curgia* Walker, 1860.

Type species. *Curgia narayani* Michaelsen, 1922.

Distribution. The home range is unknown.

***Curgiona narayani* (Michaelsen, 1922)**

Curgia narayani Michaelsen, 1922: 59.
Curgiona narayani (Michaelsen): Gates 1941b: 497.

Type locality. Madapur (Madapura), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZMUH 9157; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Deccania* Gates, 1949

Deccania Gates, 1949a: 279.

Type species. *Deccania alba* Gates, 1949.

Distribution. Central India.

***Deccania alba* Gates, 1949**

Deccania alba Gates, 1949: 279.

Type locality. Baraila near Jubbulpore (Jabalpur), Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3645; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Eukerria* Michaelsen, 1935

Kerria Beddard, 1892c: 355.

Eukerria Michaelsen, 1935: 102. nom nov. pro *Kerria* Beddard, 1892 non *Kerria* Targioni-Tozzetti, 1884.

Type species. *Kerria halophila* Beddard, 1892.

Distribution. In subtropical South America and adjacent tropical regions with two circummundane species.

***Eukerria kuekenthali* (Michaelsen, 1908)**

Kerria kuekenthali Michaelsen, 1908: 24.
Kerria selangorensis Stephenson, 1931a: 279.
Eukerria peguana Gates, 1942: 67.
Eukerria kuekenthali (Michaelsen): Christoffersen 2008: 100.

Type locality. St. Thomas Island (18.3381°N, 64.8941°W), West Indies; **Type depository.** Berlin and Hamburg Museums, transferred to Wrocław (WUMW): 515 (Blakemore 2012a); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Original home of this species is supposed to be South America (Gates 1972); Americas: Belize, Brazil, Puerto Rico, St. Thomas; Asia: Christmas Island (Australia), Malay Peninsula, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

***Eukerria saltensis* (Beddard, 1895)**

Kerria saltensis Beddard, 1895b: 225.
Eukerria saltensis (Beddard): Michaelsen 1935: 40; Gates 1942: 73; Ahmed *et al.* 2026: 381.
For synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Salto, Valparaiso, Chile (Gates 1942); **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:928, USNM 21025; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** South America and widely distributed in the world (Blakemore 2012a); Africa: South Africa; Americas: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Costa Rica, Cuba, USA; Asia: Philippines, Taiwan, Vietnam; Europe: Italy, Spain; Oceania: Australia, New Caledonia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Genus *Gordiodrilus* Beddard, 1892

Gordiodrilus Beddard, 1892a: 93.

Type species. *Gordiodrilus elegans* Beddard, 1892.

Distribution. Tropical Africa, and transported to Asia, Australia, Caribbean and other non-tropical portions of Africa (Gates 1972; Blakemore 2012a).

***Gordiodrilus elegans* Beddard, 1892**

Gordiodrilus elegans Beddard, 1892a: 84.
Gordiodrilus travancorensis Michaelsen, 1910a: 98.
Gordiodrilus paski Stephenson, 1928: 1.
Gordiodrilus peguanus Gates, 1942: 85.
Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Lagos, Nigeria; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904:10:5:607, 1904:10:20:439-474, 839,974-9; **Distribution.** Bangladesh, India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Original homeland may be in tropical Africa (Gates 1972); Africa: East and West Africa, Egypt, Ethiopia, Madagascar, São Tomé, Sudan, Zanzibar (Tanzania); Americas: Bonaco Island (Caribbean), Brazil, Dominica? Puerto Rico; Asia: Vietnam; Europe: England; Oceania: Australia; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Genus *Malabaria* Stephenson, 1924

Malabaria Stephenson, 1924b: 356.
Filodrilus Chen, 1938: 422.

Type species. *Malabaria paludicola* Stephenson, 1924.

Distribution. Mainly in Peninsular India, Myanmar, Vietnam, and Hainan (at least the latter by introduction?) (Gates 1972; Blakemore 2012a).

***Malabaria biprostata* Aiyer, 1929**

Malabaria biprostata Aiyer, 1929: 73.

Type locality. Kumili (Kumily), Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1948:6:29:36-8, ZSIC 1523; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Malabaria levis* (Chen, 1938)**

Friodrilus levis Chen, 1938: 423.

Malabaria levis? (Chen): Gates 1942: 92.
Malabaria levis (Chen): Gates 1961b: 57.

Type locality. Po-peng, Hainan, China; **Type depository.** Probably lost (Gates 1972); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Elsewhere.** Asia: China, Vietnam; **Status.** Native peregrine; **Remark.** Its original home appears to be in the southern Indian Peninsula (Julka & Paliwal 1995).

***Malabaria paludicola* Stephenson, 1924**

Malabaria paludicola Stephenson, 1924b: 356.

Type locality. Kollengode, Kerala State, India; **Type depository.** BMNH 1925:5:12:47; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality.

***Malabaria sulcata* Gates, 1945**

Malabaria sulcata Gates, 1945b: 218.

Type locality. Manikpur junction, Uttar Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC 3627; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Genus *Nematogenia* Eisen, 1900

Ocnerodrilus (*Nematogenia*) Eisen, 1900: 112.
Nematogenia Michaelsen, 1900a: 376.

Type species. *Pygmaeodrilus lacuum* Bedard, 1893b.

Distribution. Gates (1957) Stated that 'the genus is known to be represented elsewhere only by a peregrine species formerly thought to be African, but now apparently of American origin'.

***Nematogenia panamaensis* (Eisen, 1900)**

Ocnerodrilus (*Nematogenia*) *lacuum* var. *panamaensis* Eisen, 1900: 127.

Nematogenia josephina Cognetti, 1904: 3.

Nematogenia panamaensis (Eisen): Michaelsen 1900a: 376.

Further synonyms in Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Panama; **Type depository.** ?.
Distribution. India, Myanmar? Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Africa: East Africa; Cameroon, Congo, Fernando Po (Equatorial Guinea), Liberia, Nigeria, Sao Tome Island; Americas: Bahamas, Brazil, Costa Rica, Jamaica, Martinique Island (France), Nicaragua, Panama, Venezuela; Asia: Philippines, Sri Lanka, Vietnam; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remark. Gates (1972) included this species in his Myanmar list without any specific collection locations or details.

Genus *Ocnerodrilus* Eisen, 1878

Ocnerodrilus Eisen, 1878: 1.

Type species. *Ocnerodrilus occidentalis* Eisen, 1878.

Distribution. Tropical and adjacent subtropical portions of the Africa and America.

***Ocnerodrilus occidentalis* Eisen, 1878**

Ocnerodrilus occidentalis Eisen, 1878:10.

Ocnerodrilus tenellulus Gates, 1945b: 223.

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Fresno County, California State, United States of America; **Type depository.** BMNH 1904: 10:5:231-6, MNHU 2363 (= ZMB Verm. 2363, dried specimen) (Hartwich & Kiliass 1989); **Distribution.** India, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** Pan-tropical, less frequently found in temperate regions; original home is thought to be in Central or South America (Blakemore 2012a); Africa: Cape Verde Islands, Canary Islands (Spain), Great Comoro, South Africa, Zimbabwe; Americas: Cuba, Hispaniola (Dominican Republic), Martinique Island (France), Mexico, Puerto Rico, St Martin Island (France), St Thomas Island, USA; Asia: Central Asian Basin, China, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Korea, Lebanon, Palestine, Philippines, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Vietnam; Europe: Denmark, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy; Oceania: Australia, Solomon, Vanuatu; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Genus *Thatonia* Gates, 1942

Thatonia Gates, 1942: 101.

Type species. *Thatonia gracilis* Gates, 1942.

Distribution. India (north central portions of the Deccan and the Gangetic plains), Myanmar, Laos, Vietnam.

***Thatonia bolangirensis* Julka, 1976**

Thatonia bolangirensis Julka, 1976b: 326.

Type locality. Bolangir (Balangir), Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An300/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An301/1 (Paratype) (Julka 1976b); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Thatonia exilis* Gates, 1945**

Thatonia exilis Gates, 1945b: 216.

Type locality. Nowgong, Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type is currently missing/cannot be located now; **Distribution.** India; **Elsewhere.** Laos, Myanmar, Vietnam; **Status.** Native peregrine.

***Thatonia gracilis* Gates, 1942**

Thatonia gracilis Gates, 1942: 101.

Type locality. Thongwa, Myanmar; **Type depository.** None; **Distribution.** India, Myanmar; **Status.** Endemic.

***Thatonia parva* Gates, 1945**

Thatonia parva Gates, 1945b: 217.

Type locality. Satna, Madhya Pradesh State, India; **Type depository.** Type has been destroyed and/or discarded; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

***Thatonia sambalpurensis* Julka, 1976**

Thatonia sambalpurensis Julka, 1976b: 328.

Type locality. Sambalpur, Odisha State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC An302/1 (Holotype), ZSIC An303/1 (Paratype); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Family RHINODRILIDAE Benham, 1890

Genus *Pontoscolex* Schmarda, 1861

Pontoscolex Schmarda, 1861: 11.

Eurydame Kinberg, 1867: 87.

Urochaeta Perrier, 1872: 142.

For further details see James et al. (2019).

Type species. *Pontoscolex arenicola* Schmarda, 1861 (= *Lumbricus corethrurus* Müller, 1857).

Distribution. Neotropical regions, e.g. Brazil, Surinam, Guyana, Guatemala, (Panama?); except the cosmopolitan type species *Pontoscolex corethrurus*.

***Pontoscolex corethrurus* (Müller, 1857)**

Lumbricus corethrurus Müller, 1857: 113.

Pontoscolex arenicola Schmarda, 1861: 11.

Urochaeta hystrix Perrier, 1872: 142.

Pontoscolex corethrurus (Müller): Beddard 1892e: 127.

For further synonyms see Blakemore (2012a).

Type locality. Grass lawn behind the Museu de Ecologia Fritz Müller (former house of Fritz Müller) Blumenau, Santa Catarina, Brazil; **Type depository.** MZUSP 3532 (Neotype); **Distribution.** Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka; **Elsewhere.** The most widely distributed earthworm species (Gates 1972), in tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world (Taheri et al. 2018); Africa: Algeria, Cape Verde Islands, Comoros Islands, Democratic Republic of Congo, Gabon, Grande Terre Island (France), Kenya, Liberia, Madagascar, Mauritius, Nigeria, Reunion Islands (France), Sao Tome and Principe, Seychelles, South Africa, St. Helena (Britain), Tanzania; Americas: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominica, Ecuador, Falkland Islands, French Guiana, Galapagos Islands (Ecuador), Guadeloupe (France),

Guatemala, Guyana, Hispaniola (Dominican Republic, Haiti), Honduras, Jamaica, Martinique (France), Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Puerto Rico, Salvador, St. Croix (United States Virgin Islands), St. Kitts, St. Lucia, St. Thomas, St. Vincent, Surinam, USA, Venezuela; Asia: Cambodia, China, Christmas Island (Australia), Hong Kong, Indonesia, Iran, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Sumatra, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam; Europe: Azores (Portugal), England; Oceania: Australia, Cook Islands (New Zealand), Fiji, Hawaii Islands (USA), New Caledonia (France), New Hanover (Papua New Guinea), Niue, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tahiti (France), Tonga, Trinidad, Vanuatu; **Status.** Exotic peregrine.

Remarks. Pakistan is mentioned in Blakemore (2012a), but could not find any literature substantiating the record. For more details, see Narayanan et al. (2023a).

SPECIES INCERTAE SEDIS

ACANTHODRILIDAE

Genus *Diplocardia* Garman, 1888

Diplocardia Garman, 1888: 47.

Type species. *Diplocardia communis communis* Garman, 1888.

Distribution. Mexico, USA (Blakemore 2012a).

Diplocardia (?) *indica* Stephenson, 1924

Diplocardia indica Stephenson, 1924b: 353.

Diplocardia (?) *indica* Stephenson: Gates 1940a: 214.

Diplocardia (?) *indica* Stephenson: Julka 1988a: 366.

Type locality. Gorge below Chota tank in Buldana, Maharashtra State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W1148/1; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. While describing the new species *indica*, Stephenson (1924b) assigned it in the genus *Diplocardia*, which is an American genus.

But later Gates (1940a) re-examined three immature syntypes in the Indian Museum and observed that *indica* was perhaps generically distinct from *Diplocardia*. This is mainly because of its single dorsal blood vessel and ‘modified holonephridia’ than the usual type (with preseptal funnels). For more details, see Julka (1988: 367).

Lenogaster (?) *parva* Fedarb, 1898

Dichogaster parvus Fedarb, 1898b: 449.

Trigaster parva (Fedarb): Michaelsen 1900a: 334.

Eudichogaster parva (Fedarb): Michaelsen 1903a: 109.

Eudichogaster parvus (Fedarb): Stephenson 1923: 415.

Lenogaster (?) *parvus* (Fedarb): Gates 1940a: 198.

Type locality. Dehradun, Uttarakhand State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remarks. So far known only from the type locality. Based on the existing literature, Julka (1988a) provided a description of *L. parva*, but he stated that the description of the species is inadequate and perhaps partially incorrect. He also pointed out that “if the location of califerous glands in the original description of *parva* was correctly assigned by Fedarb, in that case it does not belong to *Lenogaster*”. Extensive collection is required from the type locality to determine its exact generic status (Julka 1988a). For more information, see Julka (1988a).

According to International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 2012) Article 30.1.2, names ending in *-gaster* should be treated as feminine. Here, *parvus* is masculine, hence here we corrected it to the feminine ending as *Lenogaster parva*.

Octochaetoides (?) *castellanus* (Stephenson, 1917)

Octochaetus castellanus Stephenson, 1917: 407.

Octochaetus (*Octochaetoides*) *castellanus* Stephenson: Stephenson 1923: 376.

Octochaetoides castellanus (Stephenson): Gates 1962b: 211.

Octochaetoides (?) *castellanus* (Stephenson): Julka 1988a: 370.

Type locality. Castle Rock, Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ZSIC W134/1; BMNH 1933:5:25:877-80; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. We need to know more about its digestive and excretory systems, hence it is treated as a *species incertae sedis* (Julka 1988). For more details, see Julka (1988a: 371).

Octochaetoides (?) *kurmagarensis* Gates, 1945

Octochaetoides kurmagarensis Gates, 1945a: 82.

Octochaetoides (?) *kurmagarensis* (Gates): Julka 1988a: 371.

Octochaetoides kurmagarensis (Gates): Blakemore 2007a: 19.

Type locality. Kurmagar Island (Kurumagad or Koormagad Island), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality so far. More research is needed to understand its digestive and excretory systems, hence it is treated as a *species incertae sedis* (Julka 1988). For more information, see Julka (1988a: 372).

Octochaetoides (?) *raoi* Gates, 1945

Octochaetoides raoi Gates, 1945a: 85.

Octochaetoides (?) *raoi* (Gates), Julka 1988a: 372.

Type locality. Nandydroog (Nandi Hills), Karnataka State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality so far. We need to know more about its digestive and excretory systems, hence it is treated as a *species incertae sedis* (Julka 1988). For more details, see Julka (1988a: 373).

Family MEGASCOLECIDAE

Amyntas (?) *burliarensis* (Bourne, 1886)

Pericheta burliarensis Bourne, 1886: 667.

Pheretima burliarensis (Bourne): Michaelsen 1900a: 258.

Pericheta burliarensis (Bourne): Sims & Easton 1972: 224.

Amyntas (?) *burliarensis* (Bourne): Blakemore 2007a: 22.

Type locality. Burliar, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** ?; **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. If it is a pheretimoid, it is quite unrecognizable and the only evidence for recognition is gizzard at segment 10 and the presence of intestinal caeca in 26 (Gates 1937a). Sims & Easton (1972) commented “no information is available whether copulatory pouches are present in these worms”; hence the species could be assigned to *Amyntas*, *Metaphire* or *Pheretima*. But the type locality of this species is well outside the natural pheretimoid domain, thus if it belongs to any pheretimoids, definitely will be an exotic peregrine species (Narayanan et al. 2023a). As per Blakemore (2007b) it is possibly a synonym of *Amyntas rodericensis*.

Diporochoeta (?) *dorsochaeta* Jamieson, 1977

Diporochoeta (?) *dorsochaeta* Jamieson, 1977b: 480.

Diporochoeta (?) *dorsochaeta* Jamieson: Julka 1988a: 480.

Type locality. Gundar Shola, Tamil Nadu State, India; **Type depository.** Paris Museum AH320 (Holotype), AH321; BJ 1976.5.1-2; Paris Museum AH322 (Paratypes); **Distribution.** India; **Status.** Endemic.

Remark. Known only from the type locality. This is a species with meroic nephridial condition, but Jamieson (1977b) doubtfully assigned it to the holoic Australasian *Diporochoeta*. According to Julka (1988a) meroic *dorsochaeta* with tubular prostate is assignable to *Celeriella* with oesophagus possessing a single gizzard and calciferous

lamellae in segments 13-14 but without discrete calciferous glands and intestinal typhlosole. For more information see Julka (1988a: 368).

DISCUSSION

The present study reveals a high diversity of earthworms in the South Asia-Myanmar region. The total number of earthworm species recorded from the region is 698 species/subspecies (predominantly represented by native species) belonging to 78 genera (including a genus regarded as *incertae sedis*) and 9 families (Appendix 1). Of these, 594 species (85%) are endemic, 63 species (9%) are exotic, the rest are sub-endemic, native peregrine and species of unknown status (Fig. 3). Despite making up only a small fraction (4.7%) of the world's surface, the South Asian region including Myanmar is home to about 10% of world's known earthworm fauna. Family Megascolecidae is the most dominant with 336 species/subspecies (48.14%), followed by Acanthodrilidae and Moniligastridae comprising 174 (24.93%) and 129 (18.48%) species/subspecies respectively. Together these three families contributed about 91.55% species/subspecies reported from the region. Families Lumbricidae and Ocnerothrilidae are represented by 22 and 17 species respectively, whereas rest of the families are having species within the single digit number (Fig. 4). Families Acanthodrilidae and Megascolecidae showed highest number of genera, 28 and 24 respectively. Followed by Ocnerothrilidae and Lumbricidae, 9 genera each (Fig. 5). Among the 78 genera recorded *Drawida* (107 spp.) is the most speciose genus, followed by *Eutyphoeus* and *Megascolex* (69 spp. each), *Amyntas* and *Perionyx* are represented by 59 spp. each (Appendix 1). Of the 78 genera reported, 37 (47.43%) genera are endemic to South Asia-Myanmar, mainly to India, interestingly 19 of these are monotypic (Appendix 2). In rare monotypic genera, the extinction of one species leads to the extinction of their entire gene pool, hence they deserve priority for conservation (Julka et al. 2009).

The current distribution of exotics is heavily influenced by recent, historic and prehistoric hu-

Figure 3. Status of the species recorded from the South Asia-Myanmar region

man activities and commerce but the degree of regional endemism, generally depends on palaeogeological history and the extent of glaciation or volcanism (Stephenson 1930, Gates 1972, Blake-more 2009). The Indian Peninsula was formerly a part of the ancient supercontinent Gondwanaland, which never fully submerged under the ocean (Julka & Paliwal 2005a). Majority of the native genera evolved and developed in this area (Narayanan et al. 2023a). The ancestors of the present day native Indian earthworm genera were presumably carried with the drifted away Indian plate from the Gondwana supercontinent (Sims 1980). Hence, they show strong affinities with the earthworm fauna of the other parts of the disintegrated Gondwanan land masses, now forming distinct biogeographical regions (Julka & Paliwal 2005a). Even after the suture of Peninsular India with the Asian mainland, an exchange of earthworm fauna is believed to have taken place between the peninsula and the eastern Himalaya and northeast hills (Narayanan et al. 2023a). The Indian Peninsula received *Drawida* from Myanmar-Indochina region and diversified in the peninsular India, especially in the southern Western Ghats and gave rise to a sister genus *Moniligaster*. It appears that *Perionyx* supposed to have evolved in the Deccan region of peninsular India and migrated to the northeast hills and eastern Himalayan region in the geological past and species radiation happened in the eastern Himalaya, which is a region with considerable,

Figure 4. Species/subspecies diversity in various earthworm families of South Asia-Myanmar region

Figure 5. Generic diversity in South Asian-Myanmarese earthworm families

regular rainfall and high organic matter in the soil (Julka & Paliwal 1993). The present day earthworm fauna of South Asia can be categorized into three broad groups, i) the peninsular autochthonous elements derived from the older Gondwanan land fauna, ii) the younger intrusive elements from the Indo-Chinese and Malayan sub-regions that probably dispersed in to the Indian Peninsula

following collision of the Indian plate with Asia, and iii) the exotic peregrine species introduced into the region due to anthropogenic activities.

In South Asia, peninsular India is home to the bulk of the native genera, while southern portion of the peninsula is home to most monotypic genera (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a). Majority of the

South Asian earthworms are located in the undisturbed natural ecosystems of the Western Ghats, Sri Lanka, Himalaya (especially eastern Himalaya) and North-eastern Indian hills. These are recognized as part of the Western Ghats-Sri Lanka, Indo-Burma and Himalaya biodiversity 'hotspots' (Koeing 2016). In addition to these, portions of two more biodiversity hotspots, the Mountains of Central Asia (eastern Afghanistan) and Sundland (Nicobar Islands of India), comes under the political boundary of the South Asia (Koeing 2016), but these areas are not well explored for the earthworm fauna. The Western Ghats-Sri Lanka biodiversity hotspot is the mega earthworm diversity area within South Asian-Myanmar region. It is home to 48.71% of the earthworm species reported from the region.

Introduced exotic species represent 9% of the known earthworm fauna of South Asia (Fig. 3). A total of 63 exotic earthworm species belonging to 8 families: Moniligastridae, Acanthodrilidae, Benhamiidae, Eudrilidae, Lumbricidae, Megascolecidae, Ocnerodrilidae and Rhinodrilidae have been reported from the region (Appendix 3). They might have been introduced into the region, presumably by man and other agencies (Julka 1988, 2014, Julka & Paliwal 2005b, Julka et al. 2009). Now, exotic species have successfully established their colonies in disturbed habitats following deforestation and intensive cultivation; which show their inherent ability to withstand disturbance and interference (Julka & Paliwal 2005b). The Holarctic Lumbricidae, South American Rhinodrilidae, African Eudrilidae and Benhamiidae families are exotic to the South Asia-Myanmar region. Meanwhile, a few Central Asian native peregrine lumbricid species have been recorded from Afghanistan, and several other peregrine lumbricids can be recorded from the Afghanistan and Balochistan, which fall within the Palaearctic region. The Himalayan mountain range form the southern boundary of the Palaearctic realm, hence it shares similarities in climate, flora and various fauna, but no endemic lumbricid earthworm has been recorded from there (Narayanan et al. 2023a).

First record of the African *Eudrilus eugeniae* from India is reported by Fedarb (1898a), even though, only recently it has established its colonies in different parts of South Asia. This happened mainly due to escapees from the vermin-composting facilities. South Asia has been an important political as well as trade center for millennia hence presence of many further exotic species from the region can be probable. Among the 698 species, 16 are considered as native peregrine and are widely distributed within the region, especially in India. Just like exotic species, native peregrines also can withstand disturbed conditions. Common among these are *Drawida nepalensis*, *Lampito mauritii*, *Malabaria levis*, *Octochaetona beatrix*, *Perionyx excavatus*, *Ramiella bishambari*, etc. (Narayanan et al. 2023a). At the same instance many native peregrine species have become widespread peregrine species around the globe by human transportation (e.g. *Perionyx excavatus*, *Lampito mauritii*, etc.). Both India and China have long and diverse histories of cultural exchange and are sources of several peregrine earthworm species (Blakemore 2009).

The number of earthworm species reported from different countries within South Asia-Myanmar region varies considerably. Certain countries are under-represented in the existing data and it is due to inadequacy of proper surveys and studies. In the South Asian-Myanmar region, India has the highest richness of species (503 species) of these 384 species are strictly endemic to India, followed by Myanmar with 208 species (107 endemics *sensu stricto*) and Sri Lanka 81 species (58 endemics *s.s.*) and the lowest is from the Maldives (2 species) (Table 2). Meanwhile, there are another 44 species found endemic to the South Asia-Myanmar area, but have been distributed in two or more countries of the region. The big gaps in the earthworm species diversity status in different countries of the region are mainly due to the lack of studies, difference in exploration rate, geographical location, habitat diversity etc. India is the third most earthworm-rich country in the world (Narayanan et al. 2023a). The Indian earthworm fauna shows high diversity which is

essentially due to the paleoecological, diverse physicogeographical features, drastically varying climatic zones, availability of different types of habitats with varied and distinct ecological niches.

Native earthworm species of India are mainly associated with forests (Narayanan *et al.* 2023a), which are among the most threatened ecosystems today (Myers 1983, Mudappa & Raman 2010). Compared to other South Asian countries, India is the only country that has maintained active studies on earthworm fauna even after independence. However, according to Narayanan *et al.* (2023a), taxonomic studies on earthworms are still uneven across most states, and union territories of India. Whereas not much works are happening in the countries such as Maldives, Sri Lanka, Bhutan, Afghanistan *etc.*

The Maldives is the least-studied country in the region with regard to earthworm fauna. Only one study is available on earthworms of this island country, that itself got published 123 years ago by Beddard (1903). Being an oceanic coral island group, no native earthworms are expected from the Maldives, though a serious collection may yield many exotic and native peregrine species. Thorough collection may yield many newer reports and new species from the forests, grasslands and various habitats of Bhutan, which is not systematically sampled for earthworms during the last 150+ years.

Only three works are available on the earthworm fauna of Afghanistan (Omodeo 1959, 1962, Aminjan *et al.* 2021). Normally, the family Lumbricidae is alien to the Indian subcontinent. However, owing to its proximity to Central Asia, many Central Asian local peregrine lumbricid species can be expected from Afghanistan in addition to the two Central Asian native lumbricid species reported so far (Omodeo 1959, 1962).

Many recent studies are made available on the earthworm fauna of Bangladesh (Reynolds 1994, Reynolds *et al.* 1995, Das & Reynolds 2003, Bahar *et al.* 2015). But meticulous survey in the south eastern portion, especially the Chittagong Hill Tracts in the Indo-Burma biodiversity hotspot region may yield many new records and new species, since its close proximity to Myanmar.

Mustafa *et al.* (2023) stated that 31 species are known from Pakistan, but in the present study we were able to compile 42 species from the country. But no serious studies have been conducted in Pakistan since independence, and most of the studies or reports after independence actually use old classification and already existing data. Interestingly, all the available literature on the earthworms of Pakistan is from the Punjab province, the largest province Balochistan, Sind and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are not represented in any studies. Since Balochistan is close to Iran and Afghanistan, many native lumbricids species can be expected from this region.

Table 2. Number of families, genera, species and endemic species reported from various countries of South Asia-Myanmar region

Country	Families	Genera	Species	Endemic (<i>Sensu stricto</i>)
Afghanistan	2	8	13	Nil
Bangladesh	7	14	34	Nil
Bhutan	3	6	7	Nil
India	9	75	503	384
Maldives	1	2	2	Nil
Nepal	5	11	18	1
Pakistan	7	18	42	Nil
Sri Lanka	8	20	81	58
Myanmar	9	38	208	107
South Asia-Myanmar	9	78	698	-

CONCLUSION

As per Blakemore (2025), there are currently about 7,000 species of earthworms in the world, and the probable global earthworm diversity is estimated to be 30,000–35,000 species (Decaëns *et al.* 2024). Many new species are being discovered and reported from South Asia-Myanmar region, predominantly from India. Hence, further detailed studies are urgently needed in view of the current pace of population growth, urbanization and landuse changes in the region. Especially in the rugged hilly terrains of Afghanistan, Balochistan and the forested areas of Bhutan and Nepal. Resumption of taxonomic studies of the earthworm fauna of Myanmar and Sri Lanka may unbox several new species from there. The data presented here in this work can serve as a basis for further investigations on the countries in the region.

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Appendix 1. Taxonomic composition of earthworm species found in South Asia including Myanmar

Order	Family	Genus	Species	Percentage		
MONILIGASTRIDA	MONILIGASTRIDAE	1. <i>Desmogaster</i>	4	0.57		
		2. <i>Drawida</i>	107	15.33		
		3. <i>Hastirogaster</i>	2	0.29		
		4. <i>Moniligaster</i>	16	2.29		
CRASSICLITELLATA	ACANTHODRILIDAE	5. <i>Bahlia</i>	1	0.14		
		6. <i>Calebiella</i>	1	0.14		
		7. <i>Chaetocotoides</i>	1	0.14		
		8. <i>Diplocardia</i> ?	1	0.14		
		9. <i>Eudichogaster</i>	6	0.86		
		10. <i>Eutyphoeus</i>	69	9.89		
		11. <i>Herbettodrilus</i>	1	0.14		
		12. <i>Hoplochaetella</i>	20	2.87		
		13. <i>Karmiella</i>	2	0.29		
		14. <i>Konkadrilus</i>	6	0.86		
		15. <i>Kotegeharia</i>	1	0.14		
		16. <i>Lenogaster</i>	8	1.15		
		17. <i>Mallehulla</i>	1	0.14		
		18. <i>Microscolex</i>	2	0.29		
		19. <i>Octochaetoides</i>	4	0.57		
		20. <i>Octochaetona</i>	15	2.15		
		21. <i>Octonochaeta</i>	1	0.14		
		22. <i>Parryodrilus</i>	1	0.14		
		23. <i>Pellogaster</i>	3	0.43		
		24. <i>Priodochaeta</i>	1	0.14		
		25. <i>Priodoscolex</i>	2	0.29		
		26. <i>Ramiella</i>	5	0.72		
		27. <i>Rillogaster</i>	2	0.29		
		28. <i>Scolioscolides</i>	1	0.14		
		29. <i>Senapatiella</i>	3	0.43		
		30. <i>Shimodrilus</i>	2	0.29		
		31. <i>Travoscolides</i>	4	0.57		
		32. <i>Wahoscolex</i>	10	1.43		
			ALMIDAE	33. <i>Glyphidrilus</i>	11	1.58
			BENHAMIIDAE	34. <i>Dichogaster</i>	5	0.72
			EUDRILIDAE	35. <i>Eudrilus</i>	1	0.14
			LUMBRICIDAE	36. <i>Allolobophora</i>	1	0.14
		37. <i>Aporrectodea</i>	5	0.72		
		38. <i>Bimastos</i>	3	0.43		
		39. <i>Dendrobaena</i>	4	0.57		
		40. <i>Eisenia</i>	2	0.29		
		41. <i>Eiseniella</i>	1	0.14		
		42. <i>Lumbricus</i>	3	0.43		
		43. <i>Octolasion</i>	2	0.29		
		44. <i>Perelia</i>	1	0.14		
	MEGASCOLECIDAE	45. <i>Aiyeriella</i>	2	0.29		
		46. <i>Amynthas</i>	59	8.45		
		47. <i>Argilophilus</i>	41	5.87		
		48. <i>Barogaster</i>	3	0.43		
		49. <i>Celeriella</i>	7	1.00		
		50. <i>Comarodrilus</i>	1	0.14		

		51. <i>Dashiella</i>	1	0.14
		52. <i>Diporochaeta</i> ?	1	0.14
		53. <i>Kanchuria</i>	10	1.43
		54. <i>Lampito</i>	8	1.15
		55. <i>Lenoscolex</i>	2	0.29
		56. <i>Megascolex</i>	69	9.89
		57. <i>Metaphire</i>	20	2.87
		58. <i>Nellogaster</i>	1	0.14
		59. <i>Nelloscolex</i>	3	0.43
		60. <i>Notoscolex</i>	24	3.44
		61. <i>Perionyx</i>	59	8.45
		62. <i>Pheretima</i>	2	0.29
		63. <i>Pithemera</i>	1	0.14
		64. <i>Planapheretima</i>	1	0.14
		65. <i>Polypheretima</i>	2	0.29
		66. <i>Pontodrilus</i>	2	0.29
		67. <i>Tonoscolex</i>	17	2.58
		68. <i>Troyia</i>	1	0.14
	OCNERODRILIDAE	69. <i>Aphanascus</i>	1	0.14
		70. <i>Curgiona</i>	1	0.14
		71. <i>Deccania</i>	1	0.14
		72. <i>Eukerria</i>	2	0.29
		73. <i>Gordiodrilus</i>	1	0.14
		74. <i>Malabaria</i>	4	0.57
		75. <i>Nematogenia</i>	1	0.14
		76. <i>Ocnerodrilus</i>	1	0.14
		77. <i>Thatonia</i>	5	0.72
	RHINODRILIDAE	78. <i>Pontoscolex</i>	1	0.14
2	9	78	698	100

Appendix 2. Distribution of monotypic earthworm genera in different regions of South Asia

Sl. No.	Genus	Country	Region
1	<i>Aphanascus</i>	India	Palakkad Gap (Kerala)
2	<i>Bahlia</i>	India	Middle Gangetic Plains
3	<i>Calebiella</i>	India	Middle Gangetic Plains
4	<i>Chaetocotoides</i>	India	Western Ghats (Panchgani Hills - Maharashtra)
5	<i>Comarodrilus</i>	India	West Coast Plains (Kerala)
6	<i>Curgiona</i>		Western Ghats and Coastal Plains (Goa and Karnataka)
7	<i>Dashiella</i>	India	Western Ghats (Khandala Hills - Maharashtra)
8	<i>Deccania</i>	India	Deccan Plateau (Central and Eastern)
9	<i>Herbettodrilus</i>	India	Western Ghats (Karnataka)
10	<i>Kotegeharia</i>	India	Eastern foot hills of Western Ghats (Karnataka)
11	<i>Mallehulla</i>		Western Ghats and Southern Plateau (Karnataka and Kerala)
12	<i>Nellogaster</i>	Sri Lanka	Western Province
13	<i>Octochaetoides</i>	India	West Coast Plains
14	<i>Octonochaeta</i>	India	Southern Deccan Plateau (Andhra Pradesh and Telangana)
15	<i>Parryodrilus</i>	India	Western Ghats (Kerala)
16	<i>Priodochaeta</i>	India	Western Ghats (Niligiri Hills - Tamil Nadu)
17	<i>Progizzardus</i>	India	Western Ghats (Kerala)
18	<i>Scolioscolides</i>	India, Nepal	Himalaya east of Darjeeling Hills
19	<i>Troyia</i>	India	Western Ghats (Palani Hills – Tamil Nadu)

Appendix 3. List of exotic earthworm species reported from South Asia-Myanmar region

Family	Species
MONILIGASTRIDAE	1. <i>Drawida barwelli</i>
	2. <i>Drawida japonica</i>
ACANTHODRILIDAE	3. <i>Microscolex dubius</i>
	4. <i>Microscolex phosphoreus</i>
BENHAMIIDAE	5. <i>Dichogaster affinis</i>
	6. <i>Dichogaster annae</i>
	7. <i>Dichogaster bolau</i>
	8. <i>Dichogaster modiglianii</i>
	9. <i>Dichogaster saliens</i>
EUDRILIDAE	10. <i>Eudrilus eugeniae</i>
LUMBRICIDAE	11. <i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>
	12. <i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>
	13. <i>Aporrectodea jassyensis</i>
	14. <i>Aporrectodea longa</i>
	15. <i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>
	16. <i>Aporrectodea trapezoides</i>
	17. <i>Bimastos eiseni</i>
	18. <i>Bimastos parvus</i>
	19. <i>Bimastos rubidus</i>
	20. <i>Dendrobaena hortensis</i>
	21. <i>Dendrobaena byblica</i>
	22. <i>Dendrobaena octaedra</i>
	23. <i>Eisenia andrei</i>
	24. <i>Eisenia fetida</i>
	25. <i>Eiseniella tetraedra</i>
	26. <i>Lumbricus castaneus</i>
	27. <i>Lumbricus rubellus</i>
	28. <i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>
	29. <i>Octolasion cyaneum</i>
30. <i>Octolasion lacteum</i>	
MEGASCOLECIDAE	31. <i>Amyntas alexandri</i>
	32. <i>Amyntas aspergillum</i>
	33. <i>Amyntas corticis</i>
	34. <i>Amyntas gracilis</i>
	35. <i>Amyntas hupeiensis</i>
	36. <i>Amyntas incongruus</i>
	37. <i>Amyntas minimus</i>
	38. <i>Amyntas morrisoni</i>
	39. <i>Amyntas pallidus</i>
	40. <i>Amyntas papulosus</i>

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41. *Amyntas robustus*
 42. *Amyntas rodericensis*
 43. *Metaphire agrestis*
 44. *Metaphire anomala*
 45. *Metaphire bahli*
 46. *Metaphire birmanica*
 47. *Metaphire californica*
 48. *Metaphire houletti*
 49. *Metaphire peguana*
 50. *Metaphire planata*
 51. *Metaphire posthuma*
 52. *Pheretima darnleiensis*
 53. *Pheretima vungtauensis*
 54. *Pithemera bicincta*
 55. *Polypheretima elongata*
 56. *Polypheretima taprobanae*
 57. *Pontodrilus litoralis*
 58. *Eukerria kuekenthali*
 59. *Eukerria saltensis*
 60. *Gordiodrilus elegans*
 61. *Nematogenia panamaensis*
 - OCNERODRILIDAE 62. *Ocnerodrilus occidentalis*
 - RHINODRILIDAE 63. *Pontoscolex corethrurus*
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